

**Equipping Sports Higher Education Institutions with
Intersectional, Innovative, and Inclusive
Gender Equality Plans**

D4.2 Report on the implementation of the institutional roadmaps, lessons learned and final 4I-GEPs

South-East European Research Centre

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Steps for the development of the 4I-GEPs

List of Acronyms

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
GA	Grounding Action
GBV	Gender-Based Violence
GE	Gender Equality
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
IOs	Implementing Organisations
4I-GEPs	Innovative, Intersectional, Inclusive and Impactful Gender Equality Plans

The SUPPORTER project

SUPPORTER, “SecUring sPORTs Education thRough innovative and inclusive Gender Equality Plans”, is an EU-funded project running from April 2023 until September 2025. Launched on 19 April 2023, it aims to support eight sports higher education institutions from Central and Eastern Europe in developing their own intersectional, innovative, inclusive and impactful Gender Equality Plans which explicitly address gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

Through mutual learning and interactive exchanges, the project will seek to:

1. Identify and document systemic challenges faced by sports higher education institutions in advancing gender equality and eradicating gender-based violence.
2. Develop activities tailored to each partner institution.
3. Strengthen the sports institutions’ organisational capacity to address gender equality with an intersectional approach.
4. Foster an inclusive institutional culture by developing mutual-learning processes.
5. Strengthen networking and exchange among sports institutions and with communities of practice.
6. Foster gender-related institutional, sustainable, transformative changes in the sports institutions with a specific attention on the challenge of gender-based violence -thus ultimately fostering the institutions and their Gender Equality Plans’ inclusiveness and the overall adherence to intersectionality.

While initially partnering with eight institutions, the SUPPORTER project aspires to target and reach the wider sports ecosystem and its various organisations in Central and Eastern Europe and beyond, and in the long run contribute to wide societal changes.

Project Partners

<p>SCIENCE CONNECT YOUR PARTNER IN SCIENCE</p>	European Science Foundation (ESF)
<p>UNIVERSITY OF GOTHENBURG</p>	Göteborgs Universitet (UGOT), Sweden
<p>SOUTH-EAST EUROPEAN RESEARCH CENTRE</p>	Kentro Erevnon Notioanatolikis Evropis Astiki mi Kerdoskopiki Etaireia, The South-East European Research Centre (SEERC), Greece
<p>УНИВЕРЗИТЕТ У БАЊОЈ ЛУЦИ UNIVERSITY OF BANJA LUKA</p>	Univerzitet u Banjoj Luci (UNIBL), Bosnia & Herzegovina
<p>University of Ljubljana Faculty of Sport</p>	Univerza v Ljubljani (UL), Slovenia
<p>UNIVERZITA KARLOVA</p>	Univerzita Karlova (CU), Czechia
<p>НАЦИОНАЛНА СПОРТНА АКАДЕМИЈА "ВАСИЛ ЛЕВСКИ"</p>	Natsionalna Sportna Akademiya Vassil Levski (NSA), Bulgaria
<p>LIETUVOS SPORTO UNIVERSITETAS</p>	Lietuvos Sporto Universitetas (LSU), Lithuania
<p>Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara</p>	Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara (UVT), Romania
	Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport (GSTUPES), Georgia
	Universitatea de Stat de Educație Fizică și Sport (USEFS), Moldova

Summary

This deliverable documents the second and third phases of the SUPPORTER project: the update and implementation of the institutional roadmaps, and the development of new intersectional, inclusive, innovative and impactful Gender Equality Plans (4I-GEPs). Over 16 months, the eight sports higher education institutions involved in the project leveraged knowledge gained through tailored training, collective and bilateral mutual learning, and continuous mentoring by the core team to carry out their Grounding Actions, update their roadmaps to reflect emerging needs and insights, and prepare the ground for sustainable institutional change. Guided by iterative feedback, roadmap implementation focused on raising awareness of gender+ equality, improving data collection with an intersectional approach, dedicating institutional resources, addressing gender-based violence (GBV), embedding gender into research and curricula, and promoting inclusive organisational cultures. Institutions faced challenges such as low awareness, limited resources and resistance, but adapted effectively through stakeholder engagement and ongoing support from the project's capacity-building activities.

Building on this process, each institution co-designed and formally adopted its own 4I-GEP. These new plans go beyond compliance with minimum EU requirements by explicitly mainstreaming GBV prevention and response as a core institutional priority, integrating intersectionality into data collection, awareness-raising, teaching and research, and tailoring gender equality actions to the specific realities of sports academia, where stereotypes, hierarchical structures and male-dominated leadership remain entrenched. By embedding inclusivity, innovation, intersectionality and impact into governance structures, curricula and professional training pathways, the 4I-GEPs position sports universities as frontrunners of cultural change. Together, they represent a decisive step towards sustainable transformation in sports academia and a meaningful contribution to the wider European sports ecosystem.

Highlights

- Roadmaps were implemented as **dynamic tools**, updated through feedback, stakeholder engagement and capacity-building.
- **Training, mentoring and mutual learning** supported IOs in addressing challenges and shaping their Grounding Actions.
- **Intersectionality** was mainstreamed in data collection, awareness, teaching and research, marking a major achievement across all institutions.
- The final GEPs embed **inclusivity, innovation, intersectionality and impact**, moving beyond EC compliance toward sustainable change.
- **Gender-based violence** was established as a core priority, with new protocols, reporting systems, awareness campaigns and training.
- **Tailoring the GEPs to the sports environment** proved especially powerful, addressing stereotypes, leadership imbalances and coach–student dynamics, while leveraging universities' role as multipliers for cultural change across the wider sports ecosystem

Introduction

The SUPPORTER project aims to foster gender-related institutional, transformative and sustainable changes in the sports higher education institutions with specific attention to the challenge of gender-based violence (GBV) through the development of inclusive, innovative, intersectional and impactful (4I) Gender Equality Plans (GEPs).

The transformation of existing institutional GEPs into 4I-GEPs was neither a solitary nor an isolated process. Over the course of 2.5 years, the Implementing Organisations (IOs) collaborated closely with their SUPPORTER colleagues and with their local stakeholders to achieve this goal through three distinct phases:

1. Co-design of institutional roadmaps. The IOs collaborated with the core team to co-design eight individual roadmaps, grounded in a shared understanding of key concepts and a common structure. This structure was based on a template developed by the core team and harmonised with the European Institute for Gender Equality's (EIGE) six steps of the GEPs, and including the European Commission's mandatory and thematic GEP elements, with particular emphasis on GBV. Taking into account the institutional environments and the challenges identified during the pre-design stage, each roadmap was tailored to address context-specific needs. The steps followed, as well as similarities and divergences in the initial versions of the roadmaps, are described in Deliverable D4.1 of the SUPPORTER project [available [in Zenodo](#)].

2. Implementation of the institutional roadmaps. Over 16 months, the IOs carried out a set of activities outlined in their roadmap's Grounding Actions. Recognising that the roadmaps are living documents rather than static plans, this phase also involved updates of the original roadmaps. Initiated approximately ten months into the implementation period, these revisions enabled IOs to adjust their plans in response to emerging needs and insights not apparent at the design stage, and to reconstruct their Grounding Actions in order to pave the way toward the new 4I-GEPs and broader institutional change.

3. Co-design of the 4I-GEPs. Building on the foundation laid during the roadmap implementation, as well as the knowledge gained through the project's capacity building scheme, extended networking within the SUPPORTER network, and consultation with the core team, each IO developed their new 4I-GEP, which has been formally endorsed at institutional level. These plans, tailored to the sports environment and with a continued focus on GBV, embody the principles of inclusivity, innovation, intersectionality, and impact.

Key enablers of the process were the training, mutual learning, and monitoring and mentoring schemes that accompanied the entire cycle of roadmap development, implementation, and the design of the new plans. The training programme provided IOs with a structured pathway through the six steps of a GEP, ensuring that roadmap design and later implementation were grounded in both theory and practice. Delivered through three progressive modules—basic, intermediate, and advanced—the training equipped participants with conceptual knowledge, practical tools, and context-specific skills for sports higher education, while also operationalising the 4Is framework. Regular collective and bilateral mutual learning sessions consolidated knowledge gained from training and fostered the exchange of ideas, promising practices, and pitfalls to avoid through practical exercises. Finally, continuous support through monitoring and mentoring sessions helped to surface hidden resistances, strengthen adaptability and resilience in the face of challenges, and keep institutions on track with their plans while deepening their understanding of what is needed to promote sustainable change.

As the first phase was documented in D4.1, the present deliverable focuses on the two subsequent phases. Part One describes the process, steps, and collaborative work undertaken by the IOs and the core team to update the institutional roadmaps. Part Two delves into the implementation of these roadmaps. Finally, Part Three outlines the development of the new 4I-GEPs and looks ahead to the future of gender equality in the participating organisations.

1. Update of the institutional roadmaps

Dynamic in nature, the institutional roadmaps were never intended to remain unchanged throughout their 16-month implementation. Their design anticipated iterative adaptation to enable IOs to recalibrate strategies in response to emerging needs and ensure that Grounding Actions remained feasible, contextually relevant, and impactful. A significant area of shared advancement across institutions concerned the progressive understanding and incorporation of intersectionality, both in the conceptualisation of gender and in the promotion of gender equality. This development was informed by targeted training, capacity-building activities, and mutual learning exchanges. Moreover, the roadmap updates provided an opportunity for IOs to engage in systematic reflection on the initial stages of implementation, to identify forms of resistance and practical constraints encountered, and to adapt their approaches accordingly so as to safeguard both the delivery of planned activities and their contribution to the formulation of the 4I-GEPs.

1.1. The process

The update process had been introduced to the IOs from the beginning of the project, discussed in detail during the mid-term progress meeting, and revisited during the mutual learning online sessions in autumn 2024. In December 2024, a revised roadmap template was presented to the IOs and discussed collectively during an online Mutual Learning Workshop. This new template (Annex I of this deliverable) guided the update process, requiring each IO to provide a summary of the changes introduced and the rationale behind them—ensuring that at least one change integrated an intersectional dimension. The updated template also included the revised version of the roadmap and a transitional Grounding Action describing the internal process for designing, drafting, and formally endorsing the new institutional GEP.

Each IO was invited to reflect on their progress during the first ten months of implementation, draw on the new insights and knowledge acquired through capacity-building and networking activities, and adjust their Grounding Actions accordingly to maximise effectiveness and impact. The revisions drew heavily on knowledge gained during the training programme, particularly Module II, which focused on analysing the institutional status quo, identifying objectives, and operationalising the 4Is in the sports context. The update process was carried out through extensive consultation, both with the core team and with internal stakeholders. With the core team, this was carried out during the Monitoring and Mentoring meetings; within the institutional context, the form of the consultations ranged from individual meetings to workshops or focus groups with pre-identified stakeholders. In these forums, IOs discussed their institutions' specific needs in advancing gender equality, with a particular emphasis on GBV and the sports education environment.

The outcome of these consultations informed the first draft of the updated roadmap for each IO. At least one dedicated meeting was then held with the mentoring team and each IO to review the draft, provide feedback, and ensure that all necessary components were included. This iterative process enabled IOs to refine their documents further, before finalising the updated versions of their institutional roadmaps.

1.2. The roadmap template

The updated roadmap template was structured in three distinct parts, each serving a complementary purpose in ensuring coherence, accountability, and a smooth transition toward the development of the 4I-GEPs.

1. Summary of changes

This section provided a concise overview of the adjustments made to the original roadmap. IOs were asked to specify what had changed, why the changes were necessary, and how they improved the roadmap's relevance and feasibility. The rationale could include lessons learned during the first ten months of implementation, insights gained through training and mutual learning activities, or challenges encountered such as resistance, time constraints, or resource limitations. This part served as a transparent record of the evolution of the roadmap and allowed both IOs and the core team to track the trajectory of institutional learning and adaptation.

2. The updated roadmap

This part consisted of the revised version of the institutional roadmap itself. It presented the Grounding Actions in their updated form, including their timelines, responsibilities, and indicators of progress. The aim was to provide IOs with a clear and practical tool to continue implementation over the remaining period. The updated roadmap also highlighted changes within the text of the GAs, so that the evolution of activities was easy to identify. This ensured continuity with the original version, while at the same time reflecting the dynamism of the process.

3. Transitional Grounding Action

The final part of the updated template introduced a new, transitional Grounding Action to describe the internal process through which each IO would design, draft, and formally endorse its 4I-GEP. This action was forward-looking, ensuring that roadmap implementation would naturally lead into GEP development within the project's lifespan. IOs were asked to outline the steps of this process, such as stakeholder consultations, internal discussions, and drafting stages, as well as to specify the actors involved. The action required also the identification of the body responsible for formal approval of the new GEP and the estimated time that was required for completion. This element guaranteed that the transition from roadmap to 4I-GEP was realistic, timely, institutionally grounded, and adequately resourced.

1.3. Updated versions of institutional roadmaps

The following section outlines the updated versions of the eight institutional roadmaps developed by the implementing organisations with the support of the core team. The full texts are provided in the Annexes of this deliverable. The updates are summarised in the opening section and highlighted within the text of the Grounding Actions. As implementation progressed, further adjustments were made in response to evolving challenges and emerging opportunities. This flexibility ensures that the roadmaps and, subsequently, the GEPs remain relevant and effective instruments of change.

University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (UNIBL)

University of Ljubljana, Faculty of sport (UL)

Charles University (Faculty of Physical Education and Sport)

National Sports Academy “Vassil Levski” (NSA)

Lithuanian Sports University (LSU)

Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara (UVT)

Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport (GSTUPES)

State University of Physical Education and Sport (USEFS)

2. Implementation of the institutional roadmaps

At the stage of roadmap co-creation, the IOs participated in a self-assessment procedure which, together with the drafting of the Grounding Actions, revealed common gaps, recurrent themes, and anticipated challenges for the implementation period. This section of the deliverable provides an overview of the implementation of the roadmaps across the participating IOs.

The analysis is structured around the recurrent themes identified in deliverable D4.1, which emerged from the comparative assessment of all IOs during the first project phase and provide a conceptual framework for evaluating implementation. These are the following: **building fundamental knowledge on gender+ equality in sports, increasing data collection on gender** (including an intersectional approach), **dedicating resources on the promotion of gender equality, focus on gender-based violence, embedding gender in research and education, and promoting work-life balance and organisational culture through interconnected priorities**. For each theme, the analysis considers four key dimensions: (i) the actions taken by IOs as part of their Roadmaps, (ii) persisting gaps and difficulties compared to those initially identified, (iii) lessons learned by both IOs and the core team during implementation, and (iv) which anticipated challenges materialised, whether new challenges emerged, and how these were addressed. This approach allows a **comprehensive assessment across all IOs**, highlighting patterns, best practices, and areas needing further attention.

The methodology for this analysis combined multiple sources of information. First, all the **Learning Diaries 2,3 and 4**, namely the internal self-reflection tool used by IOs on a regular basis to capture progress in roadmap implementation, adjustments needed, and transferable practices, were analysed. In addition, a dedicated Learning Diary 6 was designed by the core team and completed by each IO, documenting the specific actions undertaken during roadmap implementation, reflections on outcomes, and perceived challenges. Second, complementary data through **monitoring and mentoring sessions, and mutual learning activities**, which provided further insights from both IOs and the core team. The collected information was synthesised using the thematic clustering of D4.1. This allows for cross-cutting insights and offers a consolidated overview of the progress, roadblocks, and learning emerging from the roadmap implementation process. Finally, the cross-cutting challenges that emerged, both anticipated and unpredicted, together with the implemented solutions, are presented.

2.1. Building fundamental knowledge on gender+ equality

A central priority across all institutional roadmaps was to cultivate a shared understanding of gender+ equality and how inequalities manifest in the sports environment. To this end, each organisation introduced at least one awareness-raising Grounding Action at the very start of implementation, embedding activities addressed to both internal and external stakeholders. Awareness-raising activities were directly informed by Module I of the training, which introduced IOs to key concepts of gender equality, gender-based violence and institutional change. Where the baseline level of knowledge at institutional level appeared weaker, emphasis was placed on increasing the visibility of Gender Equality Plans and related gender mainstreaming activities, signalling that the promotion of gender equality was not simply a project output but an institutional commitment.

The activities implemented under this theme were diverse in form and focus. Some IOs opted for the format of interactive workshops and training sessions (CU, GSTUPES, UL); speeches and panel discussions (UL, SUPES, UNIBL, NSA); faculty-reserved briefings and presentations (NSA, UL); info days (GSTUPES, UVT, SUPES); or social media campaigns (LSU). These often combined sports activities with discussions on equality and inclusion and, in some cases, placed emphasis on tailored, context-specific training using role models to make gender debates more relatable (CU). Several institutions explored specific topics such as breaking gender stereotypes in sport (UNIBL, LSU, GSTUPES, CU), gender equality in recreational sport (UL), the role of GEPs in promoting a gender-inclusive culture in higher education sports institutions (SUPES, UL), inclusive physical education and sports ethics (LSU), women's leadership in sport and academia (CU), and the relationship between gender equality and fair competition (UVT, NSA). Across the consortium, outreach to both internal stakeholders (staff and students) and external stakeholders (sports federations, coaches, athletes, NGOs), either jointly or separately, was prioritised, with activities deliberately framed as highly visible.

From the implementation of awareness-raising actions, several common lessons emerged across IOs. First, the ability to combine SUPPORTER activities with existing institutional, national or international events greatly increased visibility and maximised impact. Synergies with prominent bodies such as national Olympic Committees, organisations on Continuing Education and sports organisations, alongside the presence of senior management as visible advocates, significantly enhanced both participation and legitimacy. Bringing together internal and external stakeholders created opportunities for collaborative engagement and clarified different roles and responsibilities. Well-organised and clearly structured events were also more effective in sustaining engagement, particularly when the objectives and expectations were made explicit. Formats that included inspiring role models, real-life testimonies and multimedia proved especially powerful in addressing sensitive topics and capturing attention. The inclusion of specialists, such as gender experts and practitioners, further enriched the discussions and lent authority to the events. Finally, the use of pre- and post-event questionnaires provided an effective way to measure impact, track increases in understanding and adapt subsequent activities to persisting or newly identified gaps.

2.2. Increasing data collection on gender, including an intersectional approach

Systematic data collection was among the most critical, cross-cutting gaps in the involved institutions. Thus, all IOs included at least one dedicated Grounding Action on data collection except UNIBL who, having already undertaken focus groups and surveys during the co-creation stage, chose to embed data collection within all other GAs, thereby ensuring that activities were informed by evidence and tailored to institutional needs. Across the consortium, the overarching aim was twofold: to establish a more accurate picture of gender representation and participation, and to capture perceptions of gender inequalities and gender-based violence, including through an intersectional lens.

The roadmap actions under this theme revealed both diversity and complementarity of approaches. Some institutions concentrated on perception surveys targeting students, staff and in some cases external stakeholders, designed to assess levels of awareness and attitudes towards gender equality in sport and, in certain cases, GBV and sexual harassment (CU, LSU, UVT, SUPES). To collect such data, reliance on existing and tested university tools was not always the preferred solution; the use of generic, university-wide questionnaires was sometimes abandoned in favour of faculty-specific

instruments that were piloted, revised on the basis of feedback, and redistributed to academic staff to capture the particular needs of the sports environment (CU). Others prioritised the development of gender-disaggregated statistical datasets, for example on recruitment, leadership and career progression, often building on existing HR and administrative systems (UL, NSA). Across cases, data collection was not conceived in isolation but closely interlinked with other grounding actions: perception surveys were conducted during outreach events, survey findings were fed back into training needs analyses, and statistical reviews informed the drafting of new policies and procedures.

Several lessons were drawn from these efforts. Early data collection confirmed that awareness of existing mechanisms for reporting gender-based violence and harassment was often very low, highlighting the need for more targeted dissemination and clearer communication of available channels (CU, LSU). Embedding surveys within broader awareness-raising activities proved more effective than running standalone questionnaires, as it increased participation and provided richer context for interpreting results (SUPES, CU). Interlinkages with other grounding actions also proved essential: data collection had the greatest impact when it directly informed awareness campaigns, training content or the drafting of institutional protocols (UL, NSA, GSTUPES). The process further underscored the value of inclusive and student-centred tools, adapted to the realities of younger participants, as well as the importance of covering intersectional dimensions such as disability, migration background or field of study. Notably, all institutions explicitly incorporated an intersectional approach, inspired by the capacity-building scheme of the SUPPORTER project and in particular the mutual learning workshop held in Thessaloniki in June 2024. Finally, the involvement of multiple stakeholders in the design and dissemination of surveys, from student unions to faculty representatives, was critical for building trust and broadening reach.

2.3. Dedicating resources on the promotion of gender equality

A recurring insight from the co-creation stage was that promoting gender equality required not only awareness and data but also dedicated institutional structures, roles and resources. Several IOs therefore introduced Grounding Actions designed to create or strengthen the organisational backbone for implementing their GEPs, ranging from new committees and contact points to communications strategies that ensure resources are used strategically and transparently.

The most visible expression of this commitment was the establishment of new, formal institutional bodies with a mandate for gender equality and the implementation of the GEP, approved by the competent institutional authorities (GSTUPES, SUPES, UL). In lieu of new structures, many institutions preferred to refine existing frameworks in order to be resource-efficient by refining their composition and responsibilities, thereby reinforcing expertise and authority while and avoid overlap or duplication of tasks. This often involved expanding or recalibrating ethics bodies (NSA) or HR systems (GSTUPES), redefining the role and job description of contact persons/ombudspersons with explicit responsibilities, reporting lines and proximity to students as well as staff (CU), and targeted recruitment and redistribution of tasks to secure motivated staff to take ownership over the longer term (UVT). Resource dedication was also tied to communication strategies, recognising that visibility and clarity function as institutional resources in their own right (NSA, SUPES, GSTUPES).

The roadmap implementation highlighted several dynamics that strengthen these arrangements. Early stakeholder involvement in newly created or reconfigured bodies increased legitimacy and effectiveness, especially when contact roles were clearly communicated at faculty level (CU). Aligning

ambitions with existing governance channels (e.g., ethics commissions, senate committees) helped consolidate responsibilities and reduce duplication (NSA, SUPES). Effectiveness depended not only on formal mandates but on continuous capacity building and peer learning—including training on ombudsperson work, social safety and GBV prevention (CU) and onboarding sessions for working-group members (UL). Taken together, these developments show that dedicating resources is not a one-off decision but an iterative process of embedding roles, structures and communication practices into the institutional fabric.

2.4. Focus on gender-based violence

Addressing GBV and sexual harassment was recognised as a core priority of the SUPPORTER project, with all roadmaps including at least one Grounding Action dedicated to this theme. The topic was also central in the training programme, particularly in Modules I and III, where IOs were introduced to the full conceptual scope of GBV and sexual harassment, as well as to practical tools for institutional response. These included, for example, the *UNISAFE protocol and toolkit*, the *7P model for addressing GBV in research-performing organisations*, and the application of an intersectional lens, such as guidance on supporting trans and non-binary people in academia. Building on this foundation, IOs were better equipped to design context-appropriate measures, ranging from reporting protocols and support services to awareness-raising initiatives and integration of GBV prevention into teaching and training.

Awareness-raising on GBV was often scheduled later in the implementation process, building on the earlier grounding actions of knowledge building and data collection, so that institutions could first establish a common baseline of understanding. The overarching aim was to create safe institutional environments, to establish or improve internal procedures for prevention and response, and to embed the topic within teaching, training and outreach activities.

Roadmap implementation under this theme combined three main strands of action. First, IOs worked on the development or revision of procedures for handling GBV and sexual harassment cases, ensuring that reporting channels were clarified and responsibilities defined. This included the adoption of formal protocols and procedures (UNIBL, SUPES, NSA, GSTUPES) and the introduction of confidential reporting and support bodies and policies (CU, UL, UNIBL, NSA). Second, institutions launched awareness-raising and training initiatives, designed to create safe spaces for discussion and to equip staff and students with the tools to recognise and address GBV. Examples included pilot trainings on social safety and GBV prevention for academic and non-academic staff (CU, UVT), lectures and workshops explicitly addressing GBV (UNIBL, LSU, GSTUPES), or seminars addressing GBV among other topics related to gender equality (UNIBL). Third, GBV was addressed through integration into curricula and professional training, such as workshops with PE teachers (LSU) inclusion of GBV prevention within a Social Security course, scheduled to become mandatory for all academic and non-academic staff (CU). In several cases, external expertise was sought to strengthen credibility and enrich the content of GBV-related training (UNIBL, CU, UVT).

The implementation of these actions yielded several important lessons. The most significant finding was that, in many institutions, even when procedures for reporting and addressing GBV were formally in place, staff and students often lacked awareness of how to access or use them. This highlighted a fundamental gap in communication of internal procedures. Clearly defined roles and visible reporting mechanisms emerged as key success factors for ensuring trust and accessibility. Institutions that

anchored their actions in consultation with external specialists and existing good practices advanced more quickly and with greater legitimacy. Pilot activities underlined the importance of monitoring impact: pre- and post-training surveys showed measurable increases in awareness, while pilot phases helped identify weaknesses and refine activities for greater efficiency. Engaging professional communities that shape student experience (such as coaches and teachers) proved especially effective for diffusion into daily practice. For many institutions, this was the first time GBV was discussed openly, underscoring the need for continuity and follow-up rather than one-off events. Finally, the formal approval of protocols by competent authorities emerged as essential for sustainability, moving GBV measures beyond awareness-raising toward embedded institutional governance.

2.5. Embedding gender in research and education

Rather than positioning gender as an ancillary concern, the roadmaps sought to make sure that it features as a cross-cutting element in shaping curricula and selecting topics for discussion and coursework, supervision and conducting research. Regarding the latter, effort was made to increase understanding of what “gender in research” means in practice, stepping away from the focus on gender balance towards integrating gender dimensions into research questions, design and methodology.

Implementation followed two complementary directions. On the teaching side, institutions revised curricula or introduced lectures and modules to address gender equality within sport-related disciplines, from philosophy and sociology courses to physical education and sports ethics (NSA, LSU, UVT, UNIBL). In several cases, equality was integrated into professional training formats and case-based teaching, enabling students to confront issues of gender norms and stereotypes in applied settings. An intersectional perspective was gradually introduced, with courses and modules increasingly considering how gender interacts with factors such as disability or migration background (UVT, LSU).

On the research side, institutions encouraged the uptake of gender-related thesis topics and supported staff and students in integrating equality dimensions into research design (CU, UL, LSU, UNIBL). In some cases, these efforts were reinforced through the adoption of guidelines aimed at promoting gender balance in academic projects (UL). For several institutions, this marked the first systematic attempt to embed gender considerations into research practice, signaling the beginning of a broader cultural shift in how research priorities are conceived and supervised.

The implementation of these actions underscored several important dynamics. Incremental curricular change proved particularly effective, as weaving gender issues into existing courses and modules facilitated continuity and normalisation. The extent to which students chose gender-sensitive thesis topics was closely linked to the capacity and motivation of supervisors, demonstrating that targeted staff development is indispensable. Practical, discipline-relevant examples were consistently more successful than abstract discussions in engaging students and linking equality principles to their professional trajectory. Overall, embedding gender in research and education emerged not as a discrete intervention but as a continuous process of curricular revision, staff support and cultural adaptation within academic communities.

2.6. Promoting work-life balance and organisational culture through interconnected priorities

Although explicit gaps around work-life balance were less prominent at the co-creation stage, several Grounding Actions targeted the wider organisational culture in which equality commitments are embedded. These actions focused on facilitating career continuity, fostering inclusive communication, revising institutional practices and ensuring that institutional environments support both staff and students in reconciling professional and personal responsibilities. The unifying aim was to address subtle but persistent barriers that shape participation and progression, while promoting a culture of fairness and transparency.

To achieve so, some institutions developed guidelines to support career continuity, for example by facilitating reintegration after career breaks and outlining best practices for staff returning to work (UNIBL, UL). Others worked through policy amendments and governance frameworks, introducing rules on gender-sensitive language in institutional documents, internal and external communication and academic texts. (NSA, UL, UVT, CU). In a similar fashion, a more inclusive institutional culture was pursued through the introduction of preferential working conditions for staff in defined cases, particularly those with family or disability responsibilities.

These actions underscored several dynamics. Efforts that were linked directly to existing HR and governance processes—such as career-break reintegration policies, ethics codes or institutional guidelines—proved more effective than standalone initiatives, as they were anchored in familiar procedures. The experience also demonstrated the value of intersectional approaches, recognising that measures on work-life balance and organisational culture affect staff and students differently depending on their gender, role or personal circumstances. Institutions benefited from peer learning and the adaptation of external models, drawing on documents from other universities as inspiration when drafting their own guidelines. The involvement of key stakeholders such as trade unions further enhanced legitimacy and fostered a sense of shared ownership. More broadly, the implementation showed that culture change is necessarily gradual: initiatives such as gender-sensitive language policies or stereotype-debunking campaigns require dialogue, monitoring and visibility of equality bodies to gain acceptance and to be sustained over time.

2.7. Cross-cutting challenges and solutions

The implementation of the institutional roadmaps confirmed that many of the challenges anticipated at the co-creation stage did indeed materialise, though in varying intensity across IOs. At the same time, new and unforeseen obstacles also emerged, often reflecting deeper structural or cultural barriers. The analysis shows that, while no single institution was immune from difficulties, IOs demonstrated considerable adaptability and creativity in developing mitigation strategies.

Lack of awareness and understanding was one of the most widely foreseen challenges, and it repeatedly surfaced in practice. Staff and students often had limited knowledge of basic gender equality concepts, and in some cases displayed discomfort or reluctance in discussing sensitive issues such as gender-based violence or inclusive language. IOs responded by embedding awareness-raising into existing institutional or national events, using trusted voices such as senior management or respected external actors (athletes, police representatives), and adopting iterative formats that gradually normalised discussion.

Lack of engagement and participation also proved pervasive. Staff workloads and teaching commitments limited availability for multi-hour workshops, while student participation was often low in activities not embedded within curricula. Mitigation strategies included shortening and rescheduling workshops to mid-semester periods, integrating activities into mandatory courses or high-visibility events, and relying on peer influence through student unions to increase turnout.

Insufficient data collection had been identified as a risk, and it materialised in the form of low survey response rates and reluctance to answer questions on sensitive topics such as GBV. IOs mitigated this by distributing surveys in class or during awareness events, clarifying confidentiality, and embedding data collection in institutional procedures such as gender audits. The SUPPORTER project's mutual learning workshop in Thessaloniki (June 2024) as well as the second training module on data also helped IOs to systematically integrate intersectionality into data collection tools, ensuring that gender data was analysed alongside dimensions such as disability, migration background or study field.

Validity of data and questionnaire design was less explicitly reported as a challenge, though some institutions noted that existing surveys did not capture faculty-specific needs. CU, for example, abandoned reliance on a university-wide instrument and designed a new faculty-level questionnaire on GBV and sexual harassment, revising it iteratively based on staff feedback. This adaptive approach helped to ensure more relevant and reliable findings.

Limited resources and expertise proved a significant barrier. Several IOs faced staff resignations (UVT) or budgetary constraints (UL, LSU, CU), limiting capacity to sustain roadmap actions. Mitigation focused on redistributing responsibilities, recruiting motivated new members, and ensuring management endorsement to secure protected time and micro-budgets. Where expertise was lacking, IOs turned to capacity-building, mentoring, and the involvement of external specialists.

Organisational and internal resistance emerged most visibly around inclusive language policies and GBV reporting systems. Some staff resisted changes to language use, and in certain institutions reluctance to discuss GBV openly persisted. IOs responded by formalising roles and procedures through senate or rectorate approvals, involving external experts to increase legitimacy, and using explanatory campaigns to reduce resistance. Integral to this response was the training on countering resistance which introduced the “*Realise–Reflect–Respond*” framework: (i) realise situations and arguments that commonly trigger resistance, (ii) reflect on the sentiments and dynamics behind them, and (iii) respond through targeted actions to avoid or mitigate escalation.

Communication and bureaucratic challenges were reported across institutions, particularly delays in policy approvals or coordination between departments. IOs sought to address these by aligning roadmap actions with existing governance processes (such as ethics commissions or senate committees), involving legal and HR staff early in design stages, and strengthening internal communication between units.

Finally, several **unanticipated challenges** emerged. Staff resignations disrupted continuity at UVT, polarised debates among students at NSA revealed the persistence of entrenched prejudices, and structural gender imbalances in student populations (NSA, GSTUPES) highlighted systemic constraints that cannot be resolved in the short term. These issues underline the importance of designing GEPs with resilience features, including succession planning for key roles, safe discussion formats to manage polarisation, and longer-term strategies to address structural inequalities.

3. Development of intersectional, inclusive, innovative and impactful institutional GEPs

All preceding activities of the SUPPORTER project (mapping, training and mutual learning, mentoring, and, most importantly, the implementation of institutional roadmaps) were carefully designed to converge towards the project's main outcome and lasting legacy: the development of 4I-GEPs. These plans represent a new generation of Gender Equality Plans that move beyond compliance with minimum legislative or funding requirements. Instead, they provide sustainable and transformative frameworks tailored to sports higher education institutions.

The 4I-GEPs did not emerge in isolation. They build directly on the institutional roadmaps, with already implemented or ongoing Grounding Actions forming the basis for the new documents. Insights and lessons from the training modules and the mutual learning scheme further enriched the process, while consultations with experts and affected internal actors ensured that the GEPs respond to the institutional needs while remaining true to the foundational concepts of gender equality.

This section outlines how the 4I-GEPs were developed and how they embody the principles reflected in their name. Section 3.1 describes the development process step by step. Section 3.2 presents the structural elements that define the new GEPs, showing how they align with established GEP components while incorporating the SUPPORTER guiding principles. Section 3.3 then analyses the GEPs institution by institution, drawing on project-internal and institutional sources. The analysis uses SUPPORTER tools such as the Mentoring and Monitoring scheme, transitional action plans, and the GEP checklist designed to guide and harmonise the process across all IOs. It also integrates insights from mentoring meetings and IO reflections documented in Learning Diary 7, which was dedicated to the development of the GEPs. Finally, the section links the new GEPs to earlier self-assessments (T2.3) and to the themes, gaps, and challenges identified in D4.1.

3.1. Development process

The transition from roadmap implementation to 4I-GEP drafting was carefully structured to ensure both institutional ownership and cross-consortium coherence. During the online Mutual Learning Session in December 2024, expectations for the 4I-GEPs were clarified, the rationale behind the guiding principles explained, and the steps of the development process introduced to all IOs.

Step 1: Getting familiar with the institutional process of policy adoption. Each IO was invited to map out its internal process for developing and approving a faculty or institutional policy such as a GEP. This included estimating the duration of each stage, identifying the governance structures involved, and determining the procedures for securing formal approval. These considerations were captured in the transitional action plan (described in Section 1.2), embedded in the roadmap update. This ensured clarity on what was needed, who needed to be involved, and how much time would be required for adoption. By anticipating these steps, IOs minimised the risk of bureaucratic delays and strengthened ownership of the process within their SUPPORTER working groups.

Step 2: Embedding the structural 4I-GEP elements. To avoid uniform documents that overlooked institutional specificities, the consortium deliberately decided not to impose a common drafting template. Instead, IOs were provided with a **GEP checklist** developed by the core team, which served both as a practical tool and a self-assessment mechanism.

Drawing on the knowledge gained through the GEP building blocks and the project's training programme, which not only analysed the four dimensions of the 4I framework but also demonstrated how they could be operationalised in the specific context of sports and higher education, the checklist prompted reflection under four main components:

- a) The step-by-step development process in line with EIGE guidelines (getting started, analysis and assessment, GEP design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation), with emphasis on the 4I framework, GBV, and the sports context;
- b) An “I-per-I” approach, translating each principle of the 4I framework into concrete structural elements, ensuring the GEPs were truly intersectional, impactful, inclusive, and innovative;
- c) Measures to prevent, detect and combat gender-based violence, the core anchor of the SUPPORTER project; and
- d) Tailoring the plan to the sports environment.

Alongside the checklist, IOs were provided with examples of successful GEPs from other higher education institutions to inspire adaptation of good practices to their own local contexts.

Step 3: Mentoring and peer support. A series of mentoring meetings, both planned and ad hoc, offered IO-specific guidance, helped resolve challenges, and ensured institutions progressed according to their internal structures. A key milestone was the Mutual Learning Workshop in Ljubljana, which consolidated knowledge from earlier mapping, training, and roadmap implementation. IOs presented their first GEP drafts, received feedback from mentors, exchanged experiences with peers, and worked collectively to refine their documents. The workshop also linked institutional drafting to the consortium's parallel work on policy recommendations for gender equality in sports higher education.

Step 4: Stakeholder engagement. IOs were also asked to consult internal and external stakeholders. This participatory dimension ensured that the draft GEPs reflected institutional realities, carried legitimacy across their communities, and aligned with local and national gender equality agendas. Before finalisation, IOs revisited their drafts against the GEP checklist to confirm that all required components were included and adequately addressed. This internal quality assurance step reinforced coherence and alignment with the SUPPORTER framework

Step 5: Formal adoption. Finally, each institution advanced its GEP through the formal approval processes identified in its transitional action plan. By embedding approval pathways into the roadmaps, IOs ensured that the 4I-GEPs were not only drafted but also officially adopted by institutional leadership—laying the foundation for their sustainable implementation.

Figure 1: Steps for the development of the 4I-GEPs

3.2. Structural elements

The 4I-GEPs developed within SUPPORTER were designed around a shared set of structural elements, ensuring both compliance with European standards and responsiveness to the specific challenges of sports higher education. Their guiding principles rest on four main pillars:

1. **Fulfilling the mandatory GEP elements.** In line with the GEAR tool steps and EC’s mandatory GEP elements, all GEPs were expected to include four essential features:

- Public document:* formally adopted, signed by top management, and published on the institution’s website.
- Dedicated resources:* a clear commitment of financial and human resources, including staff with gender equality expertise, to support implementation.
- Data collection and monitoring:* systematic collection and analysis of sex-disaggregated data (staff, students, leadership roles) and annual reporting based on indicators.
- Training:* awareness-raising and training activities for the whole organisation, alongside dedicated sessions on unconscious bias for staff and decision-makers.

1. **The 4I framework.** The new GEPs explicitly operationalise the four “I”s:

Intersectional: An intersectional GEP considers gender in relation to its intersections with other sociocultural, economic and political inequalities such as race, ethnicity, class, sexuality, age, dis/ability, nationality and so on, and proposes actions which take into account how different forms of inequality and disadvantage interconnect.¹

¹ Center for Intersectional Justice (<https://www.intersectionaljustice.org/what-is-intersectionality>) Collins P. H. (2015) Intersectionality’s Definitional Dilemmas. *Annual Review of Sociology*. 41:1–20. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-soc-073014-112142>.

Innovative: An innovative GEP entails the implementation of measures that demonstrate originality and creativity in fostering gender equality. This may involve introducing new ideas, concepts, and intersections; employing advanced participatory methods; forming unconventional partnerships; or implementing targeted actions to address emerging challenges. In other words, an innovative GEP offers out-of-the-box solutions to address common GE issues, while being inclusive, intersectional and impactful.

Inclusive: GEPs should address inclusiveness in its design, implementation, and evaluation in the following forms: 1) inequalities and inclusivity by considering other sociocultural factors in relation to gender+ such as supposed race, ethnicity, age, sexuality, disability etc.; 2) geographical inclusiveness by recognising the local and regional differences between organisations and enabling knowledge transfer from more advanced to less experienced organisations; 3) internal inclusiveness by engaging internal stakeholders ranging from students, administrative and academic staff to top management; and 4) intersectoral inclusiveness by engaging external stakeholders.²

Impactful: An impactful GEP entails a growing institutional capacity of the organisation for gender mainstreaming along a number of pre-identified intermediate stages and themes for change. Twelve key themes have been identified: core team of change agents; capacity/skills of the change agents for driving institutional change for gender equality; leadership actively committed to gender equality/gender mainstreaming; availability of resources; data collection and statistical analysis; involvement of internal stakeholders; involvement of external stakeholders and experts; coverage of the different dimensions/areas of gender equality; Institutional change; transparency and accountability; institutional policy-making based on robust understanding of gender equality; organisational culture; and organisational governance. Growing capacity refers to a set of impact drivers that enable effective change and impact to be achieved.

2. **Focus on gender-based violence (GBV).** A central innovation of the SUPPORTER approach was the explicit integration of GBV into institutional GEPs. While Horizon Europe identifies GBV as an optional thematic area, SUPPORTER elevated it to a core pillar. Sports institutions—often marked by hierarchical structures and masculine norms—present particular risks of harassment and abuse. For this reason, GEPs were expected to include clear procedures for prevention, reporting, and support; raise awareness through training and campaigns; and promote a zero-tolerance culture.
3. **Tailoring to the sports environment.** Sports universities and faculties are crucial arenas for gender transformation. They reproduce cultural norms of masculinity, are characterised by gender

Crenshaw, K. W. (1989) 'Demarginalizing the Intersection of Race and Sex: A Black Feminist Critique of Antidiscrimination Doctrine, Feminist Theory and Antiracist Politics.' *University of Chicago Legal Forum* 1989:139–67.

Losleben, K. and Musubika, S. (2023) 'Intersectionality'. In Duarte, M., Losleben, K., & Fjørtoft, K. (Eds.). (2023). *Gender Diversity, Equity, and Inclusion in Academia: A Conceptual Framework for Sustainable Transformation*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003363590>

Lykke, N. (2010) *Feminist Studies: A Guide to Intersectional Theory, Methodology and Writing*. New York: Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203852774>

² ERAC/SWG (Standing Working Group on Gender) (2021). *Gender Equality Plans as a Catalyst for Change*. Brussels, 1st June 2021, ERAC 1202/21. <https://data.consilium.europa.eu/doc/document/ST-1202-2021-INIT/en/pdf>

Sangiuliano, M., Karydou, K. and Kyrkou, D. (2023) It's all about Priorities: Tips for Successfully Implementing Gender Equality Actions. *International Conference on Gender Research*, 6(1): 308-311. <http://dx.doi.org/10.34190/icgr.6.1.1006>

imbalances in leadership and participation in sports and face documented prevalence of harassment and abuse. At the same time, they educate the next generation of coaches, teachers, and sports managers, giving them multiplier potential to diffuse inclusive norms across society. GEPs were therefore required to go beyond generic measures by addressing gender norms and stereotypes in sports participation, leadership, and media representation; integrating gender perspectives into sport-related teaching and research; and promoting women's representation in coaching and management roles. In this way, the GEPs serve not only their institutional community but also the broader sports ecosystem

In addition to these four pillars, the core team advised that each new GEP begin with a **situation analysis/institutional context** to ground the identification of action areas and highlight progress compared to previous GEPs. Furthermore, every GEP was required to include a **comprehensive action plan** covering its full timeline, with objectives, actions, indicators, and resources clearly defined.

Taken together, these elements form the structural skeleton of the 4I-GEPs: firmly anchored in European and EIGE's standards, enriched by the SUPPORTER framework, and tailored to the realities of sports higher education.

3.3. Analysis of new 4I-GEPs

The new 4I-GEPs represent both a culmination of the SUPPORTER process and a forward-looking commitment to institutional change. While some institutions opted for a shorter-term perspective, preparing GEPs covering the two to three years immediately following the project's lifetime, others adopted a longer-term vision by developing five-year plans that address both short- and long-term institutional needs.

This section analyses the advancements achieved compared to the GEPs in place at the project's outset and examines how the new plans connect with the respective institutional roadmaps, drawing on lessons learnt, newly identified gaps, and persistent challenges. It also assesses the extent to which the structural elements of the 4I-GEPs have been fulfilled.

The analysis is based on a combination of sources: the reflections of the implementing organisations, articulated either within their GEPs or in their final learning diaries, and the observations of the core team arising from its review of the new documents. Together, these perspectives provide a comprehensive picture of how the 4I-GEPs consolidate SUPPORTER's achievements while charting the course for sustainable institutional transformation.

3.3.1 University of Banja Luka

While the University of Banja Luka already had a Gender Equality Plan at institutional level, no faculty-specific plan existed to address the particular needs and challenges of sports academia. The University-level GEP was assessed as relatively advanced, especially in terms of innovation, intersectionality and impact, yet these strengths were not concretely articulated in practice and remained largely rhetorical. Areas such as inclusiveness, the focus on gender-based violence, and sport-specific measures were underdeveloped, while even the higher-ranked dimensions lacked

acknowledgment of inequalities or detailed measures for change. Although gender equality was already identified as a strategic priority and the University employed a gender expert, professors and researchers were not actively encouraged to engage in gender equality activities, leaving a gap between institutional commitments and everyday academic practice.

The 4I-GEP developed at UNIBL and Sport addresses these shortcomings directly, demonstrating strong alignment with the three guiding pillars of the SUPPORTER project: the 4I framework, the focus on gender-based violence, and the sports environment.

Integration of the 4I framework: *Inclusiveness* is ensured by applying the plan to all members of the academic community—students, staff, coaches, and athletes—while addressing the needs of individuals from diverse socio-economic backgrounds, persons with disabilities, and ethnic or national minorities. *Innovation* is reflected in the adoption of pioneering Faculty-level policies, including Guidelines for the Provision of Support during and after Career Breaks and Procedures for reporting GBV and SH, complemented by the appointment of specially trained *persons of trust* and a confidential reporting mechanism. *Impact* is operationalised through the combination of clear objectives, indicators, supportive policies, awareness-raising activities, reporting mechanisms, and alignment with the University GEP, ensuring structural, cultural, social, educational, and analytical impact. *Intersectionality* is integrated throughout the plan: UNIBL considered multiple and overlapping inequalities in its data collection, initially focusing on the combined impact of gender, age, position, and nationality; measures were designed to support underrepresented groups of different genders; structural impact was pursued through policies fostering diverse representation in decision-making; and gender equality content with an intersectional perspective was incorporated into teaching and learning.

Addressing gender-based violence: The prevention and elimination of GBV and SH is a key focus of UNIBL's 4I-GEP. Organisational policies were adopted that go beyond symbolic commitments, embedding clear procedures for reporting and investigating cases, and establishing a Faculty-level support system. The appointment of *persons of trust* contributes to confidential and impartial support to victims, anonymity is protected, and retaliation is prevented. Regular trainings, anonymous surveys, and awareness-raising activities are foreseen, promoting a culture of zero tolerance across the Faculty. In this way, UNIBL has translated the SUPPORTER framework into concrete structures that respond to the particular risks and power dynamics of the sports environment.

Tailoring to the sports environment: UNIBL's GEP is distinctly sport-specific, addressing both the structural imbalances in representation and participation, the cultural stereotypes and gender norms embedded in the field. It integrates gender equality into teaching and research content, including theses and seminar papers, and incorporates awareness campaigns challenging gender norms and stereotypes in sports participation, leadership, and media representation. By involving external stakeholders such as athletes and coaches, the plan extends its reach beyond the Faculty, while measures to promote women's representation in coaching and management roles target persistent structural gaps. Educational impact is further emphasised by preparing students and future sports professionals to carry inclusive practices into their careers.

3.3.2 University of Ljubljana

Before the adoption of this new plan, the Faculty of Sport at the University of Ljubljana had not developed its own faculty-specific GEP, even though gender equality had already been recognised as an institutional priority. Dedicated resources for gender equality within the Faculty were lacking, with only limited expertise available through individual staff members rather than through structured support. No systematic collection of gender-disaggregated data or use of specific indicators was in place, leaving the monitoring of progress underdeveloped. While the University-wide GEP was considered to meet the guiding principles of gender equality planning, it did not address the particularities of the sports environment, where distinct challenges such as gender norms and stereotypes, leadership imbalances, and risks of harassment required targeted action.

Integration of the 4I framework: *Intersectionality* is applied in disaggregated data collection (gender, age, nationality) to identify overlapping inequalities, especially for younger women researchers and foreign students. Measures promote underrepresented groups, although the institutional team itself has flagged the need for the inclusion of broader and systematic diversity dimensions (ethnicity, disability). *Innovation* is expressed through new, participatory and culturally sensitive mechanisms such as trusted persons, cross-functional gender equality teams, and faculty-level GEP structures tailored to sport. *Inclusiveness* was ensured through engagement of staff, researchers, students, and external partners, with dissemination strategies foreseen. Policies to guarantee accessibility for persons with disabilities or multilingual users are not yet fully addressed. *Impact* is strengthened by linking objectives to specific actions, timelines, indicators, and responsibilities. The GEP Committee is trained, annual reports are foreseen, and external experts contributed to the drafting.

Addressing gender-based violence: GBV is one of the central pillars of UL's GEP. It introduces a system of *trusted persons* at faculty level, with plans to include students in this role in future. The new system foresees victim support and clear procedures for reporting and investigating cases, sustained by anonymous reporting channels and the visible publication of policies online. Regular training and awareness workshops are mandated for staff, students, and exchange students alike. Overall, the Faculty moves from implicit institutional recognition of GBV toward concrete mechanisms and a culture of zero tolerance.

Tailoring to the sports environment: The GEP is distinctly adapted to the sports context. It introduces content on gender equality and stereotypes into the training of coaches, developed in collaboration with the Slovenian Olympic Committee and national sport federations. Awareness activities extend to students, staff, and coaches, aiming to dismantle gender norms and stereotypes in participation, leadership, and the portrayal of athletes. The plan also sets measures to encourage women's representation in sports management and academic leadership. By embedding equality in both curricula and professional development for future coaches, the UL Faculty of Sport positions its GEP as a driver of cultural change within Slovenian sport.

3.3.3 Charles University

Charles University has demonstrated a sustained commitment to gender equality since its first University-level GEP (2022–2024). While this marked an important step, the plan relied mainly on general goals, did not incorporate the 4I framework, and awareness of gender-based violence remained extremely low, while its university-wide scope did not allow for specific consideration of the sports environment (or the particularities or any other distinct faculty). The new, faculty-based 4I-GEP introduces clear advancements by strengthening data collection, ensuring deeper stakeholder involvement, and setting out a structured set of concrete measures with defined indicators, responsibilities, and timelines, while taking into account the world of sports.

Integration of the 4I framework: *Intersectionality* is explicitly addressed: the plan recognises overlapping disadvantages linked to gender, age, ethnicity, disability, and socio-economic status, and integrates these into both data collection and policy design. Actions include equitable representation in committees, curriculum updates to reflect diverse student needs, and leadership development initiatives targeting underrepresented groups. *Innovation* is visible in the introduction of creative pedagogical methods, including short educational videos, interactive digital modules, and case-based learning formats designed to integrate gender equality into sports education beyond traditional lectures. *Inclusiveness* is ensured by the participatory development of the plan, which engaged academic staff, administrative staff, students, and external stakeholders; the flexible scheduling for staff returning from caregiving leave and systematic communication campaigns on equality issues; the gathering of detailed data to identify GBV patterns among diverse groups; and the introduction of a mandatory ‘social security training’ for all staff. *Impact* is operationalised through 69 specific measures across nine thematic areas, each linked to indicators, timelines, and responsibilities. The monitoring framework combines departmental staff meetings, leadership coordination, student surveys, confidential ombudsperson reports, and an annual GEP review, ensuring sustainability and accountability.

Addressing gender-based violence: GBV prevention and response is a dedicated priority area within CU’s GEP. Mandatory training on social safety and GBV is introduced for all staff, incorporating sports-specific scenarios and bystander intervention strategies. Clear and accessible reporting mechanisms are coordinated by ombudsperson contact persons, with a focus on confidentiality, retaliation protection, and accessibility for vulnerable groups. The GEP further integrates awareness-raising into teaching, embedding discussions on GBV within practical sports courses and case-based learning, making prevention part of everyday academic life. Awareness campaigns, short videos, and student evaluation surveys reinforce this culture of zero tolerance, while evaluation mechanisms such as satisfaction feedback from reporting are built into monitoring structures.

Tailoring to the sports environment: The CU GEP directly reflects the faculty’s sports-specific context. It addresses the hierarchical power dynamics between coaches and athletes, embedding ethical standards and reporting pathways to counter vulnerabilities. Gender mainstreaming is integrated into the sports curriculum and research, including modules on gender bias in sports, leadership diversity, and media representations of athletes. Staff training supports the integration of inclusive materials and gender-sensitive coaching approaches. Research and theses are encouraged to take up gender-related themes, bridging academic learning with the realities of sports practice. The plan also promotes women’s representation in leadership and coaching roles through targeted workshops, mentoring, and awareness actions. By linking wellbeing, social safety, and equality to sports education, CU ensures its GEP resonates directly with the lived experiences of students and staff in the faculty.

3.3.4 Lithuanian Sports University

At the start of the SUPPORTER project, LSU’s GEP had no dedicated resources, gender expertise, or indicators to track progress. Awareness-raising activities existed, but there was no structured training, no measures on work–life balance or gender balance in leadership, and no attention to gender equality in research and teaching. Intersectionality and sports-specific considerations were entirely absent, and the university lacked a gender equality officer or contact point. The new 4I-GEP addresses these gaps by prioritising training and education for staff, students, and the wider sports community, allocating resources and working time to institutional committees, and establishing clear

systems for data collection and monitoring. It also builds on roadmap outputs, such as the Psychological Well-being survey and initiatives to increase student involvement, thereby strengthening its long-term impact.

Integration of the 4I framework: *Intersectionality* is incorporated by encouraging teachers and researchers to integrate gender, GBV, religion, ethnicity, age, socio-economic status, and disability dimensions into specific modules, research topics, and knowledge transfer. Training and consultations are also foreseen for staff and coaches to strengthen their capacity in applying intersectional perspectives in teaching and practice. *Innovation* is reflected in actions to expand data collection and communication methods, including the creation of a dedicated gender equality and GBV section on the university website, new methods for engaging students and staff in surveys, and strategies to increase women’s leadership participation. *Inclusiveness* is ensured through targeted internal and external communication initiatives, awareness campaigns highlighting gender aspects in research and giving prominence to role models and strengthened cooperation with national and international partners such as the National Olympic Committee and sports federations. *Impact* is operationalised by embedding gender equality and GBV prevention into strategic documents, codes of ethics, and development policies, while allocating specific human resources—such as the Psychological Wellbeing Committee, the Marketing and Communications Department, the Ethics Committee, and the Student Association—for the implementation of the new plan. It also establishes a monitoring system with clear indicators, regular reporting to governance, and sets out specific objectives with related activities, target groups, indicators, and defined responsibilities.

Addressing gender-based violence: GBV is treated as a cross-cutting concern throughout LSU’s GEP. Policies and protocols for prevention and case investigation are consolidated under the remit of the Ethics Committee, supported by the Psychological Wellbeing Committee and external partners. LSU commits to conducting regular research and surveys on psychosocial risk factors, integrating findings into the monitoring of GBV prevalence and institutional responses. Awareness-raising is pursued through seminars, trainings, and campaigns targeting both the university and wider sports community, explicitly including marginalised groups such as LGBTQ+ individuals and persons with disabilities. Support mechanisms are reinforced by dedicated institutional structures, ensuring that prevention, protection, and monitoring are sustained over the 2025–2030 period.

Tailoring to the sports environment: The new GEP addresses persistent gender imbalances in student participation, coaching, and sports leadership, with measures to encourage women’s representation in decision-making bodies and management roles. Partnerships with federations, clubs, and associations ensure that gender equality commitments extend beyond the university into the broader Lithuanian sports ecosystem. Teaching and research are infused with diversity and gender perspectives, with curricula revisions to reflect equity and social responsibility. Awareness campaigns and training initiatives also target athletes, coaches, and sports managers, equipping them with the skills to challenge stereotypes and promote equality in professional practice. By rooting gender equality in both institutional policy and its extended sports networks, LSU positions its GEP as a driver of long-term cultural change in Lithuanian sport.

3.3.5 National Sports Academy “Vasil Levski”

With the original GEP in place, NSA had no expertise in gender equality, no gender-disaggregated data collection, and no indicators to track progress. Awareness-raising activities were absent, the recommended GEP elements were not addressed, and the inclusion of 4I principles was very limited—particularly regarding gender-based violence, where awareness and procedures were almost

non-existent. The institution also lacked a harassment officer or contact point, and there were no links to strategic documents or monitoring frameworks. As a result, gender equality was not treated as a genuine institutional priority. The new 4I-GEP marks a significant shift by recognising gender equality as a strategic concern. It builds on challenges identified during roadmap implementation, leverages new structures, policies (e.g. the Communication strategy developed during the project implementation) and bodies (such as the refreshed Ethics Committee with extended mandate to promote GE) and embeds concrete objectives, identifies key internal and external stakeholders, allocates human, material and informational resources, and establishes mechanisms to monitor, prevent, and respond to inequalities.

Integration of the 4I framework: *Intersectionality* is operationalised through the creation of structures and procedures to address combined forms of discrimination (e.g. gender, social status, parental responsibilities, and hierarchical student–teacher relations). Measures include establishing a central administrative body and regulatory rules for reporting intersectional discrimination, the creation of a training strand, and taking into account various aspects of vulnerability to provide appropriate assistance and protection in case of violation. *Innovation* lies in advanced understanding of gender discrimination in its intersection with other forms of inequality, adding gender equality clauses in contracts with sports organisations, systematically updating curricula with real cases on women’s rights and violence in sport, leveraging the SUPPORTER network to extend international partnerships on this new strategic priority including planned accession to relevant European equality organisations. *Inclusiveness* is pursued through the broad participation of internal stakeholders—academic staff, administrative offices, and governance representatives—in the design of GEP activities. It also extends to the engagement of external stakeholders through outreach initiatives, while accessibility is enhanced by making gender equality policies available in multiple languages. *Impact* is ensured through a four-level structure linking goals, objectives, measures, and expected outcomes to specific targets and indicators, monitored by the trained Ethics Committee. It is reinforced by a communication strategy developed during the roadmap phase, regular data collection on female leadership and perceptions of gender equality, and cultural change measures such as increasing the visibility of women leaders and improving working conditions adapted to staff needs.

Addressing gender-based violence: NSA’s GEP dedicates significant attention to GBV, building on data from a faculty-wide survey and consultations with students and staff. Organisational policies have been reinforced through collaboration with the Ministry of Interior and the regional police, ensuring that cases of violence linked to academy members are addressed through institutional and external mechanisms. A protocol for reporting and investigating GBV has been established, complemented by expanded responsibilities for the Academic Ethics Committee. The GEP also introduces regular awareness-raising activities, integration of GBV topics in educational and scientific forums, and partnerships with external actors to strengthen prevention and response. By doing so, NSA has taken its first decisive steps towards embedding a systematic approach to GBV, moving beyond isolated initiatives to coordinated institutional action.

Tailoring to the sports environment: The NSA GEP is strongly contextualised to the realities of sport. It introduces compulsory modules for all students on gender stereotypes in sport psychology, alongside training and awareness-raising activities for coaches and teachers. It further commits to addressing stereotypes in the portrayal of athletes and coaches, ensuring that teaching and training programmes openly confront discriminatory representations. NSA will also participate in projects dedicated to overcoming gender norms and stereotypes in sport, leveraging comparative perspectives from different countries and systems. Finally, long-term measures are introduced to support women’s representation in coaching and sports management, beginning with the targeted education and encouragement of female students to pursue such roles. Through these measures, the

GEP links institutional transformation with broader changes in Bulgarian sport, recognising the Academy's strategic role as the country's main training hub for coaches, teachers, and sports managers.

3.3.6 Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara - Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (UVT-FEFS)

Before the adoption of the 4I-GEP, the Faculty of Sport at UVT had no faculty-based GEP in place, relying only on the university-wide plan. Without the SUPPORTER project, the faculty would not have had access to the resources, expertise, or collaborative framework needed to integrate innovative concepts into its policies. Gender-based violence remained insufficiently discussed in Romanian educational and sports settings, and awareness was extremely low. No specific funds were allocated, and no gender equality expertise existed among staff or administration. There was no consistent collection of gender-disaggregated data, no training or awareness-raising on gender equality, and no inclusion of 4I elements. Objectives, targets, and timelines were also absent, leaving gender equality underdeveloped and unprioritised at faculty level. The new, ambitious 4I-GEP directly addresses these gaps by introducing resources, expertise, monitoring mechanisms, listing stakeholders to be involved, and devising a structured action plan to institutionalise gender equality.

Integration of the 4I framework: *Intersectionality* is advanced through a permanent system of collecting and analysing cross-sectional data on gender, ethnicity, disability, socio-economic status, and other factors in the sports environment; differentiated mentoring, counselling, and training programmes target disadvantaged students, teachers, and coaches; and curricula and HR measures are revised to mainstream diversity, integrate case studies with gender+ perspective and address stereotypes in sport. *Inclusiveness* is pursued through stakeholder engagement in the drafting and implementation of the GEP, involving students, academic and administrative staff, and external actors such as sports federations, NGOs, and national agencies. Student voices will be emphasised through advisory forums on equity and diversity, while inclusiveness is further reinforced by disability-sensitive scholarships and initiatives like the West Summer University Programme, which fosters openness and equal opportunities. *Innovation* is reflected in the use of digital and participatory tools to advance equity in sport education. Key measures include hackathons to design IT solutions, a real-time feedback system for students to report issues or discrimination, a community of practice for teachers to share technology-based approaches, and the application of AI to analyse disaggregated data on sport participation. Co-design, peer-learning, and the creation of an InfoPoint further demonstrate a participatory and community-based approach to institutional transformation. Innovation also extends to the planned introduction of unisex sports, an idea inspired by the third training module and peer-to-peer exchanges, particularly CU's research and good practices on this topic. *Impact* is secured through clear targets and indicators across the action plan, allocation of financial, human and logistical resources, annual gender audits, publication of monitoring reports, and training on gender equality. External experts and stakeholders were also involved in the drafting process, and a dissemination strategy ensures wide institutional visibility.

Addressing gender-based violence: GBV is a central focus of the UVT GEP, structured around prevention, intervention, and cultural change. The plan foresees the adoption of clear protocols for reporting and investigating GBV cases, coupled with the establishment of an InfoPoint to guide victims to psychological, medical, or legal support services. Anti-harassment and zero-tolerance rules are to be displayed in dormitories, gyms, and classrooms, supported by awareness campaigns, annual information sessions, and inclusion of GBV prevention in curricula. Staff and student trainings

explicitly address GBV, consent, and healthy relationships, while teaching staff are encouraged to integrate open discussions and support resources in their interactions with students. Although anti-retaliation mechanisms are not yet fully formalised, the GEP acknowledges this gap and signals its integration in future updates. Through these actions, UVT moves from ad hoc awareness-raising toward an institutionalised GBV prevention and response framework.

Tailoring to the sports environment: The UVT GEP is strongly tailored to the sports education context. It addresses gender stereotypes in participation, leadership, and coaching, with curriculum revisions to include modules on diversity, equality, and management of mixed teams. Training is planned for coaches, referees, and sports managers, focusing on leadership, fair refereeing, and the prevention of bias and GBV. Student athletes are targeted through awareness events, mentoring, and scholarships, with special measures to support disadvantaged groups and students with disabilities (adapted infrastructure, dedicated equipment, counselling, and scholarships). Mixed-team competitions and thematic events are used as vehicles to challenge gender norms and stereotypes while mentoring and professional development programmes aim to increase women’s representation in sports management and research leadership. Partnerships with national sports federations, NGOs, and international institutions extend these measures beyond the university into the broader sports ecosystem.

3.3.7 Georgian State University of Sport (GSTUPES)

GSTUPES adopted its first GEP in 2022 to meet the formal eligibility requirement for participation in the Horizon Programme as a partner in the SUPPORTER project. At that time, gender equality was not part of the institutional agenda: the plan was poorly communicated, lacked managerial ownership, and made no reference to the elimination of gender-based violence or harassment. No funds were allocated for implementation, no gender-disaggregated data were collected, awareness of both gender equality and GBV was extremely low, and no relevant training was offered. The new 4I-GEP marks a turning point, setting out clear goals, measures, and activities supported by a detailed timeline, indicators, designated responsibilities, and a monitoring process. Its development was informed by the roadmap process: drawing on peer exchanges through mutual learning to develop guidelines for gender-sensitive language (as in CU and NSA); embedding a new measure for regular internal gender and intersectional audits, after recognising that this had not been achieved within the project’s timeframe; and introducing an analytical timeline to address the challenge of limited implementation periods.

Integration of the 4I framework: *Intersectionality* is addressed through intersectional audits, recruitment and promotion practices that consider overlapping identities (gender, ethnicity, disability, socio-economic status), and disaggregated data collection across multiple categories. *Innovation* is reflected in digital solutions such as a platform for anonymous feedback on gender inequalities and GBV, an interactive online course on GBV and harassment prevention, and a centralised monitoring system to identify imbalances in the decision-making process. *Inclusiveness* is pursued via flexible work arrangements, family-friendly HR policies, mentorship, and leadership programmes that accommodate diverse needs and backgrounds. *Impact* is embedded structurally, with strategic objectives, timelines, responsible stakeholders, indicators for each measure and the integration of monitoring responsibilities into institutional governance structures.

Addressing gender-based violence: GBV is a dedicated strategic priority. The GEP commits to regular training of the Gender Equality Committee on case management and confidentiality, annual intersectional audits of policies and practices related to GBV/SH, and the establishment of an independent body to handle cases. Awareness-raising is pursued through annual events, training

sessions, and public campaigns on GBV and SH. The digital feedback platform allows for anonymous reporting, enhancing accessibility and trust. Together, these actions build both preventive and responsive capacity, moving GSTUPES beyond symbolic statements to tangible institutional structures that promote a culture of zero tolerance.

Tailoring to the sports environment: The GSTUPES GEP is clearly situated in the context of sports academia. It integrates gender-focused research in sports science, supports student-led and international collaborations on GE themes, and commits to curriculum changes that embed equality, stereotypes, and GBV discussions in sports education. Awareness campaigns and alumni outreach events are framed around sports settings, aiming to challenge stereotypes and biases within the athletic community. The plan also foresees participation monitoring by gender across teaching, research, and sports leadership, and sets explicit targets for women’s representation in academic and managerial roles. By combining institutional reforms with measures specific to the sports environment, GSTUPES links gender equality directly to its role as a national sports university.

3.3.8 Moldova State University – Institute of Physical Education and Sport (IEFS)

Before the adoption of the 4I-GEP, SUPES/IEFS had no resources allocated for gender equality, no internal expertise, and no system of gender-disaggregated data collection or indicators to track progress. The existing GEP was available only in Moldovan, limiting its visibility, and there were no GBV policies or other gender-related frameworks in place. Awareness of GBV procedures was extremely low, and no training had been offered to staff or students. The roadmap process helped to identify these shortcomings and underscored the need for regular awareness-raising activities on gender equality, which has been embedded as a priority in the new GEP.

Integration of the 4I framework: *Intersectionality* is promoted by fostering an environment that recognises and addresses intersecting inequalities—such as those related to religion and beliefs, and culture—through sustained awareness-raising and diversity-building initiatives. An intersectional perspective is explicitly incorporated into modules that address gender-related topics, ensuring that teaching, discussion, and reflection take into account overlapping forms of disadvantage. *Inclusiveness* was built into the design process by engaging a broad spectrum of internal stakeholders—students, administrative and academic staff, and senior leadership—alongside relevant external actors. During implementation, inclusiveness is operationalised through institution-wide awareness activities for students and staff and through the active involvement of the Rectorate, the Quality Committee, the Ethics Commission, and the Gender Equality Committee. The GEP is *innovative* by introducing several novel instruments: a dedicated website section for the GEP and its monitoring; a “Women’s Community” aimed at capacity-building and visibility; and an information kit providing guidance to prevent discrimination and recognise stereotypes in teaching. Innovation is further evidenced by the adoption of a new GBV Protocol. *Impact* appears in new instruments such as a dedicated website section for the GEP and monitoring, a “Women’s Community” to strengthen capacities and visibility, an information kit with guidance to avoid discrimination and recognise stereotypes in teaching; and the adoption and implementation of the new GBV protocol.

Addressing gender-based violence (GBV): GBV is treated as a cross-cutting priority built around the 7Ps (prevalence, prevention, protection, prosecution, partnership, provision of services, policy). The GEP introduces the new GBV protocol developed within the roadmap implementation and commits to monitoring its effectiveness; integrates GBV into regular training and information sessions

for staff and students; and strengthens rules on non-discriminatory, inclusive communication (including training on recognising discriminatory language). Conflict-mediation provisions and confidential pathways are included to resolve incidents promptly while safeguarding those involved. These measures sit alongside awareness campaigns, scientific/round-table events on gender equality, and cooperation mechanisms that extend to external partners.

Tailoring to the sports environment: The plan is explicitly sport-specific. It links actions to IEFS's role in educating coaches, teachers and sports managers by: (i) integrating gender topics in research and study activities within physical education and sport; (ii) organising inter-university sports activities that promote gender equality and protect women participants; (iii) creating a Women's Community and profiling women's contributions in sport on the IEFS website; and (iv) partnering with the scientific/sports community through conferences, seminars, and a database of GEP good practices. The action matrix also includes measures to grow women's representation in management and decision-making—key leverage points for culture change in sport institutions.

Conclusions

The SUPPORTER project set out to achieve a demanding but transformative goal: to support sports higher education institutions in Central and Eastern Europe to move from compliance-oriented gender equality planning to the adoption of 4I-GEPs for sports institutions, that treat gender-based violence as a core institutional priority.

The process unfolded through three phases: the co-design of institutional roadmaps, their implementation and update, and the drafting, consultation, and formal adoption of the new 4I-GEPs. The participatory design ensured that resulting strategies were not isolated documents but products of continuous reflection, adaptation, and engagement with internal and external stakeholders, and leveraging knowledge from the needs-informed, multi-level training around the different steps and elements of a GEP.

Three overarching conclusions emerge from this process. **First, the roadmap methodology proved effective in activating institutional change.** By treating the roadmaps as living documents, IOs were able to adapt their actions to newly identified needs, resource constraints, and opportunities, while strengthening their grounding actions in areas such as data collection, awareness-raising, embedding gender in teaching and research, dedicating institutional resources, and addressing gender-based violence. Combined with systematic mentoring and mutual learning, this approach fostered institutional ownership and prepared the ground for more ambitious and sustainable commitments.

Second, intersectionality and gender-based violence became the main transformative anchors. Intersectional perspective, initially unfamiliar to the majority of implementing institutions, was gradually integrated into data collection, training and awareness raising, and curricula changes, broadening the understanding of gender as a standalone inequality ground. Elevating GBV prevention and response to a central pillar of the SUPPORTER project implementation opened necessary conversations for an under-the-radar topic prior to the project's outset, leading to the introduction of protocols, awareness campaigns and new reporting and support mechanisms.

Third, tailoring actions to the sports environment is crucial for both impact and sustainability at institutional level. Gender equality challenges in sports academia are distinct: entrenched stereotypes and binary condition in participation, male-dominated leadership structures, hierarchical power relations between coaches and students, and the cultural normalisation of harassment. By

embedding equality commitments directly into curricula, research agendas, and professional training for future teachers, coaches, and managers, institutions ensured that measures were relevant, legitimate, and durable. Linking gender equality to the core mission of sports universities also reinforced institutionalisation: once integrated into teaching, codes of ethics, and partnerships with federations and clubs, equality commitments are more likely to endure beyond individual champions or project cycles.

The new 4I-GEPs consolidate these advances and provide a framework for the future. Compared to the GEPs in place at the start of the project, the new plans:

- demonstrate greater alignment with European standards, fully meeting EC mandatory elements and addressing the majority of thematic elements;
- explicit adoption of the 4I framework with concrete actions ensuring inclusivity, innovation, intersectionality, and impact;
- mainstream GBV prevention and response – an area previously underdeveloped or absent in all implementing organisations – into institutional structures, awareness raising and training, curricula, and support mechanisms; and
- tailor measures to the sports context, with measures tackling stereotypes, leadership imbalances, and cultural norms, while also leveraging the multiplier role of sports universities in shaping the next generation of PE teachers, coaches, and sports managers.

The adoption of the new, sports-specific 4I-GEPs is not the end of the process but the beginning of sustainable cultural change. Their implementation will require continued commitment of resources, engagement of stakeholders, and monitoring of progress. Yet the SUPPORTER project has demonstrated that, with the right tools and support, sports universities and faculties can become frontrunners in promoting equality, preventing gender-based violence, and training future professionals to carry these values into the broader sports ecosystem in the post-project period.

Annex I – Updated roadmap template

Introduction

The SUPPORTER project aims to foster gender-related institutional, **sustainable, transformative** changes in the sports institutions with a specific attention on the challenge of **GBV through the development of inclusive, innovative, intersectional and impactful GEPs**.

The transformation of existent institutional GEPs into 4I-GEPs is pursued through the co-design and implementation of individual roadmaps, tailored to the needs of each implementing organisation (IO). Developed under WP4 of the project, the roadmap is a strategic and dynamic plan, crafted to coordinate efforts towards institutional change under a common vision. This plan outlines, in a comprehensive and systematic manner, the structure and overall execution of the designed interventions. The roadmap aims to optimise the available resources, increase the impact of the activities and effectively mitigate foreseeable risks to the implementation plan.

Co-designed by the IOs and the core team, the roadmaps are built upon a uniform understanding of the relevant concepts, respond to specific institutional problems, and draw on lessons learnt in sports higher education institutions around Europe. Developed over four months, from December 2023 to March 2024, these roadmaps followed an iterative process of development and review, both by the SUPPORTER experienced partners and internally in each institution, to ensure their relevance and applicability.

As living documents, the roadmaps have evolved over the course of their 10-month implementation. Some changes have resulted from a progressively deepening understanding of gender equality, intersectionality and inclusiveness, fostered through the training and mutual learning activities of SUPPORTER. Intersectionality, in particular, has received special emphasis throughout the capacity building programme, inspiring adjustments to various Grounding Actions across multiple roadmaps. Other updates involve necessary timeline adjustments in alignment with academic scheduling and holiday periods, as well as reflect emerging needs and lessons learned throughout the implementation process.

As outlined above, the roadmaps culminate in the development of impactful, intersectional, innovative, and inclusive GEPs. This is reflected in the inclusion of a final, transitional action in each updated roadmap, focused on the formal approval of the 4I-GEP within the institution. As with all roadmap actions, this action is tailored to the specific institutional context, taking into account the regulatory and administrative processes necessary to validate the new GEP. Embedding the approval of the new GEP within the roadmap is a critical step to ensure institutional ownership and to pave the way for its sustainable implementation and long-term impact in the subsequent roadmap phases that will follow beyond the project's lifespan.

Summary of Changes

*Please provide an overview of key updates made to the roadmap **separately for each GA**. For each change, specify its nature and include a brief justification to ensure that the roadmap remains a relevant and practical guide for achieving gender equality and addressing GBV within your institution.*

When documenting changes, consider the following:

Nature of the Change: Briefly describe the change.

Examples:

- Intersectional aspects were added to specific GAs, the timeline of a GA was modified, resources were reallocated, a different group of stakeholders was engaged than originally planned).

Justification for the Change: Explain the reasoning behind the change.

Examples:

- The change resulted from an idea emerging during capacity-building activities, e.g. discussion on intersectionality in the Thessaloniki MLW or the GBV presentation during Training Module 2, Session 3.

- Although initially aiming for two workshops, the first one attracted more participants/from more target groups, so it would be redundant to repeat. OR we need more workshops than originally planned, due to low participation

- A timeline change occurred in order to attach the awareness-raising event to a specific athletic event, to ensure high participation and save resources.

- Initial feedback from a specific activity under this GA indicated a need for broader involvement of student groups.

Intersectionality Requirement: One of the changes must be the integration of intersectional aspects into at least one GA. Please describe how these aspects have been added and their expected impact.

Example:

GA1

- We added age and ethnic origin as intersectional aspects in the data collected on staff and students of the department. The change was inspired by the intersectionality exercise during the Thessaloniki Mutual Learning Workshop of the project.

Please use the table below to list each change made, the associated GA, and a brief justification.

Description	Associated GA	Justification
Title of the change (e.g., timeline adjustment, new resources allocated, shift in focus)	Specify the GA (e.g., GA1, GA2) that this change relates to	Briefly state the reason behind the change

Please indicate all changes within your roadmap below using a different colour font or text highlight.

Grounding Actions (of the updated roadmap)

Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: The objective is to institutionalize the 4I-GEP within the framework of the UNIBL Roadmap by securing formal commitment through a structured approval process, thereby ensuring the sustainability and long-term impact of its achievements.

Implementation plan

Please describe all the steps you need to follow in order to obtain a formal approval of the new GEP within your organisation. Take into account and describe:

- a) the stakeholders that need to be involved,*
- b) the amount of time this is going to require,*
- c) the overall timeline of the SUPPORTER project and your roadmap actions, in order to devise a viable plan to ensure validation of the GEP by the end of SUPPORTER.*

Potential obstacles

Timeline

Activity (Step)	Involved stakeholders	Required resources	Timeline

Annex II – Updated roadmaps

1. University of Banja Luka, Faculty of Physical Education and Sport (UNIBL)

Summary of changes

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender equality in sports environments

- Initially, we planned to organise two separate awareness-raising events: one for students and another for staff. However, during the preparation phase, academic staff expressed strong interest in joining the student-focused event. **This led to a combined session (an event) that attracted over 80 participants (students, staff, academic staff, external stakeholders) exceeding our original target 12 participants of academic staff and 25 students.** Given the high turnout in this event, we concluded that organising a second event would be redundant, and attracting additional participants may prove quite challenging.

GA2 – no changes were made

GA3 – Training on embedding gender dimension into research and teaching content

- In future data collecting for sport-related research, we have changed our focus to intersectionality aspects (gender/nationality). We intend to observe it in detail during two scheduled workshops.** This adjustment was inspired by the intersectionality exercise conducted during the Thessaloniki Mutual Learning Workshop of the project. These new variables will enhance the inclusiveness of our data analysis and allow a more comprehensive understanding of the gender dynamics in our institution.

GA4 – Establishing a support system for GBV incidents at the faculty level

- The implementation of this GA was previously scheduled for April 2024 to June 2025. However, we completed all actions ahead of schedule, officially adopted the person of trusts and the document titled "Guidelines for the prevention of SH and GBV at the faculty level," in June 2024. We revised the timeline for this GA accordingly.**
- During the preparation of the call for confidential support persons, we identified a lack of sufficient resources to hire external personnel. As a solution, we decided to appoint internal staff to these roles and allocate additional resources to provide them with comprehensive training. This ensures the effectiveness of the support system while working within the available budget.

GA5 – no changes were made.

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
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<i>GA1- Raising awareness on gender equality in sports environments</i>	1 big event instead of 2 workshops	We manage to conduct all targeted participants in single event
<i>GA3- Training on embedding gender dimension into research and teaching content</i>	Changing the research focus (added intersectionality aspects age/nationality)	This adjustment was inspired by the intersectionality exercise conducted during the Thessaloniki Mutual Learning Workshop of the project.
<i>GA4-Establishing a support system for GBV incidents at the faculty level</i>	Timeline adjustment	We managed to finish all activities ahead of schedule

Grounding Actions

A set of 5 Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5
<i>Intersectional</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Innovative</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Inclusive</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Impactful</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Tailored to sports</i>	x		x	x	x

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender equality in sports environments

GA1 is focused on awareness-raising activities on gender equality and understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases among staff, students and external stakeholders in the academic sport environment.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture; Gender balance in leadership and decision making

b. Objectives

Results of the focus groups discussions conducted at the Faculty in preparation of the Roadmap have shown that the level of understanding and knowledge of gender equality in sports environments and institutions, particularly within the administrative staff is at low level. Thus, through GA1 we aim to address the identified gap in knowledge and understanding of key gender equality concepts in sport, as well as to establish the preconditions for more supportive organisational culture, and thus contribute to the specific objective *1) Raise awareness and understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases in sport environment.*

c. Implementation plan

The main goal of this activity is to raise awareness among the Faculty's staff and students, as well as external stakeholders on gender equality in sports environments and institutions, particularly within the academic setting. The activity is organised through thematic workshops and panel discussions targeting gender equality in sports – key concepts, unconscious bias and how to tackle them in sports. The panel discussions should raise questions about stereotypes, different experiences and (non)existing meritocracy when it comes to women in leadership, competitive or other contributions to the sports environment. One of the expected outcomes of organising such panel discussion is to inspire students and staff of the Faculty to think critically about the current challenges that different genders face depending on their sport discipline. For example, some sports are stereotyped as being for "particular gender" only (e.g., female football players or male gymnast), or working position that can be perceived as more masculine or feminine. The activity can be implemented in collaboration with sports organisations/institutions/associations. Monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of the organised activities will be done through pre- and post- workshop questionnaires focusing on measurement of knowledge of participants on the thematic subject covered by the workshops, as well as through evaluation of the structure and organisation of the workshops.

- 1) Selecting the presentation topics and design of panel discussion
- 2) Setting up external panellist members
- 3) Developing a pre/post workshop/panel discussion questionnaire
- 4) Organisation of workshop/panel discussion events (students/staff)

Success criteria (KPIs):

- **One workshop/panel discussions organised (staff, students and external stakeholders)**
- At least 12 participants of academic staff and 25 of students per workshop gathered.
- Increased knowledge on gender equality and unconscious bias among staff and students.

Implementing team: SUPPORTER project team at the Faculty (with support, when needed, from the UNIBL Gender Equality Advisory Board and Student Union).

Resources needed: external panellists (athletes, trainers, sport managers), external expert advice, particularly for unconscious bias workshops (*sought externally either through SUPPORTER network, or University Gender Equality Advisory Board network*); classroom (*available internally*); funds for covering the costs of engaging external experts.

d. Stakeholders involved

GA1		
Implementation	Internal stakeholders	External stakeholders
Co-producing	Involved: SUPPORTER project team	Involved: External experts (co-creation of workshop content), athletes, trainers
Only consulting	Approached: Gender Equality Advisory Board	Approached: sport organisations, academic sports institutions
Only informing	Approached: students, staff	Approached: sport organisations

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reluctance of students or staff to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics. Difficulties in attracting successful athletes, sport managers or trainers to talk at the panel discussion. Lack of interest in participating in workshops. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing (and communicating) clear description of the content and objectives of the workshops and panel discussion. Using the existing networks and connections with sport organisations and associations, in finding the right panellists. Providing incentives in the form of extra points for certain courses (for students).

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Selecting the presentation topics and design of panel discussion	Project team Teaching staff Students	Topics and design of panel discussion decided	Team and participants' time External expert advice	March 2024

2. Setting up external panellist members	Project team SUPPORTER experienced partners Athletes Managers Trainers Students Teaching staff	The external panellist list per workshops defined A moderator selected	Team and participants' time External expert advice	April 2024
3. Developing a pre/post workshop/panel discussion questionnaire	Project team External experts	The questionnaire for evaluation of the effectiveness of the organised workshops/panel discussion adopted.	Team and participants' time External expert advice	April 2024
4. Organisation of workshop/panel discussion events (students/staff)	Project team External experts	One workshop / panel discussions organised (staff, students) At least 12 participants of academic staff and 25 students per workshop gathered Increased knowledge on gender equality and unconscious bias among staff and students	External expert advice External panellists Moderator Classroom Funds for covering the costs of engaging external expert	May 2024

GA2 – Development of Guidelines for provision of support during and after the career break

During the gender audit conducted both at the university level (in preparation of UNIBL GEP), but also at the Faculty level (in preparation of the Roadmap) we have identified that apart from relying upon the existing legal framework regarding sick leave, parental leave and extended leave for the care for children, or other (justified) absences from work, we should also provide more support to the person on a longer absence leave (particularly maternity leave). This should be done especially with regard to any changes within the faculty which might affect their position, responsibility, workload etc. GA2 is focused on providing support to work-life balance for the faculty staff.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture

b. Objectives

The main goal of this action is to ensure that all staff, and in particular academic staff, has sufficient support during and after career breaks such as long-term illness, parental leave, care-duties that prevent them from actively engaging for longer periods (more than 15 days), etc.

c. Implementation plan

The action covers activities focusing on development of Guidelines for Provision of Support during and after the Career Break, including:

- 1) establishing a team for development of Guidelines,
- 2) drafting the Guidelines,
- 3) discussing the Guidelines with the staff and receiving feedback,
- 4) adoption of Guidelines by the Faculty management.

Success criteria:

Guidelines for Provision of Support during and after the Career Break developed and adopted.

Implementing team: SUPPORTER project team at the Faculty, Secretary General of the Faculty, Union president.

Resources needed: internal resources = staff, including Secretary General of the Faculty (legal background), Faculty management, gender equality experts.

d. Stakeholders involved

GA 2		
Implementation	Internal stakeholders	External stakeholders
Co-producing	Involved: SUPPORTER project team, Secretary General of the Faculty Approached: staff (discussing the draft)	//
Only consulting	Approached: Gender Equality Advisory Board, Legal Department of the University	//
Only informing	Approached: staff	//

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
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None.	None.
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f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Establishing a team for development of the Guidelines for provision of support	Project team Secretary General of the Faculty Union president	List of working team members and their role in draft development	Internal resources = staff, including Secretary General of the Faculty (legal background) Faculty management	March 2024
2. Drafting the Guidelines for provision of support	Project team Secretary General of the Faculty Union president	Consultation meetings	Gender equality experts	April - May 2024
3. Discussing the Guidelines with the staff and receiving feedback	Project team Secretary General of the Faculty Union president Staff	Updating drafts and creating final proposal	Internal resources = staff, including Secretary General of the Faculty (legal background) Faculty management	June 2024
4. Adoption of the Guidelines by the Faculty management	Faculty management	The Guidelines adopted	Faculty management	July 2024
5. Presentation of the Guidelines to the staff	Project team Faculty management	Launch of the Guidelines (providing information via Faculty's social networks and communication channels)	Faculty's communication officer	September 2024

GA3 – Training on embedding the gender dimension into research and teaching content

GA3 is focused on training activities on embedding gender dimension into research and teaching content in sport studies at the Faculty through organising workshops and supporting development of research projects with integrated gender dimension.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content

b. Objectives

Although some courses have integrated the gender dimension (due to the nature of the subject), there is still an evident gap in the approaches used in teaching (as perceived by students) when it comes to certain aspects of gender dimension in sports. GA3 aims at bringing the integration of gender dimension in teaching and research content to a higher level through dedicated discussions, workshops and support provided to embedding gender dimension in research. GA3 is contributing to the achievement of the specific objective 1) *Training on embedding gender dimension into research and teaching content.*

c. Implementation plan

The main goal of this activity is to train Faculty staff and students on how to recognise and embed gender dimension in their research and teaching content. The activity is organised through two thematic approaches targeting: a) gender dimension in teaching content in sport science, b) gender dimension in research in sport science. The aim of this training is to motivate teaching staff to embed gender dimension into their curriculum frame and to be more proactive in gender equality related initiatives and project applications tailored to sports. Although there are research projects and also diploma and master theses that are taking into account gender dimension, this action aims at encouraging even more engagement in this regard both at the level of students, e.g. while developing their diploma and master theses research or doing their seminar papers integrating the gender dimension in sports, or engaging them in activities during the 16 Days of Activism campaign where they can deliver presentations on particular topics relevant to gender equality in sports. Similarly, at the level of researchers the action will encourage engagement in and development of research projects with integrated gender dimension.

Monitoring and evaluation of the effectiveness of the organised workshops will be done through pre- and post- workshop questionnaires focusing on measurement of knowledge of participants on the thematic subject covered by the workshops, as well as through evaluation of the structure and organisation of the workshops.

- 1) Establishing proactive network (Supporter member team/staff/students) for embedding gender dimension into presentations, seminars, diploma or master thesis
- 2) Creating the teaching content of workshop and selecting the workshops methodology
- 3) Developing a pre/post workshop questionnaire
- 4) Organising workshops (one for staff and one for students)

Success criteria:

- Two workshops organised (one for teaching staff and one for students)
- At least 10 participants of teaching staff and 25 students per workshop gathered.
- At least five presentations, seminars, diploma, master thesis theses per academic year integrated gender dimension
- More than three research projects applications focusing on gender equality in sports submitted by 2026
- At least two research projects implemented focusing on gender equality in sports by 2026
- Increased knowledge on integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content.

Implementing team: SUPPORTER project team at the Faculty (with support, when needed, from the UNIBL Gender Equality Advisory Board and SUPPORTER project experienced organisations), teaching staff.

Resources needed: external expert advice (*sought externally either through SUPPORTER network, or University Gender Equality Advisory Board network*); classroom (*available internally*); funds for covering the costs of engaging external experts.

d. Stakeholders involved

GA 3		
Implementation	Internal stakeholders	External stakeholders
Co-producing	Involved: SUPPORTER project team	Involved: Athletes and trainers; external experts (co-creation of workshop content)
Only consulting	Approached: Gender Equality Advisory Board	Approached: sports organisations; Supporter experienced partners
Only informing	Approached: students, staff	//

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reluctance of staff and students to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics • Professors not providing support for students' seminar papers, diploma or master thesis to integrate gender dimension due to misunderstanding of the key concepts of gender equality and gender dimension in research and their applicability for their subject. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing (and communicating) clear description of the content and objectives of the workshops. • Providing training and workshops, clarifying the key concepts of gender equality and gender dimension in research and their applicability in different subjects.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Establishing proactive network (Supporter member team/staff/students) for embedding gender dimension into presentations, seminars, diploma or master thesis	SUPPORTER project team Teaching staff Students	At least five presentations, seminars, diploma, or master theses per academic year with integrated gender dimension More than three research projects applications focusing on gender equality in sports submitted by 2026 At least two research projects implemented focusing on GE in sports by 2026	Student and staff time Classroom	April 2024 - June 2025
2. Creating the teaching content of workshop and selecting the workshops methodology	Project team Gender equality advisory board	The teaching topics and methodology of workshops defined Prepared content for two events	External expert advice Classroom	October - November 2024
3. Developing a pre/post workshop questionnaire	Project team External experts	The questionnaire for evaluation of the effectiveness of the organised workshops adopted	External expert advice Classroom Funds for covering the costs of engaging external expert	February 2025
4. Organising workshops (one for staff and one for students)	Project team Teaching staff Students	Two workshops organised At least 10 participants of teaching staff and 25 students per workshop gathered Increased knowledge on integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content	Funding for research projects	March - May 2025

GA4 – Establishing a support system at the Faculty level

GA4 is focused on establishing support provision activities on preventing and combating gender-based violence and sexual harassment (GBV and SH) both at the Faculty and in sport in general through establishing support system at the Faculty in cases of GBV and SH, as well as through providing training on GBV and SH in sports environment.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

There is a low level of awareness of existence of the UNIBL Guidelines for the Prevention of Gender-Based Violence and Sexual Harassment among students and staff. In addition to that, students reported during the focus group that they have either witnessed or heard of such incidents (both on horizontal or vertical level) but have not reported further due to lack of knowledge on whom to approach or report to, or due to mistrust in the process and system in general (on a broader societal level). There is an evident need for further actions towards raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment, as well as establishing support system in cases of such incidents.

c. Implementation plan

This activity is dedicated to establishing a sustainable support system at the Faculty level for cases of GBV and sexual harassment providing a contact point (persons of trust) at the Faculty who will be in charge of 1) be the first contact for reporting GBV and SH incidents at the Faculty and 3) provide further support to victims of GBV and SH. The activity is divided into several sub-activities:

- 1) Appointing the persons of trust,
- 2) Training for person of trust,
- 3) Establishing a procedure for reporting GBV and SH at the Faculty level - elaboration of proposal,
- 4) Adoption of procedures for reporting GBV and SH at the Faculty level.

Success criteria:

- Person of trust appointed.
- Procedure for reporting GBV and SH established.
- Person of trust participated in at least two training sessions.

Implementing team: Management of the Faculty, Secretary General, appointed person of trust.

Resources needed: internal resources – staff; external expert advice (*sought externally either through SUPPORTER network, or University Gender Equality Advisory Board network*). Persons of trust, selected from the Faculty's staff (both academic and non-academic) will be appointed with a 2-year mandate by the Faculty's Council. The funds for their engagement come from their regular salaries

where their time allocated for work as persons of trust will be calculated in. External experts, engaged on ad hoc basis, will be covered from project-related and other internal funds of the Faculty.

d. Stakeholders involved

GA4		
Implementation	Internal stakeholders	External stakeholders
Co-producing	Involved: Management of the Faculty, Secretary General, appointed person of trust	//
Only consulting	Involved: Gender Equality Advisory Board at UNIBL	Approached: SUPPORTER experienced partners
Only informing	Approached: students, staff	//

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Person of trust having low level of knowledge and skills how to deal with cases of GBV and SH Lack of trust of students and staff to approach and report incidents. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Enabling continuous training and skills development for person of trust. Continuous training, internal communication, informing of students and staff by the person of trust and Faculty management.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Appointing the persons of trust	Management of the Faculty Secretary General Appointed person of trust	Persons of trust appointed	Internal resources – staff External expert advice	April 2024
2. Training for person of trust	Project team	Person of trust participated in at least 2 training sessions	Internal resources – staff External expert advice	May - November 2024

3. Establishing a procedure for reporting GBV and SH at the Faculty level -elaboration of proposal	Management of the Faculty Secretary General Appointed person of trust Gender equality advisory board	Proposal for the procedure for reporting GBV and SH elaborated.	Internal resources – staff	May 2025
4. Adoption of procedures for reporting GBV and SH at the Faculty level	Management of the Faculty	Procedure for reporting GBV and SH established	Internal resources – staff	June 2024

GA5 – Sharing knowledge on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment

Based on the very low acknowledgement regarding this issue among academic staff and student at the Faculty there is an evident need for further actions towards raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment. This GA develops and implements awareness-raising activities on GBV and sexual harassment in sport environment and promote existing achievements from university level.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

The main goal of this activity is to share knowledge to students and Faculty staff on how to recognise and act upon gender-based violence and sexual harassment in sports environment and in general. It entails regular training for staff and students during the academic year, as well as obligatory introduction workshop at the beginning of academic year for freshly enrolled students where they will be introduced with the Guidelines for prevention of GBV and SH as well as with the procedures established at the Faculty including the person of trust.

c. Implementation plan

The following activities will be carried out to implement this GA: a) promotion of existing Guidelines for prevention of GBV and SH adopted at university level, and b) sharing knowledge to students and staff how to recognise GBV and SH in the sports environment.

- 1) Selection of experts for promotion of the Guidelines and raising activities
- 2) Promotion of the Guidelines for prevention of GBV and SH and raising awareness workshop

Success criteria:

- One training events organised for staff and for students
- One introduction workshop organised for freshly enrolled students
- At least 12 participants of academic staff and 25 students per workshop gathered.
- At least 20 freshly enrolled students passed through the obligatory workshop.
- Increased knowledge of students and staff on GBV and SH in the sports environment, as well as on procedures and steps to follow in cases of GBV and SH.

Implementing team: SUPPORTER project team at the Faculty (with support, when needed, from the UNIBL Gender Equality Advisory Board and SUPPORTER project experienced organisations).

Resources needed: external expert advice (*sought externally either through SUPPORTER network, or University Gender Equality Advisory Board network*); classroom (*available internally*); funds for covering the costs of engaging external experts.

d. Stakeholders involved

GA5		
Implementation	Internal stakeholders	External stakeholders
Co-producing	Involved: Faculty management, appointed person of trust, SUPPORTER project team at the Faculty	Involved: External experts (co-creation of training content)
Only consulting	Approached: Gender Equality Advisory Board	Approached: SUPPORTER experienced partners
Only informing	Approached: students, staff	//

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reluctance of staff and students to attend the training and workshops 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing (and communicating) clear description of the content and objectives of the training and workshops • For freshly enrolled students -making the workshop obligatory as the first introductory class at the beginning of academic year.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline

1. Selection of experts for promotion of the Guidelines and raising activities	Project team Gender equality advisory board Appointed person of trust	List of lecturers defined	External expert advice	October 2024
2. Promotion of the Guidelines for prevention of GBV and SH and raising awareness workshop	Vice-dean for human resources External experts Project team	One training event organised for staff and for students One introduction workshop organised for freshly enrolled students At least 12 participants of academic staff and 25 students per workshop gathered At least 20 freshly enrolled students passed through the obligatory workshop Increased knowledge of students and staff on GBV and SH in sport environment, as well as on procedures and steps to follow in cases of GBV and SH.	Funds for covering the costs of engaging external expert Classroom	December 2024

Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: The objective is to institutionalize the 4I-GEP within the framework of the UNIBL Roadmap by securing formal commitment through a structured approval process, thereby ensuring the sustainability and long-term impact of its achievements.

Implementation plan

To obtain formal approval for the new Gender Equality Plan (GEP) within UNIBL/FFVS organization under the SUPPORTER project, the following steps must be followed:

- a) Defined all stakeholders that need to be involved in creating GEP at the faculty level (GEP FFVS)
- b) Align GEP actions with the overall SUPPORTER roadmap and with already existing GEP at the UNIBL,
- c) Communicate draft version of the GEP FFVS with the management of the faculty
- d) Adopting final version of GEP FFVS

Success criteria:

Gender equality plan at the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport, University of Banjaluka, adopted.

Implementing team: SUPPORTER project team at the Faculty (with support, when needed, from the UNIBL Gender Equality Advisory Board and SUPPORTER project experienced organisations), faculty management, student's organisation representatives, Union president, Secretary general.

Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> A lack of understanding of the importance of the document for the needs of the faculty. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> explain how the document aligns with the faculties and universities strategic goals, accreditation requirements, or policy obligations.

Timeline

Activity (Step)	Involved stakeholders	Required resources	Timeline
1. Defining the team for creating GEP	Supporter team, Dean, Secretary general, Union president, student representatives, Gender equality advisory board representative	Classroom External advice-Supporter	January 2025
2. Drafting the Gender equality plan at the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport			February/April 2025
3. Discussing the GEP with the staff and receiving feedback			April/May 2025
4. Adoption of the GEP by the Faculty council			May/June 2025

2. University of Ljubljana, Faculty of sport (UL)

Summary of changes

GA1 – Analysis of gender balance at Faculty of Sport and establishing mechanism for collecting data

In the analysis of gender balance at the Faculty of Sport, we incorporated intersectional aspects to provide a more comprehensive perspective. For employees, we collected and analysed data on nationality and age, offering insights into additional dimensions of diversity within the faculty. The report was completed in October 2024, ensuring an up-to-date overview of these critical factors. This adjustment was inspired by the intersectionality exercise conducted during the Thessaloniki Mutual Learning Workshop of the project.

GA2 – Raising awareness on gender + inequalities in sports environment and communicating the content, objectives and progress of the GEP + awareness-raising initiatives on Gender-Based Violence

The local outreach events (two train-the-trainer sessions) planned for autumn 2024 will take place in spring 2025 (the organiser of these trainings is the Olympic Committee of Slovenia and we have no influence on the dates). As we consider it important to spread knowledge about gender equality among coaches as well, the dates for the implementation have been adjusted.

We have not developed a platform with GEP-related documents, the documents are integrated into our existing website. The change is positive both financially and in terms of outreach, as the faculty's website is already well known.

GA3 – Development of the Confidential Help System

The confidential persons were not selected through a public call but were instead personally invited by our management. As a relatively small organization, we could afford this approach, given that we are well-acquainted with each other. This allowed us to appoint individuals as confidential persons who are best suited for the role, both in terms of their expertise and availability.

We also aimed to appoint students as confidential persons; however, this is not currently possible due to restrictions in the University's regulations. We plan to propose an amendment to these regulations, which would include the possibility of appointing students as confidential persons and will submit this suggestion to our University for consideration.

GA4 – Encouragement of Gender Equality in the distribution of research resources

No changes were made.

GA5 – Use of gender-sensitive language

No changes were made.

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
GA 1	Incorporated intersectional aspects, report completed on October 24.	Inspired by training.
GA 2	Change of date for local outreach events (two train-the-trainer sessions).	New dates from the event organiser.
GA 2	GEP-related documents integrated into our existing website.	Financially more advantageous and better outreach.
GA 3	Revised selection procedure for confidential persons.	Appointing individuals as confidential persons who are best suited for the role.
GA 3	No students as confidential persons.	Restrictions in our University's regulations.

Grounding Actions

A set of 5 Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5
<i>Intersectional</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Innovative</i>			x		
<i>Inclusive</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Impactful</i>	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Tailored to sports</i>	x	x	x	x	x

GA1 – Analysis of gender balance at Faculty of Sport and establishing mechanism for collecting data

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring.

b. Objectives

1. Analysis of gender distribution.
2. Leadership and committee composition analysis.
3. Data collection on gender-based incidents.
4. Analysis of results and report preparation.

c. Implementation plan

1. Analysis of gender distribution:

- To obtain existing data on gender diversity in various studying programs (students), administrative staff, researchers, pedagogical staff. Focus on methods, competent body and frequency of the existing gender audit mechanisms.
- To analyse the data to determine the gender balance across different roles within the faculty.
- Identify what data is not being collected and suggest enrichment of the data collection and analysis process with new areas to be monitored.

2. Leadership and committee composition analysis:

- Review organisational charts and committee membership to assess gender representation in leadership positions and decision-making bodies.

- Identify any gender disparities in leadership roles and committee memberships.

3. Data collection on gender-based incidents:

- To track the number of reported incidents of sexual violence, harassment, or discrimination over a specific period (last 3 years).
- Document the nature of each incident and the actions taken in response.

4. Analysis of results and report preparation:

- Prepare a report summarising the findings on gender equality in the faculty
- Plan further steps to improve gender diversity and awareness of the GEP.

d. Stakeholders involved

1. Project team:

- Analysing the data, preparing the report and planning further steps to improve gender diversity at the faculty.

2. Human resources department:

- Preparing the data about gender distribution across different roles and levels within faculty.

3. Management and Human resources department:

- Gathered insights on number of reported incidents of sexual violence, harassment, or discrimination over a specific period.
- Gathered insights on the nature of each incident and the actions taken in response.

e. Potential obstacles

- Low engagement (due to limited time, inadequate efforts for the recruitment of participants, little interest on gender equality)
- Internal resistances (to identify the need or value of expanding the gender audit or to give prominence to latent inequalities, to share the relevant data)

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Analysis of gender distribution	Project team Human resources department	Report about the current situation	Human resources Data analysis tools	March – June 2024
Analysis on leadership committee composition	Project team Human resources department	Report about the current situation	Human resources Data analysis tools	March – June 2024

Data collection and data analysis on gender-based incidents	Management Human resources department	Report about the current situation	Human resources Data analysis tools	March – June 2024
Analysis of results and report preparation	Project team	Written report summarising the findings and recommendations	Human resources Data analysis tools	June-July 2024

GA2 – Raising awareness on gender + inequalities in sports environment and communicating the content, objectives and progress of the GEP + awareness-raising initiatives on Gender-Based Violence

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Public document and Awareness-raising

b. Objectives

1. Develop an internal (for faculty staff and students) and external (for external stakeholders) communication campaign.
2. Organise informational sessions and workshops (three international sessions (2 for faculty staff (researchers, administrative staff), 1 for students), two local events for external stakeholders).
3. Develop an online platform with GEP related documents (accessible for internal and external stakeholders).
4. Participation at events related to sports higher education institutions (at least three events).

c. Implementation plan

1. Communication campaign:
 - Develop a communication campaign scheme.
 - Design the campaign.
 - Launch the campaign.
2. **Organising informational sessions and workshops for faculty staff and students:**
 - Organise sessions and workshops to introduce faculty members, staff and students to the content of GEP (three internal sessions).
 - Provide an overview of the objectives (ppt presentations), key components and importance of the GEP in promoting gender equality within the faculty.
 - Encourage participants to express their opinions and concerns ('sticker' workshop) and provide information about gender diversity at the faculty.
 - Organise two local events to showcase the benefits of GEP in the making.
3. **Develop online platform with GEP related documents:**
 - Create a dedicated section on the faculty website or intranet portal where individuals can access GEP-related documents, resources, and updates.
4. Participation at events related to sports higher education institutions (at least three events).

d. Stakeholders involved

1. Project team:

- Organising informational sessions, workshops and events, provide information about gender diversity.
- Participation at events related to sports higher education institutions (at least 3 events).

2. Project team and Department for multimedia:

- Develop, design and launch the communication campaign.
- Publication of GEP-related documents.

e. Potential obstacles

- Low engagement of participants (lack of time/interest of faculty staff, students and external participants to attend informational sessions, workshops and events).
- Lack of financial resources.
- Internal resistances (e.g. the campaign does not get approval).

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Develop communication campaign scheme	Project team Department multimedia for	Communication campaign plan	Human resources	April – May 2024
Design the campaign	Project team Department multimedia for	Campaign material	Multimedia tools Human resources	May – June 2024
Launch the campaign	Project team Department multimedia for	Clarity understanding and Inclusivity	Communication platforms Multimedia tools and Human resources	June – October 2024
Organising informational sessions and workshops	Project team	Feedback from participants	Human resources	April 2024 – June 2025
Develop online platform with GEP related documents	Project team Department multimedia for	Developed platform	Human resources Software/technological equipment	March – October 2024
Participation at events related to	Project team	Participation at least 3 events	Human resources	March 2024 – June 2025

sports education institutions	higher education institutions			
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GA3 – Development of the Confidential Help System

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

1. Appointing Confidential persons.
2. Knowing who victims/survivors can turn to if they come across Violence, Harassment or Bullying.
3. Establish a system for documenting inquiries and resolutions while ensuring anonymity.
4. Ensuring awareness of the Policy on Measures to Combat Violence, Harassment and Bullying.
5. Education and training for confidential persons.

Confidential help system will be maintained beyond the project duration - Confidential Persons will work on a voluntary basis (our University practise), free trainings for Confidential Persons will be provided by our University

Since the confidential help system will be voluntary, it is important to outline incentives for participation like highlighting the importance of the role, relief from other tasks and allow staff more time to engage. Students can get extra credits or reference letters.

For sustainability beyond the project, training and education will be provided, that means regular workshops for new confidential helpers, continuous monitoring and evaluation.

In the future, efforts will be done to secure permanent financial sources.

c. Implementation plan

1. **Appointing Confidential persons.**
 - Approval of new appointment by senior management.
 - Preparation of the call for publication.
 - Publication of the call for confidential persons.
 - Selection procedure.
 - Notification of selection.
2. Knowing to whom victims/survivors can turn to if they come across Violence, Harassment or Bullying.
 - Publication of the list and contact details of confidential persons on the UL FŠ website.
 - Informing staff and students by email.

3. Establishment of a system for documenting inquiries and resolutions while ensuring anonymity.
 - Participation of management and confidential persons in university trainings.
 - Collaboration with legal experts to ensure compliance with confidentiality regulations.
4. Education and training for confidential persons.
 - Participation of confidential persons in university trainings.

d. Stakeholders involved

1. Project team:
 - Cooperation with management.
2. Management and Human Resources:
 - Appointing Confidential persons.
 - Collaboration with legal experts to ensure compliance with confidentiality regulations.
3. Department for multimedia:
 - Assistance in preparing presentations.
 - Publication of confidential persons on the UL FŠ website.
4. Confidential persons:
 - Collaboration with legal experts to ensure compliance with confidentiality regulations.
 - Education and training.

e. Potential obstacles

- Gender equality (men as Confidential person).
- Completion of their studies (students as Confidential persons).
- Availability of trainings for confidential persons.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Preparation of the call for confidential persons	Management Human Resources	Prepared call	Human resources	April – October 2024
Publication of the call for confidential persons	Management Human Resources	Publication of the call	Human resources	October 2024
Selection procedure of the confidential person's call	Management Human Resources	Selection procedure carried out	Human resources	November 2024

Notification selection of	Management Human Resources	Notification sent	Human resources	November 2024
Training of confidential persons	Confidential persons	Participation in trainings	Human resources External trainers	December 2024
Establishment of a system for documenting inquiries and resolutions while ensuring anonymity	Project team Confidential persons Management IT team	New reporting system set up and running	Human resources Software and technological equipment	January 2025
Publication of the list and contact details of confidential persons on the UL FŠ website	Department for multimedia	Publication on the website	Human resources	January 2025
Informing staff and students by email about confidential persons	Management and Human Resources	Email sent	Human resources	January 2025
Collaboration with legal experts to ensure compliance with confidentiality regulations	Management and confidential persons	At least one collaboration within the year	Human resources	From February 2025 on

GA4 – Encouragement of Gender Equality in the distribution of research resources

a. GEP element

Thematic: Integration of gender dimension into research and teaching content

b. Objectives

- Collecting data on current projects and resources.
- Gender balance in the distribution of research resources.
- Gender balance in participation in projects.
- Encouraging research projects to be led by younger women and promoting the creation of gender- balanced research teams.

c. Implementation plan

1. Collecting data on current projects and resources.
 - Analysis of the current situation - overview of gender representation in ongoing research projects.

2. Gender balance in the distribution of research resources.
 - Promoting gender balance from the start of the project's application process.
 - Presentations of benefits of gender equality at the academic assembly.
 - Conversations with research projects leaders.
3. Gender balance in participation in projects.
 - Promoting gender balance from the start of the project's application process.
 - Presentations of benefits of gender equality at the academic assembly.
 - Conversations with research projects leaders.
4. Encouraging research projects to be led by younger women and promoting the creation of gender- balanced research teams.
 - Promoting gender balance from the start of the project's application process.
 - Conversations with younger researchers.

d. Stakeholders involved

1. Project team:
 - Presentations at the academic assembly.
2. Research office:
 - Analysis of the current situation.
 - Promoting gender balance from the start of the project's application process.
 - Conversations with projects leaders and younger researchers.

e. Potential obstacles

- Negative project leaders' response.
- Younger researchers will not want to take on this role.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Analysis of the current situation	Research office	Report about the current situation	List of ongoing projects Human resources	April 2024 June 2025
Promoting gender balance from the start of the project's application process	Research office	Conversations with applicants carried out	Research office Consultant	From February 2024 on
Presentations of benefits of gender	Project team	Presentation made	Literature Presentation	September 2024

equality at the academic assembly			Human resources	
Conversations with research projects leaders	Research office	Conversations with research leaders carried out	Research office Consultant	From February 2025 on
Conversations with younger researchers	Research office	Conversations with younger researchers carried out	Research office Consultant	From February 2025 on

GA5 – Use of gender-sensitive language

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Gender equality in recruitment and career progression; Work-life balance and organisational culture

b. Objectives

1. Assessment and Analysis.
2. Development of guidelines and resources.
3. Providing Feedback and Correction.

c. Implementation plan

1. Assessment and Analysis
 - Comprehensive assessment of current language usage and practices across various aspects of the faculty, including official documents, communication channels, forms, and educational materials.
 - Identify areas where gender-sensitive language can be improved or integrated more effectively.
2. Develop guidelines and resources
 - Develop comprehensive guidelines and resources that outline best practices for using gender-sensitive language in written and verbal communication.
 - Provide examples, templates, and practical tips to support individuals and departments in adopting inclusive language practices.
3. Providing Feedback and Correction
 - Encourage individuals to offer feedback and corrections when they detect language that lacks inclusivity.
 - Fostering a culture where everyone feels accountable for promoting inclusive language usage.

d. Stakeholders involved

1. Project team:

- Assessment of current language usage.
- Identify areas where gender-sensitive language can be improved.
- Develop comprehensive guidelines and resources.
- Provide examples, templates, and practical tips.
- Encourage individuals to offer feedback and corrections.
- Fostering a culture for promoting inclusive language usage.

2. Human resources office:

- Assessment of current language usage.
- Identify areas where gender-sensitive language can be improved.

3. Quality assurance office:

- Assessment of current language usage.
- Develop comprehensive guidelines and resources.
- Provide examples, templates, and practical tips.
- Encourage individuals to offer feedback and corrections.

e. Potential obstacles

- Low interest of Staff
- Resistance to change
- Lack of awareness and understanding
- Cultural and linguistic challenges

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Assessment and Analysis	Project team Human resources office Quality assurance office	Report	Human resources	September 2024
Develop guidelines and resources	Project team Quality assurance office	Guidelines made	Literature Human resources	November 2024
Providing Feedback and Correction	Project team Quality assurance office	Feedback received	Feedback mechanism Human resources	November 2024

Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: to secure formal institutional commitment to the 4I-GEP through a structured approval process, and ensure the lasting effect of the roadmap's achievements.

Implementation plan

To achieve formal approval of the Institutional 4I-GEP within our organization, the following steps must be followed:

1. Preparation of the draft by the internal core team (January - February 2025)

The process begins with the development of a comprehensive draft for the Institutional 4I GEP by the core team. This step includes thorough analysis and preparation to ensure that the plan aligns with organizational goals and lessons learned from SUPPORTER trainings and Institutional roadmap implementation.

2. Involvement of focus group (March 2025)

A focus group consisting of staff (researchers, pedagogical staff and administrative staff) and students will be consulted. The purpose of this step is to gather different perspectives, identify potential issues and ensure inclusion in the planning process.

3. Adaptation based on feedback from the focus group (April 2025)

The feedback collected from the focus group will be reviewed and the draft proposal will be adjusted accordingly. This will ensure that the Institutional 4I-GEP reflects the needs and suggestions of the stakeholders involved.

4. Adoption by the Dean's collegium (April - May 2025)

The revised proposal will be submitted to the Dean's collegium for approval. This step ensures that the management supports and endorses the plan before it is submitted for final approval.

5. Approval by the Senate of the Faculty of Sport, University of Ljubljana (May - June 2025)

The final step will be to submit the proposal to the Senate of the Faculty of Sport for official approval. This marks the official approval of the Institutional 4I-GEP within our organization.

Stakeholders that need to be involved: internal SUPPORTER core team, management, researchers, pedagogical staff, administrative staff, students, senate members.

Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited engagement or participation of stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Actively communicate the purpose and benefits of the Institutional 4I-GEP. Identify and involve key influencers within each stakeholder group to encourage broader participation.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Delays in timeline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Plan for contingency time within the timeline to absorb minor delays without impacting the overall timeline.

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges in Senate approval 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide clear, evidence-based arguments to address potential concerns and ensure the proposal is well-prepared for the final approval.
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Timeline

<i>Activity (Step)</i>	<i>Involved stakeholders</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
<i>Draft by the internal core team</i>	Core team	Literature, project documentation, human resources	January – February 2025
<i>Focus group</i>	Core team, researchers, pedagogical staff, administrative staff, students	Human resources, feedback mechanism	March 2025
<i>Draft adaption</i>	Core team	Human resources	April 2025
<i>Adoption by the Dean’s collegium</i>	Management	Human resources	April – May 2025
<i>Approval by the Senate</i>	UL FŠ senate members	Human resources	May – June 2025

3. Charles University (Faculty of Physical Education and Sport)

Summary of changes

GA1 – no changes were made.

GA2 – Forming educational modules and material for staff and students on gender, sexuality and intersectionality

The original GA2 focused on developing and implementing workshops and training sessions on gender+ equality topics, aiming to raise awareness and build capacity among staff members. The focus was primarily on gender+ equality, without a specific emphasis on broader social security issues, including gender-based violence (GBV).

Updated Scope and Implementation:

*During the reporting period, our faculty decided to expand the scope of GA2 by integrating **social security training**, a program piloted at the university rectorate. This program demonstrated its value in addressing social security concerns comprehensively, and we opted to collaborate with the rectorate to adapt and include this initiative in our roadmap. This change arose from identified needs within our faculty, particularly the importance of creating a safe and supportive work environment.*

Piloting Phase (Winter Semester 2024):

The Social Security Course was piloted at the rectorate level during the winter semester of 2024. The pilot phase targeted a small group of staff across the university and focused on key topics such as workplace safety, equity, and GBV prevention. Feedback gathered from participants informed refinements in the course structure and content.

Faculty Implementation Plan (2025):

Building on the success of the rectorate's pilot, our faculty will implement the course mandatorily for all employees in the first half of 2025. This marks an important step in localizing the program and ensuring alignment with our institutional priorities. The course will feature two tailored training streams:

- 1. Academic Staff: The training for academic employees will focus on integrating social security and gender+ equality considerations into teaching, research, and academic interactions, including addressing power dynamics with students.*
- 2. Non-Academic Staff: The training for non-academic employees will concentrate on creating a safe and equitable administrative and operational environment, highlighting the importance of respectful communication and proactive conflict resolution.*

Reflection on Changes:

This update reflects a broadening of GA2 to include social security as a core element, addressing identified gaps in the original plan. The inclusion of mandatory training ensures consistent engagement across all staff levels and signals the institution's commitment to fostering a safe and inclusive environment. Moreover, tailoring the content for academic and non-academic staff acknowledges the diverse roles and responsibilities within our faculty, enhancing the relevance and impact of the training.

GA3 – Training activities on how gender impacts sports research

Due to unforeseen circumstances, specifically the tragedy at Charles University in December 2023, a series of mandatory security-related trainings were introduced across the institution. These sessions were critical for addressing immediate concerns and ensuring the safety and well-being of staff and students. As a result, capacity for implementing additional workshops or training sessions, including those planned under GA3, became significantly limited.

To adapt to this challenge, the gender equality training activities originally scheduled for the latter half of 2024 have been postponed to the first half of 2025. This postponement allows for a more structured and impactful implementation without overburdening faculty resources or staff schedules.

Justification for Change

- 1. Institutional Priorities: The unexpected introduction of security-focused training took precedence, leaving limited capacity for other workshops during the same period.*
- 2. Resource Allocation: With faculty and administrative resources redirected to address urgent security concerns, it was essential to avoid compromising the quality and effectiveness of the gender equality trainings.*
- 3. Maintaining Impact: Postponing the training activities ensures that sufficient time, attention, and resources can be devoted to their planning and execution, maximizing their long-term impact.*

GA3 – No changes made.

GA4 – Gathering information on GBV and sexual harassment

During the local outreach event in October, we distributed questionnaires designed to gather information on gender-based violence (GBV) and sexual harassment. Feedback collected from the event revealed that the original questionnaire format did not fully address the distinct needs and perspectives of academic employees, non-academic employees, and students.

As a result, we decided to revise the questionnaires to make them more suitable for these specific groups. The updated questionnaires are designed to capture the unique challenges and experiences faced by each group within the context of GBV and sexual harassment, ensuring more accurate and relevant data collection.

Currently, we are in the process of finalizing the revisions to the questionnaires and continuing with the data collection phase. The revised questionnaires will be distributed to the relevant stakeholders once they are ready.

Timeline Adjustment:

This adjustment to the questionnaires and the continuation of data collection has slightly shifted the timeline from the initial plan, but we expect to complete the data gathering and analysis in the coming months. The revised questionnaires will enable a more comprehensive understanding of the GBV and harassment issues across different groups within the institution.

GA5 – no changes were made

GA6 – no changes were made

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
GA2	Inclusion of mandatory Social Security Course/training for all staff + timeline adjustment	The change involves integrating a Social Security Course, piloted at the rectorate level, into our roadmap. The course will become mandatory for all faculty staff in 2025, with two tailored streams for academic and non-academic staff. The timeline is adjusted to reflect a mandatory rollout for all faculty staff in the first half of 2025.

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
GA3	Timeline adjustment + new resources allocation	The tragedy at Charles University in December 2023 required the implementation of mandatory security-focused trainings. Limited capacity and resource constraints made it necessary to postpone the planned gender equality training activities to the first half of 2025. Faculty and administrative efforts were temporarily redirected to address immediate safety concerns. This adjustment ensures that sufficient time and resources will be available for effective implementation of the postponed activities.

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
GA4	Revision of questionnaires + time adjustment	The need to revise the questionnaires arose after feedback from the local outreach event in October

		2024. This revision aims to ensure more relevant and accurate data collection for each group.
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Grounding Actions

A set of 6 Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5	GA6
<i>Intersectional</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Innovative</i>		x	x		x	x
<i>Inclusive</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Impactful</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Tailored to sports</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender+ equality and inequalities in sports environments

GA1 is focused on raising awareness activities on gender equality and understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases in the academic sport environment.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

b. Objectives

- To get the topic of gender equality on the organisation's/faculty's agenda
- To promote a uniform understanding on the concept of gender+ equality in higher education
- Raise awareness and understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases in the sports environment both at institutional and at local/national level.

c. Implementation plan

1. Set up a working team (incl. comms, students and/or staff) and clearly allocate tasks

2. Develop the scheme (Define objectives, target audience, timeframe and budget, activities and desired outcome)
3. Design the material (define appropriate channels, create the visuals)
4. Finalise the material and seek approval (if necessary)
5. Implement the activities (Suggested activities: Workshop/panel discussion events for academic/admin staff and students – e.g. for new students in induction week, 1 local stakeholder event for external stakeholders, 1 social media campaign)
6. Impact evaluation and suggestion for future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, GE expert at Uni/Faculty, students and staff reps

Only consulting: GE/Ethics Committee, mid-level management, external consultants

Only informing: High-level management, external stakeholders

e. Potential obstacles

- Low engagement of participants (lack of time/interest of faculty staff, students and external participants to attend informational sessions, workshops and events).
- Lack of financial resources
- Internal resistances (e.g. the campaign does not get approval)

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Develop communication campaign scheme	Project team	Communication campaign plan	Human resources	April – May 2024
Design the campaign	Project team Department multimedia for	Campaign material	Multimedia tools Human resources	May – June 2024
Launch the campaign: Organising informational sessions and workshops	Project team	Feedback from participants No. of participants	Communication platforms Multimedia tools and Human resources	June – October 2024
Develop an online platform with GEP related documents	Project team Department multimedia for	Developed platform	Human resources Software/technological equipment	March – May 2024

Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms	Human resources	October – November 2024
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GA2 – Forming educational modules and material for staff and students on gender, sexuality and intersectionality

Co-operation and co-creation with knowledgeable staff in the areas of gender, sexuality and intersectionality from other faculties to form educational modules for staff and students.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

Thematic: Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

b. Objectives

These actions aim to improve the general knowledge of gender, sexuality and intersectionality by enriching existing courses with gender-sensitive topics and encourage greater participation of students within and beyond the faculty of physical education and sport. Collaboration with academic staff at university level to create holistic educational materials will address the current knowledge gap and increase teaching standards and curricula. **Additionally, the scope of this GA has been expanded to integrate social security training, including workplace safety, equity, and gender-based violence (GBV) prevention. This decision follows a successful pilot at the university rectorate and addresses the faculty's commitment to fostering a safe and supportive work environment.** This approach not only aims to improve the academic community's general knowledge on these topics but also to create a supportive environment that encourages exploration and understanding of complex social issues, ultimately contributing to a more inclusive and informed academic setting.

c. Implementation plan

To enhance gender sensitivity in our educational and research practices, we have laid out a focused implementation plan. Our first step involves integrating gender-sensitive elements into the teaching of an existing Research methodology course for doctoral students. The effectiveness of this initiative will be judged by updates to the course syllabus, participation rates of doctoral students, and their feedback. Essential resources for this include expert consultations and training materials for the instructors.

Simultaneously, we will enrich the subjects "Academic Writing" (focused on work with publication activity/results of scientific work) and "Violence, Individual, and Society" courses for undergraduates with gender dimension discussions, managed by Undergraduate Program Coordinators and course instructors. This will necessitate revised course materials and instructor training on gender issues.

FPES will also initiate the co-creation and wide distribution of educational materials, specifically brochures and information leaflets focusing on gender, sexuality, and intersectionality. These materials will be disseminated to both staff and students, extending from the university level down to our faculty, ensuring a broad reach and impact. This effort aims to provide accessible, foundational knowledge that supports further learning and discussion within our academic community.

To support active learning and engagement, FPES will promote and motivate students into enrolment in relevant subjects. This includes courses offered within our faculty and those available in other faculties, covering lectures and seminars on gender, sexuality, and intersectionality. By doing so, we intend to foster a multidisciplinary learning environment that encourages a deeper understanding of these critical issues.

In addition to these educational efforts, the faculty will implement mandatory Social Security training for all staff, following the pilot course conducted at the rectorate level in Winter Semester 2024. The faculty's rollout in 2025 will feature two tailored training streams:

- **Academic Staff:** This training will focus on integrating social security and gender+ equality considerations into teaching, research, and academic interactions, particularly regarding power dynamics with students.
- **Non-Academic Staff:** This training will emphasize workplace safety, respectful communication, and proactive conflict resolution, ensuring an equitable and supportive work environment

The effectiveness of these actions will be measured by updated course syllabi, student enrolment numbers, course feedback, and participation in the mandatory Social Security training. Additionally, metrics will include number of digital and physical brochures/leaflets distributed throughout the university and faculty levels.

d. Stakeholders involved

Project team, Study department, Academics, Department of Internal Affairs, Department of International Relations, Students, Rectorate (CU Point/Board for Social Affairs and Sustainable Development/Council for Equal Opportunities), **Rectorate-level Social Security experts and trainers**

e. Potential obstacles

- Resistant attitudes amongst staff and students. This could be overcome by targeted promotion and education based not only on faculty management, but also on key players from among students and employees.
- Lack of financial resources for the training of the module instructors
- **Potential logistical challenges in implementing the Social Security course as mandatory training across all staff categories, requiring close coordination with the rectorate.**

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
Assess training needs of course teachers	Project team GE experts at Uni	Focus groups to discuss and identify needs	Human resources	April 2024
Training of course teachers	Project team GE experts at Uni External experts	Increased knowledge of course teachers on GE issues	Human resources External expertise Venue	April – May 2024
Review existing material on selected courses	Course teachers Project team	Report on suggested areas for improvement	Human resources	May – June 2024
Revise and enrich course syllabi and material	Course teachers Project team	Consultation process with external experts Revised course material	Human resources External expertise	June – September 2024
Pilot Social Security Course at the rectorate level	Rectorate, Project team	Feedback from participants, refinement of materials	Training materials, participant input	Winter Semester 2024 (November-December)
Finalise course material and seek approval	Course teachers Upper management	Approved syllabi and course material	Human resources	September 2024
Implement mandatory Social Security training for all staff	Faculty management, Project team	Completion rates for staff participation	Training resources, facilitators	First half of 2025 (March/April 2025)
Inform students/staff of new, gender-sensitive course content (e.g. in induction week)	Course teacher Project team Communication team	Increased student enrolment (10-20) Student feedback	Human resources Communication/evaluation tools	September 2024 – January 2025
Compilation and revision of educational material	Project team Internal Affairs	Revised educational material	Human resources (time for revision) Revised educational material Expert consultation	April – May 2024

Distribution of educational material	Internal Affairs Department	Number of digital/physical distribution	of Human resources Communication tools	July – August 2024
	International Relations Department Rectorate Communication team			

GA3 – Training activities on how gender impacts sports research

Training for both domestic and international researchers on how gender impacts sports research, e.g. methodologies, sampling, inclusive and intersectional practices.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

Thematic: Integrating the gender dimension into research and teaching content

b. Objectives

The purpose of this action is to fill in knowledge gaps and increase awareness of the impact of gender in sports research. Currently, there is no such training for researchers, causing research output and quality to be lesser than other European higher education research institutes. By improving knowledge of gender amongst the research community, gender equality practices can be mainstreamed through the spread of information and education. The goal is to better equip internal stakeholders so that issues relating to gender in academia can be challenged.

c. Implementation plan

We will organise gender-sensitive research practice training for academics and researchers. This starts with defining the training scheme's objectives, target audience, activities and time plan. After outlining the scheme and individual activities, GE experts will be identified internally and, in case that internal resources are not sufficient, external expertise will be sought. The preparation of the training material precedes the launch of the training scheme. After its completion, the training will be evaluated to identify strengths and weaknesses, amendments will be made and the possibility to repeat on a periodical basis will be explored.

We will measure success through the attendance records, and training reports. Required resources include expert facilitators, session venues or platforms, and training content.

Overall, success will be indicated by updated course syllabi, student participation numbers, and comprehensive training feedback. To support these initiatives, we will discuss allocating a budget for expert consultations, material development, and use communication and evaluation tools to measure impact, aiming to foster a more inclusive academic environment.

d. Stakeholders involved

Project team, Academic employees, Research employees, pre-graduate and postgraduate students, External trainers

e. Potential obstacles

Potential obstacles include student/researcher apathy and a lack of staff to take charge of such training. There could be bigger propagation and motivation for attendance. It is also important to find suitable experts for training.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Define the training scheme	Project team Study department Internal Affairs Department	Outline of planned training	Human resources	May – June 2024
Seeking internal and external expertise	Project team Internal Affairs Department Communications team	List of trainers	Human resources Financial resources for external trainers	July 2024
Preparation of training material	Project team Trainers IT team (if necessary)	PPT presentation Training material	Human resources; Software and other digital tools	September 2024
Delivery of Training for academic/research staff	Internal Affairs department Trainers Project team	Staff participation numbers Feedback	Expert facilitator Communication/evaluation tools	September – November 2024
Impact evaluation	Internal Affairs department Project team	Knowledge increase through knowledge-control pre/post training questionnaire No. of participants Participant feedback	Human resources Evaluation tools	December 2024

GA4 – Gathering information on GBV and sexual harassment

Collection of data on the current state of knowledge regarding GBV at faculty level.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring.

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment.

b. Objectives

These actions aim to understand what the current state of knowledge is within the faculty regarding GBV and sexual harassment, such as, how people think it happens, what counts as GBV/SH, what resources they know are available if GBV/SH occurs. It is unclear what services/resources are available to victims, so clarification is required so that they can seek help quickly. These objectives would address the lack of information regarding GBV and SH available to staff and students.

Originally, we planned to analyze the results of a university-wide questionnaire that had been previously distributed. However, after reviewing the available data, we realized that the existing questionnaire did not fully address the specific needs of our faculty. As a result, we developed and distributed our own faculty-level questionnaire to gain a more tailored understanding of GBV and SH issues within our institution.

c. Implementation plan

FPES originally intended to utilise the results of a university-wide questionnaire that had been previously distributed. However, due to limitations in the existing questionnaire, we created and distributed a faculty-specific questionnaire instead. This allows us to collect more targeted data on the perceptions and awareness of GBV and SH among our staff and students.

Following its initial distribution, we identified the need for revisions to better accommodate different faculty groups. The questionnaire was refined and redistributed, and the collected responses will now serve as the primary source for our analysis.

Indicators:

Successful development, distribution, and refinement of a faculty-specific questionnaire on GBV and SH. Comprehensive analysis of the revised questionnaire data, providing a baseline understanding of GBV and sexual harassment awareness.

d. Stakeholders involved

Project team, Study department, Academics, Department of Internal Affairs, Department of International Relations, Students, Rectorate (CU Point/Board for Social Affairs and Sustainable Development/Council for Equal Opportunities)

e. Potential obstacles

- Lack of understanding

- Low engagement (due to limited time, inadequate efforts for the recruitment of participants, little interest on GBV)
- Lack of financial resources
- Internal resistances (to identify the need or value of a gender audit or to give prominence to latent inequalities)
- **The need for additional time to analyze the revised questionnaires, potentially delaying the overall timeline.**

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Development and distribution of initial faculty-specific questionnaire	Project team	Baseline data collection on GBV and SH within the faculty	Human resources, Consultation with stakeholders	October 2024
Feedback collection from local outreach event	Project team	Identification of limitations in the initial questionnaire	Participant feedback, Survey review	October 2024
Revision and redistribution of faculty-specific questionnaire	Project team	Updated questionnaire tailored to academic staff, non-academic staff, and students	Human resources, Consultation with stakeholders	November 2024-December 2024
Suggestions for additional data collection	Project team, Internal Affairs Department	Report with recommendations	Human resources	November 2024
Suggestions of additional tools for data collection	Project team, Internal Affairs Department	Report with recommended data collection methods/tools beyond the questionnaire	Human resources	November 2024
Analysis of revised questionnaire data	Project team, Internal Affairs Department	Comprehensive insights into GBV and SH across different groups	Staff time for analysis, Consultation with rectorate	March-April 2025

GA5 – Awareness-raising on GBV at institutional level and beyond

This Grounding Action develops and implements an awareness-raising, evidence-based campaign on Gender-Based Violence in the sports context.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

Based on the results of the knowledge-gathering carried out in the previous GA, awareness-raising initiatives and education will address the presented gaps in order to increase understanding among staff and students regarding the concept and forms of gender-based violence (physical, sexual, psychological, economic and financial, sexual harassment, online) in the sports context. This will assist in creating a safe environment and a culture of respect and equality. Also, staff and students will be introduced to the relevant regulatory framework and internal procedures in place (reporting and case management, support mechanisms) in a simple and comprehensive manner. Beyond the institutional level, an awareness-raising event will be organised to extend a uniform understanding of GBV and to promote a culture of zero tolerance towards gender-based violence within the sports context.

c. Implementation plan

Building on the insights gained from the previous GBV information gathering, we will launch awareness-raising and educational activities designed to address identified knowledge gaps. These initiatives will be tailored to our faculty's context, with a particular emphasis on the intersection of GBV, sexual harassment, and sports. Staff and students will be informed of the plan for GBV awareness raising at the Academic meeting in January 2025.

Support from vice-deans (for Internal Affairs and for International Relations) will be crucial in disseminating information and fostering an environment that values and promotes gender equality. Their involvement will help amplify the reach and impact of the messages being communicated, ensuring that the importance of the GEP is recognised at all levels of the faculty (Information will be disseminated mainly at international staff meetings, which happen every month, at meetings happening every week for top and middle management, and through newsletters which go to all employees and students).

Vice-deans and contact persons will also be participating in many GE-oriented events, for example: "Women who inspire" (March 8th), participation in the new EqualEdu project, and participation in the LERU-CE7 international workshop "Inclusive GEPs in FPE10" on March 14th and 15th. This could also help with information dissemination and fostering the environment that promotes gender equality.

Also, a local stakeholder event (e.g. in the form of an awareness day) will be organised to raise awareness of targeted external stakeholders such as sports clubs, trainers, associations, umbrella organisations, public authorities.

Indicators:

Attendance: Attendance records for awareness raising activities will be meticulously maintained. High participation rates will indicate a strong community interest and commitment to addressing GBV and sexual harassment.

Event Report: After the events or activities, we will compile comprehensive event reports. These reports will document the activities conducted, participation levels, participant feedback, and any measurable outcomes or shifts in awareness and understanding among attendees.

After GA4 and GA5, if anyone experiences GBV, firstly there will be an app available for FPES (it is already being prepared), where individuals can report an incident. In the app there will be a chatting function, where an individual reporting an incident will have the possibility to chat with the contact persons at the faculty. Depending on the situation, the individual will have the option to only chat anonymously with the contact person to find a solution, or in more serious cases the individual will have opportunity to decide to meet personally and talk about the incident (thus revealing their identity). Depending on situation and seriousness, incidents are solved either on faculty level with contact persons, or can be pushed to university level for ombuds person. Secondly, as there is already an ombuds person at the university level established and right now 2 contact persons established at the faculty, where students and employees can report any incident (GBV, sexual harassment etc), there is no need to create another contact point/bureau at this stage. Further details on the faculty contact point can be found in GA6 (Redefining the contact persons job description for GEP implementation).

d. Stakeholders involved

Faculty management - contributing to plan development and coordination, overseeing execution

Academics – offering expertise on gender-based violence

Rectorate – EOC - Providing institutional support

Internal Affairs - facilitating communication

International Relations Department, Rectorate – Council of Equal Opportunities, Members of the Rector's Board for Social Affairs and Sustainable Development

e. Potential obstacles

The largest obstacle to this would be securing adequate funds. To prevent this, talks must be held with the relevant managing staff at the rectorate. Currently it is unclear whether internal staff hold the adequate knowledge to host and produce meaningful, well-informed awareness-raising initiatives. This can be overcome through consultation with external experts and putting out a university-wide call for expertise or using information from other projects' toolkits to reinforce knowledge of key actors. Other obstacles include low engagement (due to lack of time/interest), internal and external resistances.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
Development of awareness-raising programme	Project team Internal Affairs department Communications team	Document of the campaign scheme	Human resources	September 2024
Design the material	Project team Internal Affairs Department Communications team	Complete material of the campaign	Software Communication tools Human resources	October – November 2024
Finalise and seek approval	Project team Internal Affairs department Top management	Official approval by the management	Human resources	November 2024
GBV awareness raising promotion at Academic meeting	Student Body Internal Affairs Department Top management (vice-deans)	Staff and student attendance	Human resources Venue	January 2025
Awareness raising activities (campaign/workshop)	Project team International Affairs Department	Event attendance report,	Event venue Staff time (International Affairs Dpt) for organisation	January 2025-June 2025
External stakeholder event	Project team International Affairs	Number of participants	Event venue Human resources	February – March 2025
Evaluate the scheme's impact and explore possibility for future relaunch	Project team International Affairs Department	Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms	Human resources	May – June 2025

GA6 – Redefining the contact persons job description for GEP implementation

This grounding action will expand the existing ombudspersons responsibilities according to implementation of the new GEP.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture; Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment; Gender equality in recruitment and career progression.

b. Objectives

The objective of creating a role dedicated to the execution of these tasks is to maintain accountability. Currently the faculty is reliant on external advisors/ombuds people. Although this should remain as a top-down approach to addressing gender equality, a bottom-up approach could help improve more sympathetic attitudes to the GEP.

c. Implementation plan

To effectively implement the GEP with redefined internal roles aimed at bridging the gap between top-down approaches and grassroots, empathetic engagement, the following structured steps are proposed:

Defining the Mandate for contact persons:

First, a distinction is made between contact roles: one dedicated to employees and another for students. These roles will serve as primary points of contact for all GEP-related inquiries, suggestions, or concerns, ensuring that stakeholders have a clear and accessible channel for communication.

Allocation of Tasks:

Allocate specific tasks associated with each role. This includes the responsibility for forwarding information to all stakeholders, distributing relevant updates, resources, and opportunities through email, and actively mentioning these points during faculty meetings to keep the community informed and engaged.

Seeking Approval from Upper Management:

Present the proposed redefinition of roles and allocation of tasks to upper management (Dean's Board) for approval. This step is crucial for ensuring that the initiative has the necessary backing and authority to be implemented effectively.

Ongoing Training Appointed Gender Equality Persons:

The contact persons are already continuously provided (monthly) with necessary training for the individuals appointed to these positions (ombudspersons positions). Training is provided by a university level ombuds person and covers the methods for effective communication, strategies for promoting gender equality within the institution, mediation etc.

Redefinition of these internal roles aim to bridge the gap between top-down approaches and the need for more grassroots, empathetic engagement with gender equality initiatives.

To effectively implement these redefined tasks, we will start by distinction of the contact roles: one dedicated to employees and another for students. These roles will serve as primary points of contact

for all GEP-related inquiries, suggestions, or concerns, ensuring that stakeholders have a clear and accessible channel for communication.

The responsibility of forwarding information to affected stakeholders will be a key function of these roles. This will include the distribution of relevant updates, resources, and opportunities via email and the active mention of these points during faculty meetings. This ensures that all members of the faculty are kept informed and engaged with the GEP's progress and initiatives.

Indicators:

Number of Requests/Initiatives: Tracking the number of requests or initiatives received by the contact persons for employees and students will serve as a key indicator of engagement and active participation in the GEP. A higher number of requests or initiatives will indicate a growing interest and involvement in gender equality matters within the faculty.

Engagement Metrics: The effectiveness of information dissemination efforts will be measured through engagement metrics, such as the reach of emails, attendance at meetings where GEP initiatives are discussed, reports from these meetings and the level of participation in related activities.

d. Stakeholders involved

Internal Affairs Department, Contact persons for staff and students, Dean's Board

e. Potential obstacles

Since it will not be a primary job but a new added agenda, we can meet with some unwillingness. This could be overcome by giving the person an additional pay to their full-time agreement.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Defining the Mandate for contact persons	Project team Internal Affairs Department	Redefined job description	Human resources	March 2024 – May 2024
Allocation of tasks	Dean's Board	Qualitative assessment of the requests/initiatives by the ombudsperson Job description for ombudsperson	Human resources	June – July 2024
Seeking Approval from Upper Management	Dean's Board	New approved positions	Human resources	September 2024

Training of appointed Gender Equality Persons	Project team Internal Affairs Department External trainers	Increased capacity of GE persons	Human resources; Training material; Financial resources for external expertise/trainings attendance	October – December 2024
Communication of new roles and ways for effective collaboration with relevant institutional bodies	Internal Affairs department Communications team	Information email Meeting with relevant bodies	Human resources	November – December 2024
Support from faculty leaders	Vice-dean for Internal Affairs Vice-dean for International Relations	Number of email reaches Meeting attendance and reports Activity participations	Human resources	January – June 2025

Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: to secure formal institutional commitment to the 4I-GEP through a structured approval process and ensure the lasting effect of the roadmap’s achievements.

Implementation plan

a) Stakeholders to Involve:

- **Dean’s Board:** Essential for formal approval of the 4I-GEP as they have the authority to validate and integrate the plan into the institution’s formal structures.
- **Rectorate:** High-level institutional leadership must approve the 4I-GEP to ensure it has institutional backing.
- **Human Resources (HR):** HR will need to be involved for integration of the new policies into existing staff regulations, especially for training and ongoing professional development.
- **Faculty Staff (Academic and Administrative):** Their feedback is crucial for refining the GEP, ensuring that the plan is feasible and meets the needs of all stakeholders.
- **Ombudsperson:** Will contribute to the review of GBV policies, ensuring that the roadmap addresses the institution’s gender equality issues thoroughly.

b) Time Requirements:

- **Preparation phase:** Gathering feedback, reviewing current GEP policies, and consulting with relevant stakeholders will take approximately **2–3 months**.

- **Approval process:** The formal approval process, including meetings with the Dean’s Board and Rectorate, may require **1–2 months**.
- **Integration and final adjustments:** After approval, further work will be needed to integrate the GEP into institutional processes, which will take **1–2 months**.

c) Overall Timeline of SUPPORTER Project and Roadmap Actions:

Considering the overall timeline of the SUPPORTER project, we aim to complete the institutional approval process by **mid-2025**, aligning with the first half of the year, after finalizing GEP training and adjustments in GA2 and GA3.

This timeline should allow sufficient time to integrate feedback from the pilot phases and finalize the plan. We will also need to ensure that the approval process does not conflict with other mandatory training or institutional requirements.

Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance from faculty or administrative staff 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Engage stakeholders early in the process and ensure regular communication. Hold informational sessions to explain the benefits of the GEP.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delays in approval due to administrative bottlenecks 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Build in additional time to accommodate potential delays. Establish clear communication channels with involved stakeholders to facilitate quick decision-making.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Difficulty in integrating GEP into existing processes 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Offer detailed guidelines on how GEP can be implemented alongside existing policies. Work closely with HR and faculty leadership to ensure smooth integration
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Limited engagement or awareness about the importance of GEP 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide continuous information and training on the significance of the GEP for gender equality and the institution’s broader strategic goals. Use workshops and seminars to raise awareness.

Timeline

Activity (Step)	Involved stakeholders	Required resources	Timeline
Initial review of current GEP and feedback	Dean’s Board, HR, Ombudspersons, Faculty Staff	GEP document, feedback mechanisms, workshops	January – March 2025
Stakeholder meetings and consultations	Dean’s Board, HR, Ombudspersons, Faculty Staff	Meeting rooms, online platforms for virtual meetings	February – April 2025
Finalizing GEP document and adjustments	Dean’s Board, Rectorate, HR	Draft GEP document, external consultants (if needed)	April – May 2025
Formal approval and integration	Dean’s Board, Rectorate	Presentation materials, approval process guidelines	May – June 2025

Full integration	faculty	<i>HR, Ombudspersons</i>	<i>Faculty</i>	<i>Staff,</i>	<i>Training resources, GEP integration materials</i>	<i>From June 2025</i>
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4. National Sports Academy “Vassil Levski” (NSA)

Summary of changes

GA1 – Building a Communication and Networking Policy

- no changes were made

GA2 – Raising Awareness on Gender Equality and Inequalities in Sport Environments

- no changes were made

GA3 – Establishing a Commission for Implementation of the GEP along with Rules for its Functioning

All set functions of the initially planned commission remain the same and only the form of creation had to change – instead of a new commission creation the composition of the existing Academic Ethics Commission was enlarged, and new fields of monitoring and care were added through the rules of functioning of the commission.

Change in GA3, Activity 3.2. The concept of the commission establishment was changed as the change consists in the following – instead of establishing a new an independent commission with a mandate to monitor exclusively the gender equality in the NSA it had been decided to enlarge the tasks and responsibilities of the existing Academic Ethics Commission. This Commission functions as university body to protect among others the rights of both men and women in professional and personal environment.

a) Nature of the Change:

The existing Academic Ethics Commission originally included three members – academic representatives. After the decision of changing, it enlarged its composition from 3 to 5 members as the newly voted 2 members are women. Along with the composition of the Commission the two new members were informed about their specific mission and roles. The adoption of the new Commission composition has passed all procedures for legitimate amendments in internal regulations of NSA.

b) Justification for the Change:

After thorough discussions with the Rector's Board and the Administrative Director regarding the establishment of a Gender Equality Commission, we have concluded that a more effective and sustainable approach would be to expand the scope of the existing Commission for Academic Ethics. This decision was reached based on the following considerations:

1. **Efficient Use of Resources:** Establishing a separate Gender Equality Commission would require additional administrative resources and structures. By incorporating gender equality into the mandate of the Commission for Academic Ethics, we can utilize existing mechanisms and expertise more effectively, ensuring seamless implementation and oversight.
2. **Interconnected Themes:** Issues of gender equality are inherently linked to the principles of academic ethics, such as fairness, inclusivity, and respect. Addressing gender equality within this broader ethical framework ensures that it is treated as an integral component of our institutional values, rather than as a standalone issue.
3. **Broader Institutional Impact:** Expanding the Commission for Academic Ethics allows us to embed gender equality considerations into all aspects of academic and institutional life. This integration reflects our commitment to fostering an inclusive and ethical environment across all levels of the institution.

4. **Inclusivity and Expertise:** To ensure the necessary focus and expertise on gender equality, two additional members with relevant experience and perspectives will be appointed to the Commission. Their input will enrich the Commission's work and ensure that gender equality remains a priority.

c) Intersectionality Requirement: *The change in the GA3 was introduced with a view to get better intersectionality – the existing commission members are aware not only of GE issues, but they have information on all kinds of ethical infringements – concerning age, ethnicity, social origin, level of sports achievements, sport specific issues etc. This allows simultaneous evaluation of problems reported in gender imbalance.*

GA4 – Needs Assessment and Analysis

– no changes were made

GA5 – Creating a gender equality database

5.1 Updated team of responsible actors and inclusion of legal advisor in the working team

5.4 Designing the database, adding content (5.5) and dissemination (5.6) have been merged and become one measure in the GA.

The three measures are very close in their content and expected results and it would be better visible to have them in one activity. 5.5 and 5.6 are deleted. The deadline for the common activity follows the last one in the three – May 2025.

GA 6 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

6.3 Designing the material, Finalise and seek approval (6.4) and launch of activity (6.5) have been merged in one common measure. The three measures do not have separate value and report a common result. That is why it is more efficient to work on them as one activity. The deadline remains May 2025.

GA7 – Use of inclusive language

– the title of the GA was shortened and generalised because attention to the language used is needed not only in regulation documents but in overall speech in teaching and intercommunication.

GA8 – Integrating Gender equality related topics in the Curriculum

– the title underwent small correction with a view of clarification of the meaning.

Grounding Actions

A set of eight Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5	GA6
<i>Intersectional</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x
<i>Innovative</i>	x	x		x		
<i>Inclusive</i>			x	x	x	x
<i>Impactful</i>	x	x		x		x
<i>Tailored to sports</i>		x	x	x		x

GA1 – Building a Communication & Networking Policy

Building an effective communication policy and channels that covers the various dimensions of gender+ equality. Identification of external stakeholders at governmental, local and other universities level. Exchange of information and good practices. To create a dynamic and supportive ecosystem where everyone is actively involved in advancing gender equality, contributing to a workplace and academic environment that is equitable, inclusive, and respectful of diverse personalities and identities.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources; Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture

b. Objectives

The aim of the "Communication and Networking" action within the GEP for the National Sports Academy is to cultivate a culture of awareness, collaboration, and support for gender equality. This initiative seeks to elevate understanding and engagement across all stakeholders, including students, faculty, coaches, and external partners. Through effective communication channels and networking opportunities, the goal is to build a supportive community that values diversity and fosters an environment where every individual feels empowered to contribute to gender equality efforts.

Additionally, the action aims to address concerns through open communication and organise networking events that bring together diverse voices from the sports community. Ultimately, the aim is to create a positive and inclusive organisational culture where gender equality is integral to the identity of the NSA, promoting an environment free from gender-based discrimination. Contribute to building a positive organisational and institutional culture that values gender equality as an integral part of its identity.

c. Implementation plan

1.1 Identifying key internal (within the university, including students, faculty, administrative staff, and alumni) and external stakeholders.

1.2 Defining the communication strategy objectives, tools and task allocation

1.3 Developing communication strategy, including the establishment of regular channels, such as email exchanges, university events, seminars, and departmental meetings, to update stakeholders on GEP progress and initiatives in the Academy and vice versa – the external stakeholders to raise awareness of current issues and national specifics. The communication strategy should be aligned with the university's academic environment to engage these stakeholders effectively.

1.4 Seeking approval for the finalised communication strategy (if necessary)

d. Stakeholders involved

Internal: Besides the main team, there are a number of stakeholders that will be involved in this action. The project team will communicate with the Academic Ethics Commission, Complaints Commission, and the Students Council. There will be a second circle of communication with key persons: The Rector, the Assistant Rector, the Administrative Director, the Legal Advisor, the President of the Student Council, The Deans of the three Faculties, the heads for attestation (every department has a trusted person who is monitoring the academic development).

External: the project team, succeeded by the Gender Equality Commission upon its creation, needs to create a network with the Equal Opportunities, Anti-Discrimination and Social Assistance Unit (EADSU) in the Disability, Equal Opportunities and Social Assistance Policy Directorate (PDEASP) of the Ministry of Labour and Social Affairs. The Unit is also the secretariat of the National Council for Equality between Women and Men of the Council of Ministers. The gender equality coordinator of the regional municipality of Sofia will also be invited to the network. Important stakeholders in the network will be the related NGOs like "Centre for Women's Studies and Policies", "Animus", etc.

e. Potential obstacles

1. Our institution has strong traditions and cultural norms. Overcoming ingrained stereotypes and traditional gender roles may be challenging.
2. Choosing the right communication channels and ensuring their effectiveness can be challenging. Some stakeholders, both internal and external may not be reached through traditional channels, requiring innovative approaches or top-down approach.

3. Limited human resources and work overload may hinder the implementation of comprehensive communication strategies or the organisation of impactful networking events.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1.1 Identifying key stakeholders	Rector Project team	Map of names	Human resources	March – April 2024
1.2 Defining objectives, tools and tasks	Project team Academic Ethics Commission PR Communications department	Outline of the communication strategy	Human resources	April – May 2024
1.3 Development of communication strategy, including communication channels	Project team Rector's board Communications department	Communication strategy document Timetable of events Regular report	Human resources Consultation time Communication tools	May – June 2024
1.4 Seeking approval	Rector's board	Approved strategy	Human resources	June 2024

GA2 – Raising Awareness on Gender+ Equality and Inequalities in Sports Environments

GA2 is focused on raising awareness activities on gender equality and understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases in the academic sport environment.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

b. Objectives

- To get the topic of gender equality on the organisation's/faculty's agenda
- To promote a uniform understanding of the concept of gender equality in higher education
- To integrate discussions on unconscious bias, stereotypes, and the implications of gender inequality on individuals and the broader sports community.

c. Implementation plan

- 2.1 Setting up a working team (incl. academics, students and/or staff) and clearly allocating tasks
- 2.2 Developing the scheme (Define objectives, target audience, timeframe and budget, activities and desired outcome)
- 2.3 Designing the material (define appropriate channels, create the visuals)
- 2.4 Finalising the material and seeking approval (if necessary)
- 2.5 Implementing the activities. These may include: Social media campaigns for commemorating international days associated with gender equality, such as International Women's Day, through the organisation of special events that emphasise the significance of gender inclusivity in the sports arena; Targeted campus events for academic/admin staff and students, one local stakeholder event for external stakeholders)
- 2.6 Evaluating impact and suggestions for future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, PR, Student and staff representatives

Only consulting: Academic Ethics Commission, mid-level management, external consultants

Only informing: High-level management, external stakeholders

e. Potential obstacles

Some individuals within the university community, including faculty, staff, and students, may resist changes in the traditional norms and practices related to gender roles and equality. This could result in vague interest towards the planned events. Deep-seated stereotypes and prejudices related to gender roles in sports may hinder the acceptance of gender equality initiatives. Overcoming these ingrained beliefs can be a significant challenge. The sports university's culture among students may present barriers to the successful implementation of gender equality initiatives. Ensuring active participation and engagement from both students and staff in awareness activities can be a challenge. Apathy or disinterest may hinder the impact of the initiatives.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
2.1 Setting up the working team	Project team PR Student/staff representatives	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024
2.2 Develop an awareness-raising scheme	Working team	Detailed plan	Human resources	April – May 2024
2.3 Design the awareness-raising scheme	Working team Department multimedia for	Communication material Material for the awareness-raising activities	Multimedia tools Human resources	May – June 2024

2.4 Finalise and seek approval	Working team Rector's board	Approved campaign	Human resources	June 2024
2.5 Launch the activities: Organising informational sessions and workshops. Incl. Local stakeholder event	Working team	No. of planned events No. of participants Feedback from participants.	Communication platforms Multimedia tools and Human resources	June – October 2024
2.6 Evaluating impact	Working team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms Number of posts/reactions in social media	Human resources	October 2024 – November 2024

GA3 – Establishing a Commission for Implementation of the GEP along with Rules for its functioning

This activity will mark the beginning of a public expression of the gender equality policy at the National Sports Academy - Sofia. In view of the current administrative structure of the NSA, we will create a database with the available administrative units responsible for gender equality and the responsible persons in cases of gender violence or sexual assault.

The creation of a management capacity with the appointment of responsible persons by name of a collective body for the implementation of the equality policy will give a visible expression of the importance of this policy and give impetus to processes such as monitoring, reporting, training, etc. The commission will be established technically by enlargement of the existing academic ethics commission and approved formally by a decision of the Academic council and Rectors board. This will allow the members of the commission to concentrate exclusively on the issues of gender equality, at the other hand to interconnect it with the general ethics and to develop expertise in a normative and practical aspect. The appointment of a Commission for ensuring gender equality will be combined with the development of rules for the functioning of this commission, which will be adopted by the Academic Council. The approval of this commission by the highest academic body will create recognition of the strategic intentions of management for the sustainable implementation of gender equality policy in the academic and administrative environments.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources; Public document.

b. Objectives

This action corresponds to one of the basic GEP requirements – it will be publicly available, the Commission's members will be known, the results of their activities will be monitored and publicly

available. As such the Commission will rely on commitment of dedicated human resources and gender expertise to implement the GEP. Commission's members will be purposefully qualified and will keep an archive of data and monitoring/evaluation reports. The Commission for ensuring gender equality will respond to the need of more awareness, developed procedures, correspondence of the procedures to the national and European requirements, training events and personal attitude in case of the equality rights infringement.

This action aims to create a set of commitments and actions that will promote gender equality in the organisation (NSA) through a process of structural change.

Specific objectives:

- to create an administrative body in the institution to be responsible for cases of gender discrimination, gender violence, and sexual assault.
- To increase gender expertise within the faculty, with a focus on gender issues in sports environments
- To establish accountability for the implementation and update of the 4I-GEP within the institution/faculty
- To ensure clear task allocation and smooth cooperation among institutional bodies with a similar mandate
- To raise the awareness of academic and non-academic staff, students and young scientists in the NSA on issues of gender inequality, gender rights and the legal rights of every person in this regard.
- To launch structural changes and establish institutional capacity
- To start strategic and policy development with continuity in strategic periods
- To create a degree of understanding and support for the implementation of these policies among the entire academic community
- To ensure the institution's contribution to pan-European social transformation regarding gender equality
- To ensure sustainable transformation in the overall strategic framework

c. Implementation plan

The activity of creating a Commission engaged with ensuring gender equality is long-term and related to a comprehensive academic commitment.

The activity expects to achieve visibility of the problem, demonstrate the determination of the institution's management to maintain a policy of gender equality, involve the entire composition of the academy in dealing with current problems and future challenges, create an example for the younger generation of students for an uncompromising position on the rights of equality in a working environment, in team relationships, in a public national and European framework.

This activity includes the following stages:

3.1 Informing the academic community about the presence of a focus on gender equality in the institutional vision, the need to create organisational capacity and the open possibility of proposing committee members

3.2 Formulation of criteria for selection of candidates for inclusion as members in the commission; these criteria will be consistent with the functions and role of the commission, as well as with the need for the members to benefit from the collective trust

3.3 Determining the members of the Commission based on submitted applications and a conversation with the approved candidates; the Commission will be institutionalised by a decision of the Academic council and will have a mandate, the duration of which will be decided during the implementation of the activity

3.4 Define the mandate of the Commission: Developing rules for the Commission's activity, as well as defining its connections and relations with other bodies related to academic ethics and the institution's relations with external organisations and policies; the rules of activity of the Commission in ensuring gender equality will be voted on by the Academic Council. The Commission will be the first step for establishing structures within the field of research and innovation (R&I) to combat and reduce gender imbalances and inequalities.

3.5 Identifying training needs of the Commission members on gender equality through discussion with GE experts

3.6 Delivery of training for the Commission members according to identified needs

3.7 Meeting of the Commission with relevant institutional bodies to communicate their role and discuss effective ways for collaboration

The main indicators (but not the only ones) that will report the successful progress of the activity will be:

To achieve the goals and results of this activity, both internal resources will be used - teachers who have experience in developing this topic, literature and Internet accessible resources, as well as external expertise - specialists and lecturers from state institutions with leading responsibility for the development of state equality policy and colleagues from other academic institutions who have better experience in establishing equality measures.

In addition to the available resources of researchers and technology, the implementation of the policy to create internal capacity to maintain gender balance and equality will also rely on project activity through developed projects in the fields of education, science, citizens' rights, culture and sports.

The work of the Commission will be visibly considered when evaluating the quality of work of the National Sports Academy. The evaluation of the committee members, as well as the overall achievements of the committee, will be part of the internal evaluation of the academy.

d. Stakeholders involved

Institutionally, the following will be interested in this activity, as well as actively participating in the implementation: the governing bodies of the administration - rector and rector's council, academic council, student council, deans and heads of departments. In the communication of the National Sports Academy outside the institution, the main state bodies will be addressed - the Ministry of Labour and Social Policy, the Ministry of Education and Science, the Scientific Research Fund, the Directorate of Structural Funds at the MES, National Statistics Institute main non-governmental organisations that support the development of equality policy, international organisations.

There will be different levels of participation and support by the stakeholders:

- Level of assistance in training events
- Level of information supply by the governmental institutions
- Level of cooperative work with other academic institutions
- Level of partnership co-working in project frameworks

e. Potential obstacles

There exist some obstacles that should be envisaged and response should be planned in order not to stop the process of implementation and sustainability achievement:

- categorical conviction on the part of the academic staff that there is no need for measures to change the gender culture in the institution

Measure: starting with information materials and discussions on the topic

- lack of broad and in-depth knowledge of European gender equality policy

Measure: discussions with experts and law specialists to gain equal understanding

- lack of systematic approach to tackle the interrelated sub-activities

Measure: coordinated schedule for launching the main training events and the procedure for Commission members appointment

- lack of holistic approach and focusing only on R&D gender equality

Measure: inclusion of representatives from all circles of the academic community in the commission work

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
3.1 Informing the academic community	Rector's Council	Achieved satisfactory awareness level	PR expert Experts for IR	March – October 2024
3.2 Formulation of selection criteria	Rector's council Legal Department	Acceptable criteria for commission's selection	Internal information Available EU publications	September – November 2024
3.3 Recruitment of Commission members	Legal Department	Choice of three or five broadly trusted commission's members	Human Resources Experts preparing amendment on their duties and functions	September – November 2024
3.4 Developing the mandate	Head of main academic units	Document with Commission's mandate	Human resources	September – December 2024

		Established internal structures and capacity pool		
3.5 Identifying training needs	Academic Ethics Commission (AEC) Internal/ external experts	Report on knowledge gaps after meeting with GE experts	Human resources External expertise	November – December 2024
3.6 Training of Commission members	AEC Project member Internal/ external experts	Training material Increased knowledge	Human resources	January – March 2025
3.7 Internal and external communication of the Commission's creation and mandate	Project team members Head of main academic units Deans and Head of Departments	Satisfactory degree of internal communication	Institutional departments (heads and active department members) Communicators with external stakeholders	January – February 2025

GA4 – Needs Assessment and Analysis

Analysing the current situation and drawing up proposals for optimising the existing legal and institutional framework and units.

Will provide an opportunity to define the content and monitoring elements of the institutional needs analysis, annual performance measurement and new GEP areas of priority. Outsource the collection of data and include the results as part of the institution's internal quality and performance report.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring

b. Objectives

To date statistical information on gender balance is presented at the national level every three months to the NACID (National Information and Documentation Centre). This action aims to generate information regarding the institution's state-of-play, including perceptions on gender equality, and to determine relevant needs and areas of priority. This will lead to highlighting activities that will sustainably spread and promote gender equality in the organisation through good practices.

c. Implementation plan

The activity of generating and disseminating information and data on needs requires the active participation of the Commission and the Director of Administration and Business, and the overall commitment of all units in the organisation.

The activity expects to achieve sustainable awareness in the organisation and maintain a gender equality policy in the work environment, in line with the national and European framework.

This activity includes the following stages:

4.1 Identification of responsible organisers for the implementation of the activity

4.2 Identify suitable methods to collect and analyse data: interviews, surveys, focus groups; for a higher degree of trust in the institution, some of these mechanisms will be tailored to the necessary anonymity. Determining information parameters for conducting interviews and developing surveys (questionnaires) in accordance with academic ethics and the institution's relations with external organisations and policies; Coordination of the proposals for information parameters with the academic leadership, human resources and the lawyer of the organisation

4.3 Developing data collection tools (i.e. interview/focus group guide, questionnaires etc.)

4.4 Recruitment procedure: Inform the units of the organisation about the existence of a gender focus in the institutional vision, the need to generate and analyse information.

4.5 Conduct the data collection procedures (e.g. to determine views, preferences and viewpoints of awareness of gender equality in the units of the institution, focus groups will be formed, which will support the development of ideas, priorities and opportunities for sharing and developing specific proposals.

4.6 Analysis of the information generated and identifying areas of priority to focus on in the updated 4I-GEP

The main indicators that will report on the successful progress of the activity will be:

- percentage of faculty, students, and staff who would participate in interviews, surveys, focus groups, and open discussions for awareness and analysis of gender equality at the institution
- the level of awareness of gender equality among academic staff;
- degree of awareness of gender equality on the part of students;
- degree of awareness of gender equality on the part of administrative staff;
- increase in the number of initiatives related to GEP compared to the original statistics
- improving the level of awareness of European policies on gender equality and gender-based violence among faculty, students, and staff.

In order to achieve the aims and outcomes of this activity, both internal resources - academics with expertise in the subject, literature and internet resources - and external expertise - specialists from government institutions with lead responsibility for the development of government equality policy and colleagues from other academic institutions who have better experience of developing equality measures - will be used.

The information will be visibly reported on in assessing the quality of the National Sports Academy's work.

d. Stakeholders involved

Institutionally, besides the project team, the following will be interested in this activity and will be actively involved in its implementation: the governing bodies of the administration - Director of

Administrative and Business Affairs, Academic Council, Student Council, Deans and Heads of Departments. In the communication of the National Sports Academy outside the institution, the main state bodies will be addressed - Ministry of Labour and Social Policy, Ministry of Education and Science, National Statistical Institute.

There will be different levels of stakeholder involvement and support:

- level of assistance in conducting surveys
- a level of assistance in organising focus groups for discussions
- level of cooperation with other academic institutions
- level of peer collaboration in projects

e. Potential obstacles

There are some obstacles that need to be anticipated, and a response planned to avoid halting the implementation process and achieving sustainability:

- Overcoming ingrained stereotypes and conviction of academic staff, administration and students that there is no need for needs analysis surveys and a gender database.

Measure: start with information materials and discussions on the topic

- Reluctance to participate openly in research through interviews and surveys

Measure: ensuring anonymity of respondents

- Lack of a systematic approach to address interrelated sub-activities

Measure: coordinated timetable for launching activities

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
4.1 Identification of organisers	Project team	Allocation of responsibilities	Human resources	September 2024
4.2 Identifying data collection and analysis methods	Project team Academic Ethics Commission	Methodological plan (actions and content defined) Timetable of events	Human resources Consultation time with experts	September 2024
4.3 Developing data collection tools	Project team Academic Ethics Commission	Interview guide and/or Questionnaire	Human resources Consultation time with experts	October – November 2024
4.4 Recruitment procedures	Project team HR Student Union	List of recruitment criteria Number of prospective respondents reached	Human resources Communication tools	December 2024

		Recruitment methods/tools employed		
4.5 Data collection	Project team AEC Student Council External experts	Number of respondents/participants Number of interviews Feedback from personal meetings and focus groups	Human resources	January – February 2025
4.6 Data analysis and setting priorities	Project team AEC	Report on findings	Human resources	March 2025

GA5 – Creating a gender equality database

Based on the results of the previous GA, this action creates a database to make the gender audit and gender related information publicly available and easily accessible to all units in the institutional structure.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring

b. Objectives

The aim of this action is to create and maintain a database of all the gender-related information in the NSA in order to construe a comprehensive image of the national and organisational regulatory framework, to consolidate understanding of the internal relevant structures, procedures and competent bodies and to draw attention on existing gender inequalities and the developed strategies to overcome them.

c. Implementation plan

5.1 Setting up a working team and allocating creative, operational, and content-related tasks on the gender database

5.2 Defining the purpose, content, and format of the database.

5.3 Compiling and reviewing existing sex-disaggregated data, relevant national legal and policy documents, and the organisation's strategic and operational documents.

5.4 Designing the database, adding content and dissemination for information on gender and equality at the institutional level.

d. Stakeholders involved

Project team members, AEC, Communications Department, Management, Students, Administrative Staff

e. Potential obstacles

- Internal resistances to acknowledge the need for such a database or the importance to increase transparency on the gender equality issues
- Lack of financial resources
- Lack of appropriate technological equipment/expertise to create or maintain the database

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
5.1 Setting up a working team	Project team AEC Communications team University Legal Adviser	Allocation of responsibilities	Human resources	January 2025
5.2 Defining the database's purpose/content/format	Working team Management	Plan for the database	Human resources	January 2025
5.3 Compiling and reviewing existing data	Project team AEC	Compiled national laws and internal regulations	Human resources Consultation time with experts	February – March 2025
5.4 Designing the database, adding content and dissemination	HR Working team members	Results included in the Annual report of the university. The Report is transparent and accessible to everyone.	Human resources Communication tools	March – May 2025

GA6 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

This GA develops and implements awareness-raising activities on GBV and sexual harassment in sport environment and promote existing achievements from university level, but also at local level by raising awareness of external stakeholders.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- To increase understanding both of internal and of external stakeholders on the concept and forms of gender-based violence (physical, sexual, psychological, economic and financial, sexual harassment, online) in the sports context
- To create a safe environment and a culture of respect, equality and zero tolerance towards gender-based violence
- To introduce staff and students to the relevant regulatory framework and internal procedures in place (reporting and case management, support mechanisms) in a simple and comprehensive manner

c. Implementation plan

The following activities will be carried out to implement this Grounding Action:

6.1 Set up the working team (incl. students and/or staff, and a communication team to engage external stakeholders effectively)

6.2 Develop a comprehensive scheme (Define objectives and message, target audience, timeframe and budget, outline the campaign's activities and desired outcome)

6.3 Design the material for the planned activities, approval and launch of the activity (define appropriate channels, create the visuals, prepare the presentations)

It will also include a local stakeholder event (e.g. in the form of an awareness day) to raise awareness of targeted external stakeholders such as sports clubs, trainers, associations, umbrella organisations, public authorities.

6.4 Evaluate the scheme's impact and explore possibility for future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Project team, Academic Ethics Commission, Student Union, Management, PR/Communications team. In the communication of the National Sports Academy outside the institution, some national sports federations will be involved, the Bulgarian Olympic Committee, the governmental bodies responsible for the GEP implementation, Labour Unions from the sectors of Sports and Higher education.

e. Potential obstacles

- Lack of interest/time of targeted stakeholders
- Lack of adequate resources (human resources, expertise, financial resources to engage external expertise)

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
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6.1 Setting up the working team	Project team Communications team Students/Staff representatives	List of team members defined	Human resources	October 2024
6.2 Development of comprehensive scheme	Working team	Document of the scheme, with time plan of activities and budget	Human resources	October 2024
6.3 Design the material, approval and launch of the activity	Working team External experts	Complete material of the campaign	Software and communication tools Human resources	November, 2024 – May 2025
6.4 Evaluate the impact and explore possibility for future relaunch	Working team External experts	Increased knowledge of students, staff and external stakeholders on GBV and SH in sport environment, as well as on procedures and steps to follow in cases of GBV and SH Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms	Human resources	May – June 2025

GA7 – Use of Inclusive Language in Institutional Documents

This action is geared towards promoting inclusivity by revising documents, including academic policies, handbooks, and communication materials, to ensure that language is inclusive and embraces diversity. This promotes a sense of belonging for individuals of both genders within the sports university community.

- Development and supplementation of the existing regulations in the NSA, creation of new commissions and the appointment of responsible persons.
- Development of the existing lecture courses in NSA such as Sociology of Sport and Philosophy of Sport, Psychology of Sports etc. with new topics such as: Violence, Gender and Sport. Gender stereotypes, sports, etc. Increasing the hours in these disciplines.

a. GEP element

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture

b. Objectives

The aim of document revision and the application of inclusive and tolerant language is to foster a more inclusive and respectful academic environment within the sports academy.

The revision process aims to identify and rectify unintentional biases present in language that may perpetuate stereotypes or reinforce gender norms. It seeks to create a more neutral and equitable representation of individuals, irrespective of their identity, thus preventing unintended bias. Inclusive language fosters an atmosphere of tolerance by acknowledging and respecting the diversity, contributing to a campus culture that values and celebrates individual differences, thereby encouraging tolerance. Through document revision, the NSA will set a positive example for students, faculty, and staff, fostering a more inclusive and tolerant academic community. Ensuring that institutional documents adhere to inclusive language principles aligns with broader national policies on diversity and inclusion, helping the NSA to meet or exceed regulatory and accreditation standards related to gender equality, and ensuring compliance with official policies.

c. Implementation plan

7.1 Collect and identify institutional documents and policies which are going to be reviewed

7.2 Review and Update of Documentation - Review and update existing institutional documents and policies to ensure they align with gender equality principles. Institutionalisation of gender equality as a guiding principle of the university's mission and strategy.

7.3 Develop guidelines on inclusive language use that respects diverse identities in relation to the Bulgarian national policy and the gender equality principles.

7.4 Encourage the use of inclusive language in all university communications, documentation, and official forms.

d. Stakeholders involved

A large number of representatives within the university administrative and academic structures will be involved in these GA – Besides the entire rector's board, the main project team and the GE commission, the legal advisor, the HR director and the PR will be involved.

e. Potential obstacles

- Internal resistances
- Lack of time for document review
- Lack of expertise on inclusive language

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
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7.1 Collect documents for review	Project team HR	List of documents for review and update	Human resources	October – November 2024
7.2 Review and update of documentation	Project team Academic Ethics Commission Legal advisor	Revised documents and summary of updates	Human resources	December 2024 – February 2025
7.3 Develop guidelines for inclusive language use	Project team AEC HR	Document of guidelines	Human resources	October – December 2024
7.4 Encourage inclusive language use	Project team AEC PR/Communications department	Number of internal and external stakeholders reached via email, social media posts/reactions, website visits	Human resources	March – May 2025

GA8 – Integrating Gender in the Curriculum

Teaching: Conducting exercises and lectures with 1st and 4th year students at the National Academy of Sports in the Philosophy of Sports and Sociology of Sports classes based on the results of the project.

a. GEP element

Thematic: Integration of gender dimension in the research and teaching content

b. Objectives

The objective of integrating gender equality into teaching is to cultivate a more inclusive and fair academic landscape. This involves infusing the ethos of gender equality into educational curricula across diverse disciplines. The purpose is to:

- **Elevate Awareness:** Heighten awareness among students, faculty, and researchers regarding the crucial significance of gender equality, diversity, and inclusion within their specific areas of study.
- **Challenge Assumptions:** Confront and dismantle gender stereotypes and biases embedded in academic content, ensuring that teaching materials and research methodologies are devoid of discriminatory elements.

- **Cultivate Inclusive Learning:** Establish a learning environment that is not only inclusive but also supportive of all genders, offering equal opportunities for academic success, irrespective of gender identity.
- **Shape Future Advocates:** Equip students with the knowledge and skills needed to become advocates for gender equality in their future careers, whether within academia or other professional realms.
- **Exemplify Role Models:** Highlight and celebrate accomplishments of individuals from all genders in academia, serving as inspirations and challenging stereotypes surrounding gender and academic achievement.
- **Advocate for Inclusive Policies:** Champion and implement policies that uphold gender equality within academic institutions, fostering an environment that acknowledges and celebrates diversity and inclusion.

Through the integration of gender equality into teaching, the National Sports Academy will contribute to the creation of a more equitable society, preparing students to be informed, conscious, and proactive contributors to a world of sport that values individuals and respects their human rights for access to sport.

This GA will be linked to the three important strategic points of the NSA – quality of education, internationalisation and excellence in research.

c. Implementation plan

8.1 Review the curriculum and identify gender-related topics in existing modules and gaps

8.2 Define sports-specific contents that address gender-related issues, including historical inequalities, opportunities, and challenges in each sport. Each sport module should entail reference to gender equality and persistent stereotypes.

8.3 Incorporate case studies that highlight the achievements and challenges faced by athletes of both genders in various sports. Showcase examples of successful female athletes and their impact on the sports landscape. These examples would be with a strong emphasis on those sports which are considered “male” sports. Showcase examples of successful male coaches in traditional “female” sports.

Although traditionally, our curriculum is tailored to the specific nature of each sport taught in our Academy; we must ensure that our students will gain a deeper understanding of the gender dynamics within their chosen discipline and contribute to fostering a more inclusive sports culture.

8.4 Finalise the new curriculum and submit for approval

8.5 Communicate the integration of the gender dimension in academic teaching.

d. Stakeholders involved

A large number of representatives within the university community will be involved in these GA – The education supervisors and module teachers in each department, the directors of the different centres in NSA, the Deans, The rector's board, and in particular, the Vice-rector for Education and the Vice-rector for Research. The steering will be the project team and the AC commission. The key role in the promotion of research topics will be the Directors of the different master's programs.

e. Potential obstacles

As modernisation of teaching and encouraging research are among the milestones of NSA, no obstacles are foreseen for these GA, besides lack of staff time.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
8.1 Review of curriculum	Project team AEC Vice rector for education	Report on existing relevant topics and suggestions	Human resources	January 2025
8.2 Discuss and define new topics/methods	Project team AEC Module teachers External experts	Updated topics/methods	Human resources External expertise	February – March 2025
8.3 Incorporate case studies	Project team AEC Module teachers External expertise	Summary of case studies	Human resources External expertise	March – April 2025
8.4 Finalise and seek approval	Project team AEC Vice Rector for education	Updated curriculum approved	Human resources	May 2025
8.5 Dissemination and communication of new curriculum	Project team AEC PR/Communications team	Number of internal and external stakeholders reached	Human resources Communication tools	June 2025

Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: to secure formal institutional commitment to the 4I-GEP through a structured approval process and ensure the lasting effect of the roadmap's achievements.

Implementation plan

Starting point: The National Sports Academy had a formally adopted Rules for gender equality in carrying out research activities (05.09.2022) before the start of the SUPPORTER project

implementation. The strategy covered a range of areas that mainly concerned gender-balanced academic ethics. The implementation of the current SUPPORTER project has significantly broadened the view of the academic, administrative staff and the student community on women's rights to equality, the areas in which these rights may be affected, as well as the procedures through which to act in clearly defined cases. A need was identified to revise the existing strategy to expand its scope, as well as to explicitly involve the so-called 4I - aspects of all provided measures (inclusive, innovative, impactful, intersectional). The National Sports Academy strategic rules were adopted as one of the policies of the Rector's Council. The Rector's Council in the presence of all management representatives approved and adopted the rules as a legally binding document. Amendments to the strategic rules will have to go through the same validation process to have the same value.

Steps to obtain a formal approval of the new GEP:

The following stakeholders will participate in the development and adoption of the new document:

- Members of the SUPPORTER team;
- Legal adviser of the National Sports Academy;
- Consultative group at the vice rector for science and international relations;
- Faculties' leaderships
- Members of the Academic Ethics Commission;
- Vice-rectors at the National Sports Academy;
- Chairman of the General Meeting;
- Rector of the National Sports Academy.

The action of revising and adopting the new GEP will take 5 (five) months starting on 01 February 2025 by completing the following tasks:

1. Reviewing the current text and identifying the additions that need to be made in view of 4I aspects – deadline 30 March 2025
2. Drafting the amendments and consolidation of the text – deadline 30 April 2025
3. Consultations with the expert groups and leading managers – 20 May 2025
4. Making available and sending copies to the members of the Rector's office – deadline 30 May 2025
5. Submission for the procedural discussions and approval to the Rector's office and inclusion in the schedule for adoption of internal documents – deadline 30 June 2025

Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Possible emergence of an unforeseen need for explanations in written and oral form of the nature of 4I and the need to take them into account 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Preparation of explanatory text to be attached to each request for coordination
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Refusal of some management bodies to take a sphere of new responsibilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Talking about tools that could facilitate and optimize assigned responsibilities
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Resistance to change stemming from procedures having the risk of becoming burdening (coordination procedures, for instance) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Effective communication, demonstrating the benefits of the new approach, and involving key stakeholders in the decision-making process

Timeline

Activity (Step)	Involved stakeholders	Required resources	Timeline
1.Reviewing the current text and identifying the additions that need to be made in view of 41 aspects	Team members Legal adviser	<i>Human resources</i>	01.02.2025 - 30.03.2025
2.Drafting the amendments and consolidation of the text	Team members Legal adviser	<i>Human resources</i>	01.04.2025 - 30.04.2025
3.Consultations with the expert groups and leading managers	Consultative group at the vice rector for science and international relations; Faculties' leaderships; Members of the Academic Ethics Commission;	<i>Human resources</i>	01.05.2025 – 20 May 2025
4.Making available and sending copies to the members of the Rector's office	Vice-rectors at the National Sports Academy; Chairman of the General Meeting; Members of the SUPPORTER team.	<i>Human resources</i>	20 May 2025 - 30 May 2025
5.Submission for the procedural discussions and approval to the Rector's office and inclusion in the schedule for adoption of internal documents	Faculties' leaderships Vice-rectors at the National Sports Academy; Chairman of the General Meeting; Rector of the National Sports Academy.	<i>Human resources</i>	01 June 2025 - 30 June 2025

5. Lithuanian Sports University (LSU)

Summary of changes

GA1 - Social Campaign raising public awareness on choosing a sport based on individual desire rather than stereotypes.

In point GA1, the dates for the implementation of the activities were delayed, because in November and December 2024, together with the Communication and Marketing Department, we were very busy with the organization of two international events: the Sports Forum and the International Conference. As a result, there was no time to prepare for the activities planned in the campaign and to complete them on time.

GA2 - To improve and conduct a regular survey to assess the effectiveness of initiatives in reducing gender-based violence and promoting a safe and respectful environment.

We have included questions about negative experiences related to age, religious beliefs and disability as intersectional dimensions in the data collected on university staff and students. This adjustment was inspired by the tasks carried out during the Thessaloniki Peer Learning Workshop of the project. These new variables will increase the inclusiveness of our data analysis and allow for a clearer and more comprehensive understanding of the situation at our institution.

GA3 - Introduce innovative teaching methods and materials that challenge gender stereotypes, gender-based violence and promote diverse role models in sports.

When planning to supplement the module with the planned topics and methods, the student survey data was planned to be received by June 2024, but student activity was low, so the survey deadline was extended to December. Also, taking into account the inclusion of another additional topic on gender equality and disabled sports issues, the deadline for updating the module (program and materials) was extended to January. This topic was encouraged after discussion in 6th MLW. Workshop/panel discussion date adjusted to February 2025 because students start studying after the exam session.

GA4 - Encourage research initiatives that explore the intersection of gender and sports

We had planned to submit thesis topics to students in February 2025, the Department of Studies set separate dates for masters and bachelors. Masters had to submit topics already in December 2024, and bachelors had to submit topics in March 2025. Therefore, the dates have been extended for both topic submission and topic selection.

GA5 - Training and capacity-building on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment for internal and external stakeholders

In GA5 point (Inviting external lecturers who are experts in different (presented) topics) was added another date for inviting external lecturers, as it was very difficult to coordinate dates with lecturers for training in advance (dates and lecturers had to be changed several times). After the November lecture was scheduled with Dr. Margarita Jankauskaitė, (Center for Equality advancement), that in January we will plan separate trainings for students; there are also negotiations for a seminar with other lecturers on the topic of multiculturalism and discrimination, but they also asked for more time for negotiations.

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
GA1	Timeline	Shift in focus to another international events.

		High employment of colleagues (Communication and Marketing Department) due to other LSU activities.
GA2	To include intersectional aspects, the questions were approved at the Psychological Well-being Committee on November 21 and included in the questionnaire in December.	Inspired by training
GA3	Change of date for student's report; for adjusting the module with new topics and methods and for workshop/panel discussion for students.	Inspired by training in 6th MLW. Implementers need more time to prepare and implement activities
GA4	Change of date for submitting and choosing thesis topics to student	New dates from the Department of Studies.
GA5	Timeline; Negotiations with new external lectures	Difficulties to coordinate dates with lecturers

Grounding Actions

A set of five Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5
<i>Intersectional</i>		x			x
<i>Innovative</i>			x	x	
<i>Inclusive</i>	x				
<i>Impactful</i>		x		x	
<i>Tailored to sports</i>	x			x	x

GA1 – Social Campaign raising public awareness on choosing a sport based on individual desire rather than stereotypes

A Social Campaign with a variety of activities will be organised to encourage participation and leadership in sport-related activities for all genders and raise public awareness of choosing a sport based on individual desire rather than stereotypes.

This activity is intended to organise and carry out a Social Campaign about stereotypes in sports (gender, coaches, refereeing in competitions, leadership, media). For example, sports that demonstrate strength and power, such as football and basketball, combat sports are seen as expressions of masculinity, while aesthetic sports, such as dance, are feminised.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

b. Objectives

A Social Campaign about gender stereotypes in different sports can serve several purposes:

- a) **Raise Awareness:** The campaign seeks to bring attention to the pervasive gender stereotypes that exist within various sports, for example, combat sports only for men or gymnastic - only for girls; The campaign can educate the public about the issues.
- b) **Challenge Stereotypes:** This involves questioning preconceived notions about what is considered "appropriate" or "expected" for individuals of different genders in the context of sports.
- c) **The Campaign can invite to empower women and challenge that certain sports are more suitable for men or that women are less capable in certain athletic pursuits these stereotypes by showcasing their achievements and abilities in various sports; Encourage male involvement:** The campaign may encourage male involvement in a broader range of sports, promoting the idea that interests and talents are not limited by gender.
- d) **Shift Cultural Perceptions:** It promotes the idea that everyone, regardless of gender, should have the freedom to participate in sports without facing judgement or limitations.
- e) **Diversity:** By showcasing a variety of role models, the campaign helps break down stereotypes and encourage a more inclusive sports culture.
- f) **Ultimately, a Social Campaign about gender stereotypes in sports strives to create a more equitable and inclusive sporting environment.**

c. Implementation plan

What types of activities are designed to implement this GA?

The Social Campaign will encompass interviews with success stories, short videos and dissemination activities. The campaign's objectives, target audience, timeframe, required tools/budget and audience will be developed in detail. The interviews will be carried out and the material will be thoroughly devised, along with a dissemination plan. The campaign will then be launched and monitored to assess its impact.

What will be achieved with these?

To bring attention to the pervasive gender stereotypes that exist within various sports and question them; raise awareness that everyone, regardless of gender, should have the freedom to participate in sports without facing judgement or limitations in this way promoting inclusivity.

Are these envisaged as parallel actions or sequential?

This is parallel activity in the implementation of other project objectives.

What measurable indicators will be used to assess the successful implementation of these activities?

- Engagement of the sports community (for example famous professional athletes, sports influencers) (3 professional athletes, 1 referee, 1 leader, 1 sport journalist)
- Reach of the general society (How many views were there on social networks)
- Any changes in attitudes (for example, open discussion in social portals: FB, Instagram: How many "like", comments)

What resources will be needed and how will they be obtained?

It is planned to cooperate with the University's Communication and Marketing Department to prepare and conduct high-quality interviews with professional athletes. Payment to the University's marketing staff for interview-appropriate video editing and dissemination.

The implementing team: specialists from the Communication and Marketing Department (two people). Information Technology Department (one person), Students Union; Project managers (three persons);

The success criteria:

- Preparing interviews with success stories of professional athletes (boxing, moto sport, free fights, break), who are genuinely committed to challenging gender stereotypes in sports.
- Developing Campaign Materials: Creating compelling visuals, videos, and written content to support our campaign (These materials should effectively convey our message and evoke emotional responses).
- Developing a visually appealing and memorable slogan for our campaign; utilising the Multiple Communication Channels: social media, traditional media, websites, and sports community events to reach different segments of our target audience.
- Engaging Influencers and Ambassadors (Professional athletes);
- Integrating of educational components into our campaign (different resources, and educational materials that help inform the public about gender stereotypes in sports and why they need to be challenged);
- Measuring of engagement, reach, and any changes in attitudes or behaviours related to gender stereotypes in sports.

The resources required for its effective implementation. Human resources for creating interviews, specialists capable of high-quality filming and editing of narrated success stories (interview) and their payment (Communication and Marketing Department).

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, Communication and Marketing Department, Information Technology Department, University students: professional athletes – Ambassadors

Only consulting: University Students' Union, external stakeholders

Only informing: External stakeholders: local, regional and country sport communities (Sport Federations; Sport journalists; Sports clubs, Municipal sports centres, National Olympic Committee)

e. Potential obstacles

- Funding obstacles. Lack of funding can make difficulties to high-quality filming and editing of narrated success stories
- Ambassadors may avoid telling their stories publicly for fear of different comments

Possibilities to prevent or timely address such obstacles:

- To calculate a realistic budget before acting (reduce the number of ambassadors)
- Establish trust and communication with Ambassadors (emphasise the positive impact their stories can have on challenging stereotypes, creating safe and confidential spaces for interview, assuring their' s stories will be treated with respect and sensitivity, providing options for ambassadors to share their stories anonymously)
- Implement moderation measures on social media platforms and other communication channels where the stories will be shared. This involves actively monitoring comments and removing any that are disrespectful or harmful. Clearly communicate the zero-tolerance policy for inappropriate behaviour.
- Publicly acknowledge Ambassadors efforts, share success stories, and highlight the positive impact their stories have had.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Set up a team for the campaign	Project team Communication and Marketing Department Student representatives	List of team members	Human resources	January 2025
Define campaign objectives, content, timeframe, budget	Project team Communication and Marketing Department	Outline of the campaign	Human resources	January 2025

	Students			
Creating Campaign Design	Project team Communication and Marketing Department Students Union	Developing a visually appealing and memorable slogan for our campaign	Human resources for creating design of campaign	January 2025
Preparing interviews with success stories (4-5) of professional athletes (for example, boxing, moto sport, free fights, break dance; Basketball and/or football referees (persons from outside); leaders from sport federations.	Communication and Marketing Department Students' Union	Search for Ambassadors who agree to share their success stories	Human resources for creating of interview Financial resources	February-March 2025
Developing the campaign materials	Project team Information Technology Department Communication and Marketing Department	Processing and finalising the campaign material (posts, videos)	Specialists capable of high-quality filming and editing of success stories (interview) Financial resources	April 2025
Launch of Campaign (Dissemination of Campaign Materials)	Information Technology Department Communication and Marketing Department	Processing and publishing convincing, informative and attractive success stories on the YouTube channel	Human resources Financial resources	April 2025
Campaign monitoring	Communication and Marketing Department	Measuring of engagement reach Measuring changes in attitudes related to gender stereotypes in sports (open discussion in social portals: FB, Instagram: How	Human resources for monitoring	May-June 2025

		many comments)	"like",		
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GA2 – To improve and conduct a regular survey to assess the effectiveness of initiatives in reducing gender-based violence and promoting a safe and respectful environment.

This activity is intended for the improvement of the survey aimed at assessing the effectiveness of initiatives in reducing gender-based violence and promoting a safe and respectful environment. The survey will be supplemented with relevant questions. It will help the university to better understand the psychological well-being of students and staff, especially considering issues of gender equality and gender-based violence. The survey will be supplemented with relevant questions.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

Each year, the University's Psychological Wellbeing Committee conducts a psychosocial risk factors and psychological well-being monitoring survey for university staff and students (separately) (form link for staff - <https://forms.gle/sKHkLo9kkVxWKHqj9> ; form link for students - <https://forms.gle/qwS1KuLAX85XkYkS7>). The current questionnaire contains questions related to emotional well-being, emotional support, opportunities for solving psychological problems at university, availability of psychological/emotional support, social capital, etc. The problem is that the current questionnaire contains only one question related to gender equality and gender-based violence - "Do you experience unpleasant situations or comments related to gender at university?". The data of the last survey showed that 4% of students and 11% of employees answered this question positively, but we do not have more detailed data. In addition, the university psychologist defined that during counseling students talk about this and this shows that the problem exists. Therefore, supplementing the questionnaire with detailed questions about this problem will allow to see not only the extent of the problem, but also the origins and causes of the problem, and whether individuals know where to turn for help, whether they are receiving appropriate help, etc. In this way, the full picture of the problem will be revealed. After obtaining a detailed picture of the problem, it will be decided how to improve the existing system of psycho-emotional support of the university and what community awareness measures to apply (e.g. training etc.). Beneficiaries will be the university community.

Purposes:

- Prepare specific questions related to gender equality, including experiences and perceptions of gender discrimination and equal opportunities in the university, and questions about gender-based violence, including experiences and reactions to harassment, sexual violence and other forms of violence.
- Adjust and improve the questionnaire based on the results of the pilot study.

- Organize the implementation of the questionnaire throughout the university.
- Analyze the data collected, identifying key issues and trends related to psychological well-being, gender equality and gender-based violence.
- Prepare a report on the research findings, including key findings and insights.
- Provide recommendations to the university on how to improve psychological well-being, strengthen gender equality and reduce cases of gender-based violence.

c. Implementation plan

Filling out the questionnaire will be in the following steps:

- the psychological well-being committee (with stakeholders) will develop questions related to the topics of gender equality and gender-based violence. They will be added to the existing questionnaire.
- A pilot study will be conducted.
- The results of the pilot study will be analysed
- Inappropriate questions are deleted and/or corrected
- A survey of university employees and students will be conducted
- Survey results will be analysed and presented to the university community
- Recommendations will be provided to the university on how to improve psychological well-being, strengthen gender equality and reduce cases of gender-based violence

The survey will be conducted by the Psychological Wellbeing Committee (PWC). PWC has conducted research on psychological well-being and related factors, but one question in the questionnaire is related to gender-based violence: "Do you experience unpleasant situations or comments related to gender at university?" and one question related to the availability of psychological support: "How do you rate the availability of psychological/emotional support (in terms of time, place and financial resources) and Do you experience unpleasant situations or comments related to gender at university?"

During the development of the questionnaire, it is intended to add 8-11 questions related to gender equality, gender-based violence and negative experiences related to age, religion, beliefs, disability and how effective the harassment and violence prevention policies and procedures are at the university.

The survey will be carried out through electronic mail of university students and employees. Criteria (measurable indicators) to evaluate the successful implementation of these activities will be:

Level of participation:

How many people, especially from different gender groups, participated in the survey? A successful survey should cover various gender groups and ensure representativeness. It is planned that there should be a similar number of different gender groups (e.g. 50% men and women each).

Level of answers:

How many people completed the questionnaire completely? This may indicate the willingness of respondents to participate and provide accurate data.

Level of detail:

Did respondents answer more detailed questions in the same way as shorter ones? Detailed answers can provide a deeper understanding of the situation.

Security assurance:

Have adequate security measures been implemented, particularly with regard to sensitive issues such as the protection of victims of violence?

Use of reports: Are the results useful and used to make decisions that can improve gender equality or reduce violence?

It is stipulated in the provisions of the PWC that the survey must be carried out at least once a year.

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, Psychological Well-being Committee. For creating questions, help will be sought from the Lithuanian Office of the Equal Opportunities Ombudsperson (external stakeholders).

Only consulting: Internal resources will also be used: Ethics Commission, Human Resources Management Department, Research Methodology professors (internal stakeholders). Communication and Marketing Department and Student Union for recruiting participants.

Only informing: Upper management

e. Potential obstacles

Possible obstacles (after a pilot study):

- Too few or too many questions
- Few respondents
- Respondents will not want or are afraid to answer "sensitive" questions.

Measures to remove obstacles to improve the survey process and obtain quality data:

- Consult with experts and adjust the questions so that they are formulated clearly and neutrally, in order to reduce the fear of answering; that the questionnaire is of optimal length and does not contain overly complex or redundant questions
- Ensure that the recruitment process is as widely publicised as possible and reaches different gender, age, ethnic origin and other social groups using different communication tools (email, group tutor and Students Union (for students)).

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Creating questions survey	Project team Psychological Well-being Committee External consultants	An improved questionnaire covering issues of gender equality and gender-based violence.	Time for meetings with stakeholders Time to edit the questionnaire	November – December 2024
Pilot study	Psychological Well-being Committee	~15-20% of students	E-mail Students' tutors Student Union	February – March 2025

		~20% of university staff who filled out the questionnaire		
Analysis of the pilot study	Project team Psychological Well-being Committee	Identifying weak and points successfully eliminating them Report with analysis results	Time for analysis	March - April 2025
Conduct a survey of university employees and students	Project team Psychological Well-being Committee	15-30% of respondents (in students and staff groups) who filled out the questionnaire	Time for meetings with stakeholders Time to edit the questionnaire E-mail	May 2025
Analyse survey results and present them to the university community	Project team Psychological Well-being Committee	20-30% of community members will participate in the presentation of the results	Time for preparing presentation Time for presentation	June 2025
Prepare and provide recommendations	Project team Psychological Well-being Committee	Recommendations are given to the responsible university committees	Time for preparing recommendations	July – September 2025

GA3 – Introduce innovative teaching methods and materials that challenge gender stereotypes, gender-based violence and promote diverse role models in sports.

This Grounding Action develops and implements a series of awareness-raising activities on gender+ equality in the sports environment at institutional level.

The university offers an optional module "Sports against violence and exclusion" that can be chosen by students of various programs. The topics of this module are mainly related to bullying and violence in sports activities, hostile behaviour among athletes, etc. Therefore, it is intended to include topics and innovative approaches related to gender stereotypes, gender equality and gender-based violence.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content

b. Objectives

- To promote a uniform understanding on the concept of gender+ equality, with a focus in the sports context and in higher education.
- The aim of the module development is to broaden students' knowledge of gender stereotypes in sport, as well as issues related to gender-based violence, including sexual harassment. This is fully compatible with the strategic action plan, which includes educational measures, increasing awareness of the issues of gender equality, gender stereotypes, gender-based violence and methods to overcome them.

c. Implementation plan

Include the following topics in the module:

- **Gender stereotypes related to sports.** By providing various examples of inappropriate behaviour found in sports and discussing the reasons for this.
- **The principle of equal opportunities.** Emphasising that all athletes have equal opportunities to participate in any sport and any level of sports events, regardless of gender.
- **Gender-based violence, including sexual harassment in sports.**

Include innovative methods in the module:

- **Use various examples of sports.** Students could present the stories of different athletes, regardless of their gender.
- **Use technology, thereby encouraging students to engage in active learning processes.** It is possible to create interactive training programs that reflect various sports activities. Encourage students to create their own recordings, videos or projects that highlight diversity and equality in sport.
- **Include case studies.** For example, invite coaches to share their experiences of how they have promoted diversity and equity in their training.
- **Discussion and reflection.** Organise group discussions about gender stereotypes in sports and how they can be overcome. To encourage students to reflect on their experiences in sports and how they can contribute to the promotion of equal opportunities. Criteria for evaluating the successful implementation of this activity - how many students will choose this module.

Workshop/panel discussion for students regarding awareness-raising activities on gender+ equality in the sports environment.

- Design the material (define appropriate channels, create the visuals)
- Impact evaluation

Resources:

Internal - the teacher's time (for supplementing the module with topics, innovative methods and preparation for workshop/panel discussion) and psychological costs (considering the application of innovative methods, formulating tasks, predicting settlements, etc.) and financial (paying guest lecturers).

External - guest coaches gender experts.

Implementing persons: lecturers of the module and students who will choose this module.

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, Module teachers (they will be responsible for workshop/panel discussion also). For implementing innovative methods in the module, working coaches from sports centres will be invited and gender experts (external stakeholders).

Only consulting: For supplementing the module lecturers (internal stakeholders) will be included.

Only informing: Upper management.

e. Potential obstacles

Anticipated obstacles to the implementation of this GA:

- Financial obstacles. Lack of funding can make it difficult to implement innovative teaching methods and create interesting and engaging teaching materials.
- Students will not choose a module.
 - Small number of students in workshop/panel discussion.

To prevent these obstacles:

- Since there are lecturers-practitioners at the university, we will try to invite them as guests of honour.
- Promote this module and workshop/panel discussion through university information channels and University students Union.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Discuss among the module teachers the topics and methods to be included in the module	Project team Module teachers	Choice of topics and methods	Time	May 2024
Survey towards previous students to gather their views on whether and how the module would benefit from a gendered perspective	Module coordinator	20-40 percent of students who responded	Time for creating questions Time for survey and analysis of results E-system	June – December 2024
Adjusting the module with new topics and methods	Module teachers	Updated module and (syllabus material)	Time E-system	January 2025
Workshop/panel discussion for students regarding awareness-raising activities on gender+ equality in the sports environment	Project team Module teachers	Clarity and understanding Inclusivity Feedback from participants	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources	February 2025

		No. 10-20 of participants		
Teaching the module	Teachers Students Guest coaches Gender experts	60-80% attendance of student seminars and lectures	E-system Teachers Classrooms Computers	February – June 2025
Student survey about the module (feedback) and assessing the new syllabus	Module coordinator Module teachers	Positive feedback from ~15-20 students about the module Improved understanding of students (by compared previous and current feedback from students)	E-system Time for analysis of survey results Time for assessing the new syllabus	June 2025

GA4 – Encourage research initiatives that explore the intersection of gender and sports

Under this activity, teachers will introduce students to topics related to gender equality and gender-based violence in sports. At the same time, encourage students to choose these topics for their final theses, delve into this topic, conduct research and based on it, make proposals for solving these problems.

a. GEP element

Thematic: Integration of the gender dimension into research and teaching content

b. Objectives

The goal is to encourage students (bachelor, masters) to conduct more, broader and more detailed research related to gender equality in sports and gender-based violence in sports.

Currently, the university offers few thesis topics (both at bachelor and master's level) to students related to gender differences in sports, gender-based violence in sports, etc. Therefore, this activity will aim to close this gap. This is fully compatible with the strategic action plan as it will broaden the field of research on gender equality and gender-based violence. The possibility of having real statistics related to these problems, detailed theoretical and empirical analyses, recommendations for sports institutions.

c. Implementation plan

The implementer of this activity is the Department of Physical and Social Education, teachers and students. Resources that will be needed - teachers' competences, databases, research methodologies.

Implementation process - the Head of the Department of Physical and Social Education will suggest competent teachers to submit an expanded list of bachelor's and master's theses topics related to the problems of gender equality and gender-based violence in sports. After analysing existing research, competent teachers will provide students with possible topics or students can suggest their own topics related to the mentioned problems. It is also possible to submit requests to external partners (sports centres, sports clubs) about research related to gender equality and gender-based violence that would be of interest to them. Encourage students to present topics relevant to them themselves.

The successful implementation of this activity will be measured through the following indicators:

- how many topics related to gender equality in sport and gender-based violence in sport were presented to students (bachelor and master).
- how many students chose these topics.
- how many students successfully defended these theses?

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, both external (sports centres, sports clubs, sports schools) and internal (Physical and Social Education Department, teachers, students) stakeholders will participate in the implementation of this activity.

Only consulting: Students

Only informing: Management

e. Potential obstacles

- **Complex topics.** Sometimes the chosen topic can be too complex or too broadly defined.
- **Lack of motivation:** If students are not motivated or do not have a clear understanding of the importance of their chosen topic, this can lead to a weak commitment to the work.

Removing these obstacles should:

- **Emphasising the relevance of the topic.** Clearly demonstrate how the material being taught is relevant to students' lives and how it can contribute to their career goals or personal development.
- **Maintaining a personal connection with teachers.** Make it easy for students to communicate with teachers, get advice, get support and share their thoughts.
- **Creativity and freedom of choice.** To give students the opportunity to choose projects, topics or assignments that are of interest to them or related to their career aspirations.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
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Analysis of topics, contact with external partners	Department of Physical and Social Education	The themes of these are highlighted	Time for analysing topics Time for meetings with stakeholders Databases	September – December 2024
Submitting topics to students (or students submitting their own topics)	Teachers Students	Five to ten topics related to gender equality and gender-based violence in sports are presented	Electronic platform of LSU	December 2024 - March 2025
Choice of topics	Students	Three to seven topics are selected	Electronic platform of LSU	December 2024- April 2025

GA5 – Training and capacity-building on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment for internal and external stakeholders

This activity is designed to carry out training programs GBV, diversity or multiple identities in sport, for university community and external partners (Sports Federations, Sports clubs, Sports schools, Municipal sports centres, National Olympic Committee).

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

The purpose of training programs on gender equality, gender-based violence, diversity, and multiple identities in sports is multifaceted:

- "Know how"- to recognise, evaluate, prevent and have different tools to solve problems regarding GEP, GBV, diversity or multiple identities in the sports community.
- To equip individuals with the tools and skills to intervene when witnessing discriminatory behaviour, harassment, or violence.
- To improve communication skills and build empathy to facilitate respectful and inclusive interactions among athletes, coaches, and staff from diverse backgrounds.
- To invite "to open mind" to address stereotypes, biases, and discriminatory attitudes related to gender, race, ethnicity, sexual orientation, ability, and other identity factors.
- Improve Organisational Culture to build a positive and inclusive organisational culture that reflects a commitment to diversity and gender equality
- To raise awareness to comply with organisational policies related to gender equality, discrimination, and harassment.

c. Implementation plan

Trainings are conducted for the university's target groups (administration, teachers, researchers, students, doctoral students) and social partners.

Training topics could be these:

- GEP, GBV, multiple identities and diversity issues in sports
- Prevention of GBV and creating a safe and supportive environment.
- Harm of stereotypes and discrimination in sports.
- Practical sessions (case study: how to react when witnessing discriminatory behaviour, harassment, or violence).

What will be achieved with these?

Practical tools “Know how” for teachers, coaches, athletes, administration.

Are these envisaged as parallel actions or sequential?

The training activities are both: sequential (one training session (six hour) per three months or four training sessions per year) and parallel (G1, G2, G3, G4).

What measurable indicators are going to be used in order to assess the successful implementation of these activities?

- Ruler method to evaluate your knowledge before and after each workshop.
- Self-test questions after each workshop or feedback quiz (closed questions) after each workshop.
- Number of participants: at least 20-30 participants in each workshop.
- Dissemination of each workshop in LSU website and social media.
- Workshops and the number of participants is recorded in the rector's annual report.

What resources will be needed and how will they be obtained?

The human resource (HR):

- For invitation external lecturers who are experts in different (provided) topics.
- Preparing workshop material (project team members).
- Dissemination of workshops (University Communication and marketing department).

Funding for external lecturers.

The implementing team within LSU will be:

- Project team members;
- Knowledge and innovation relay department.
- Communication and marketing department.

The success criteria are the following:

- Lecturers from outside who are experts in GE and GBV
- Successful dissemination of workshop to the public
- Great interest from the university community and outside and a large number of participants

d. Stakeholders involved

Together with the project team will be involved:

Internal stakeholders:

Co-producing: Ethics Commission, Psychological Welfare Committee, Student Union

Only consulting: Department of knowledge and innovation relay

Only informing: Vice Rector of studies

External stakeholders:

Only consulting: Office of the Equal opportunities, National Olympic Committee, Sports Federations

Only informing: National Sports Agency, local and country Sports Clubs, Municipal Sports Centres, Sports Gymnasiums

e. Potential obstacles

Lack of interest of the target group members (regarding the stereotypes point of view about GE and GBV).

Possible solution: successful introducing and dissemination of social Campaign to gather a suitable number of participants for workshops

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
Development of the training scheme (objectives, timeline, target audience, budget)	Project team	Outline of the training scheme	Human resources	April – May 2024
Preparing workshop material	Project team	Established themes and preparing workshops material	Human resources Project team Knowledge and innovation relay department	May – August 2024
Invitation external lecturers who are experts in different (provided) topic	Project team Knowledge and innovation relay department	External lectures (two experts): agreed topics and execution time	Funding for external lecturers	May – June 2024, January 2025
Organising of 4 workshops for the target groups	Project team Knowledge and innovation relay department	Ruler method to evaluate participants' knowledge before and after each workshop. Self-test questions after each workshop or feedback quiz (closed questions) after each workshop.	University's target groups (administration, teachers, researchers, students, doctoral students) External participants: coaches, athletes, representatives of the Sport clubs, Sports Federations	September 2024 – May 2025

				Municipal sports centres	
Dissemination workshops	of	Project team	Preparation of the articles (4) for the social media	Communication and marketing department	September 2024 –May 2025

Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: to secure formal institutional commitment to the 4I-GEP through a structured approval process, and ensure the lasting effect of the roadmap’s achievements.

Implementation plan

To achieve formal approval of the Institutional 4I-GEP within our organization, the following steps must be followed:

1. Perfection of the draft of the 4I-GEP (January - February 2025)

The process begins with the SUPPORTER core team perfection the Institutional 4I GEP draft. This step involves sequential steps to improve the content, structure and overall quality to ensure that the plan aligns with the organization’s goals and lessons learned from the SUPPORTER’s training and implementation of the institutional plan.

2. Feedback from students and staff (February - March (1st half) 2025)

Feedback will be collected from university staff and students. The goal of this step is to receive comments, different perspectives, and suggestions to adjust the Institutional 4I-GEP.

3. Presentation for review to University Rectorate (March (2st half) 2025)

Taking into account the comments and suggestions of the University community, the improved document will be submitted for review to the University Senate. This step ensures that the Senate provides suggestions for improvement, as well as supports and approves the plan before it is submitted for final approval.

4. Finalise the draft (April 2025)

This stage will prepare the final version of the Institutional 4I-GEP. This step ensures that the Institutional 4I-GEP will be submitted for final approval.

5. Approval by Rector’s order (May 2025)

The revised Institutional 4I-GEP will be submitted to the University Rector for approval. This marks the official approval of the institutional 4I-GEP within our organization.

6. Presentation of the approved document on University community public disk (May (2nd half) 2025)

The approved institutional 4I-GEP is placed in the LSU public space. The aim is to ensure that the 4I-GEP is publicly accessible.

Stakeholders that need to be involved: SUPPORTER core team, Ethics Committee, Human Resources Department, Psychological Well-being Committee, University staff, students, Senate members, Rector.

Implementation plan

Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
Delays in timeline	Plan for contingency time within the timeline to absorb minor delays without impacting the overall timeline
Limited participation of stakeholders	Actively invite and communicate the benefits of institutional 4I-GEP. Identify and engage key influencers within each

	stakeholder group to encourage active participation
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Timeline

Activity (Step)	Involved stakeholders	Required resources	Timeline
Perfection of the draft of the 4I-GEP	Psychological Well-being Committee SUPPORTER core team	Project documentation, human resources	January-February 2025
Feedback from students and staff	Human Recourses department Student Union Committee of Ethics	Human resources, feedback mechanism	February - March (1 st half) 2025
Presentation for review to University Rectorate	Heads of Departments, Administration, Vice-rectors.	Human resources	March (2 nd half) 2025
Finalise the draft	SUPPORTER core team	Human resources	April 2025
Approval by Rector's order	SUPPORTER core team	Human resources	May 2025
Presentation of the approved document on University community public disk	SUPPORTER core team Human Recourses department	<i>Human resources, IT</i>	May (2 nd half) 2025

6. Universitatea de Vest din Timișoara (UVT)

Summary of changes

GA1 – Establishing a gender audit mechanism and mapping knowledge on selected GEP elements.

With this GA we aimed to identify:

- the possible problems that could occur within our institution regarding the gender equality due to the lack of knowledge regarding the GEP and GBV principles.
- the real level of awareness of our academic and research staff regarding the GEP and GBV principles and issues.
- possible problems that could affect social relations and the work environment through the misunderstanding or defective application of some principles related to gender equality in the process of recruiting human resources, respectively in the process of integrating into the collectives of the faculty some minority members from the point of view of the GEP principle

- No changes were made

GA2 – Creating a communication and dissemination strategy

With this GA we aimed to build an effective communication policy and channels that covers the various dimensions of gender+ equality and focuses on external stakeholder engagement.

- No changes were made

GA3 – Raising awareness on gender+ equality in sports environment

With this GA we aimed to:

- Insert the topic of gender equality on the organisational agenda
- Promote a uniform understanding on the concept of gender+ equality in sports higher education
- Initiate discussions on unconscious bias, stereotypes, and the implications of gender inequality on individuals and the broader sports community
- Explain the role of the GEP in advancing gender+ equality and institutional change

During this activity we propose a series of awareness raising activities consisting of 3 items:

a) Infoday

b) Stakeholder event

c) Social media campaign

The first 2 were organised together as a bigger event according to the proposed time schedule in October. The first 2 were organised according to the proposed time schedule in October. The last one was postponed for February 2025 due to the fact that more knowledgeable experts showed their interest to participate as external advisers within the project. In order to benefit of their

expertise and to accommodate them within the activity. This changed the evaluation of the impact which needs a time adjustment accordingly.

GA4 – Development of a Guideline for the prevention, assessment and intervention in situations of harassment in the workplace and among students

This Grounding Action consists in the development of a guideline for preventing and addressing GBV incidents at the faculty.

Implementation Plan

1. Thorough assessment of existing policies and practices related to GBV prevention and treatment and of their alignment with the national and European legislation. This step also draws on the results of GA1 regarding the perceptions and incidents of GBV at faculty and university level.
2. Identification and appointment of competent body for handling reports on GBV incidents
3. Development of the guideline document, which shall include: a) scope and guiding principles, b) prevention measures, c) reporting procedures, d) support services within and outside the University, e) investigation procedures, and f) violation consequences.
4. Seek approval of the new GBV guideline and related procedures.
5. Training of the new GBV body in charge of implementing the Guideline on what is gender-based violence and its specificities, for example, understanding trauma and implementing a victim-centred approach.
6. Preparation for the implementation of the Guideline - Establishment of the stipulated procedures.

Within this GA we operated some changes regarding *time adjustments* for two of the activities, Development of the guideline postponed for February 2025 and Seek approval for the new Guideline postponed for March 2025.

This was necessary because we identified experts who will contribute to the document in order to add value to the document, specially in the area of integrating the elements related to intersectionality. Thus they can help us to understand better and then to apply the intersectionality concepts within the guideline and further 4I-GEP in order to combat any kind of gender inequality or to be able to identify how gender-based violence does not manifest uniformly but can be affected by other dimensions of identity.

Thus, the experts will share their expertise in order to help us to integrate better the intersectionality principles first into a guideline document regarding a gender equality then in our 4I GEP with focus on gender-based violence by helping us in creating an inclusive framework sensitive to diversity:

- through educational programs that address gender-based violence from multiple perspectives. These include training modules for teachers, coaches, and students on how gender and race stereotypes influence relationships and behaviors in sports.
- Collecting data that reflect diversity and allow for a more detailed understanding of gender-based violence through an intersectional analysis.
- Collaboration between educational institutions, sports organizations, government authorities, and non-governmental organizations is crucial in creating a comprehensive plan that addresses gender-based violence. These entities can work together to create prevention

measurements and ensure real protection adapted to the needs of all individuals, regardless of their background.

Therefore, integrating intersectionality first into a guideline document and further in our 4I -GEP is essential for addressing gender-based violence in a comprehensive way, recognizing the complexity of various identities and forms of discrimination that intersect in the context of sports and higher education.

GA5 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

- No changes have made

GA6 – Proposing inclusive actions within the teaching curriculum for practical/ sports activities towards gender+ equality

This GA consists of a number of actions that encourage a productive dialogue among academic and research staff members in order to agree on the GE principles and concepts that have to be incorporated into the teaching scheme. This will lead to proposed amendments in the existing curriculum.

1. Within this activity we proposed some time adjustments regarding activities Creating the auto evaluation assessment form - We started the auto-evaluation assessment quiz form but we do not have the final version until January 2025 when all the training materials will be done.
2. Preparing focus group discussion with the academic staff in order to explore: a) identification of GE differences, b) coping strategies applied during the teaching activity, c) topics and methods that need to be incorporated in the curriculum, d) the possibility of making amendments to existing modules - Due to Holydays and legal free days in December was not the best month to round up a focus group. Therefore this activity was postponed for February 2025
3. Discussion with previous students to gather their views on whether and how the curriculum would benefit from a gendered perspective - Due to the time delays in order to create the student focus group we have to postpone the discussions with the students for March 2025

Grounding Actions

A set of six Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5	GA6
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<i>Intersectional</i>	x	x	x			
<i>Innovative</i>		x	x			x
<i>Inclusive</i>		x	x	x	x	x
<i>Impactful</i>		x	x	x	x	
<i>Tailored to sports</i>	x	x	x		x	

GA1 – Establishing a gender audit mechanism and mapping knowledge on selected GEP elements

The GA1 consists of creating a survey quiz that will be designed to collect information regarding the following topics:

- Level of awareness on gender equality
- Gender balance in leadership and decision-making and GBV in PESF-UVT
- Integrating gender into research and teaching in PESF-UVT

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring; Dedicated resources

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment; Gender balance in leadership and decision-making

b. Objectives

O1 Identifying the possible problems that could occur within our institution regarding the gender equality due to the lack of knowledge regarding the GEP and GBV principles.

O2 Identifying the real level of awareness of our academic and research staff regarding the GEP and GBV principles and issues.

O3 Identifying possible problems that could affect social relations and the work environment through the misunderstanding or defective application of some principles related to gender equality in the process of recruiting human resources, respectively in the process of integrating into the collectives of the faculty some minority members from the point of view of the GEP principle.

It is known that each field has its own peculiarities. Thus, GA1 responds to our institutional need to have an overview of the specific problems that could arise within the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport in UVT.

By achieving the objectives proposed in GA1, first, we will have obtained a first assessment of the level of knowledge and interest in gender inequalities issues. The analysis of the survey results will reveal issues related to recruitment, career progression and decision-making: managerial issues, decisions related to the increase or reduction of human resources, the integration of new members, selection among current employees or students who belong to gender minorities. Also, it will enable the identification of problems and ensuing solutions related to work-life balance and other GEP

elements in the academic and research activity in the field of sports, as well as of unforeseen situations arising at the workplace regarding GBV.

c. Implementation plan

To complete the task, the following **sequential** actions will be implemented.

1. Creating a working team and assigning roles in a clear manner to capitalise on relevant expertise and avoid confusion in task implementation. Members of the Communication Department may join to assist with the creation of tools for the recruitment of participants.
2. Creation of the survey quiz form
3. Collecting data from the electronic platform that automatically ensures data collection and subsequent data analysis and processing
4. Analysing the data using the quantitative methods identified during the development of the methodology
5. Elaborating the scientific report based on the analysed data
6. Dissemination of project results

Analysing all the information from the faculty-specific survey, we aim to obtain information that, incorporated in the future training materials of the faculty staff, will add more value to the already existing academic expertise of our academic and research staff on the application of the current GEP's principles. At the moment, at our institutional level, only a few actions have taken place regarding gender equality, and even fewer regarding GBV, which involved a limited number of employees. Thus, by understanding the current state of knowledge regarding the principles of GEP and GBV, we will create the basis for an increase in the quality of the work environment, on the one hand; on the other hand, we will be able to monitor and address the dynamics of the evolution of service relations, for the creation of a more inclusive academic environment.

- The data will be analysed both globally and based on the declared gender of the respondents in order to create a multiaxial barometer.
- The first axis of analysis is the identification of the most important and specific problems of our collective that could interfere with the balance between life and work, both on a general and on a gender-specific level. The questionnaire will be shared with other partner institutions in the project, in order to be applied, if suitable, to their institutional context and produce comparable data within the SUPPORTER project.
- The second axis of analysis is related to the evaluation of the respondents' opinion regarding gender in decision-making. The aim is to identify the possible problems, at the institutional level, that the managerial team members could face at their workplace, in the case that they belong in the gender minority.
- The third axis of analysis is related to the evaluation of the respondents' opinion regarding the general and specific level of knowledge regarding the principles related to gender equality. This will facilitate the identification of possible misunderstandings of the GE principles that could lead to a defective application of these desired to the recruitment of new human resources in our institution. The aim is to identify possible problems that could interfere with the provision of equal opportunities on all genders when accessing different positions in the faculty's organisational chart. We will insist on identifying the causes that could generate possible problems of a socio-economic nature, in the short, medium and long term, at the institutional level if a certain candidate is recruited to occupy a certain position within the staff either academic level or research.

- The fourth axis of analysis is related to the evaluation of respondents' perceptions and knowledge regarding GBV. The main purpose is to identify issues that might arise in the academic environment regarding GBV, including the most important factors that could trigger GBV-type actions from all participants in the teaching process and research in the institution. This is necessary for the creation of a distinctive chapter within the PESF GEP on GBV, encompassing the definition of types of GBV, relevant problems and treatment of possible incidents. This chapter is currently missing from the general university GEP and could thus become a milestone for the development of a new and improved version of the university-wide GEP. It will also help to devise future training activities for academic and research staff as well as students.

The measurable **indicators** used to monitor the accomplishment of the GA1 are as follows:

1. The survey quiz. Existing questionnaires from previous research or other projects may be used or serve as inspiration.
2. The number of respondents, segregated into categories (staff/students, level of education, position etc.)
3. The data analysis that reflects the global answers and answers provided by the gender related interviewed subgroups.
4. Finalising the survey based on focus group discussion with target audience
5. The final report that contains the conclusion of the study.
7. At least one scientific paper will be submitted to the prestigious journals as a dissemination part of the results.
8. The materials that could be disseminated at different workshops.

Required resources:

a) Human resources

- The project team members involved in
 - Co-creation of the survey quiz - five members
 - Data analysis and processing - five members
 - Elaboration of the GA1 Report - five members
 - Elaboration of scientific papers - five members
 - Elaboration of the materials that will be disseminated within the workshops
 - Dissemination of the results of the study at scientific meetings and symposia
- The academic, research, administrative staff of PESF–UVT to participate in the survey - 35-40 persons (target group 1)
- The students from bachelor, master and doctoral studies (target group 2) min. 300 persons
- An extra resource involves the Ethics Committee members, the Vice-Rector for Research, and the representatives of the Department of Media and Communication that will participate as guests at our InfoDay.

B) Material resources

The material resources will be largely covered by the project funds, including salaries of the project team members, direct costs, and costs of materials such as office supplies, dissemination posters, the dissemination materials for the InfoDay: posters, roll-ups, flyers. A special category of expenses will be the publication tax necessary for the publication of the scientific papers resulted from the study.

The **success criteria** for GA1 are as follows:

- Creation of a comprehensive and complex survey quiz

- Elaboration of the GA-1 report that will present the results and the conclusion of the study
- The elaboration of at least one scientific paper based on the results of the survey.

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Ethics Committee, Department of Scientific Research and University Creation, Department of Communication, Image and Institutional Marketing

Only informing: Vice Rector for Research, PESF-UVT Union, Legal Department

e. Potential obstacles

The GA-1 should be implemented without major obstacles but there are some situations beyond our control that could hinder the implementation of the GA, such as the following:

- Insufficient data collection due to low interest/reluctance of staff/students to express their perceptions on the topic
- Detection of possible biases due to stereotypes regarding GE and GBV
- Unexpected disasters (war, social, environmental, medical) impairing the project implementation

Possible mitigating measures include:

- Promotion via email, flyers, one-to-one and group discussions explaining the importance of participation for the development of a PESF-UVT reflecting the institutional needs
- Focus group with academic staff before the creation of the survey to detect main issues
- Depends on the gravity of the situation of the unforeseeable disaster, any measure will always prioritise the health and safety of the team

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Create a working team	Project team PESF-UVT	List of team members for this GA	Human resources	April 2024
2. Review and analysis of existing datasets and methods	Project team, Ethics Committee	List of identified gaps	Human resources Software	April – May 2024
3. Define suitable data collection and analysis methods	Project team Ethics Committee Legal department	Methodological plan for the collection and analysis of data	Human resources	May 2024
4. Creation of the survey quiz form to	Team project Ethics Committee	The survey quiz that covers all proposed chapters, including	Human resources Software	June 2024

meet all the chapters mentioned above	Legal department	consent form in the beginning		
5. Finalise the survey through focus group discussion	Project team Staff/student representatives	Insights from focus group Final version of questionnaire	Human resources Classroom for focus group	June – July 2024
6. Informing the target groups and disseminating the survey	Project team Ethics Committee Communications Department	Min. 300 persons from main target groups in InfoDay Number of persons reached via email/website/other communication channels	Human resources Venue Software (for the survey) Communication tools	June – July 2024
7. Running the survey	Project team	The raw data sheet collected from the quiz platform	Human resources IT support (technological equipment, software)	September – October 2024
8. Analysing the data using statistical methods	Project team	Statistical data	Human resources Software for statistical analysis	November 2024
9. Elaborating the scientific report based on the analysed data	Project team Ethics Committee Department of Research	The final GA1-Report submitted at academic journal	Human resources	January 2025
10. Dissemination of survey results	Project team Communications Department Department of Research	Publicity materials Flyers UVT	Human resources Communication material	January – March 2025

GA1- No changes were made

GA2 – Creating a communication and dissemination strategy

This GA builds an effective communication policy and channels that covers the various dimensions of gender+ equality and focuses on external stakeholder engagement.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources; Training and awareness-raising

b. Objectives

By this action we aim to provide all the information regarding gender equality, the GEP and the other related policies, and to attract new collaborations with other groups from UVT oriented to better implementation of gender equality actions.

This action will increase the visibility of the project and the results within UVT academia and society regarding gender equality in sports higher education.

This will be achieved through the development of a concrete communication strategy that invests in the creation/exploitation of effective communication channels and explores networking opportunities.

c. Implementation plan

1. Setting up the working team (including communications team members, students and/or staff) and clearly allocating tasks for building the communication strategy
2. Defining the communication strategy objectives, tools and key internal and external stakeholders
3. Development of the communication strategy, including the establishment of regular channels (such as email exchanges, university events, seminars, and departmental meetings) to update stakeholders on GEP progress and initiatives related to gender+ equality.
4. Seeking approval for the finalised communication strategy (if necessary)
5. Development of an InfoPoint at the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport to serve as a repository for all the information related to gender+ equality. All information regarding the project's ongoing and upcoming actions and results will also be communicated via the InfoPoint.

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, Department of Research and University Creation, Department of Communication, Image and Institutional Marketing

Only consulting: Legal Department, Ethics Committee, IT Support, Senior management

e. Potential obstacles

The following obstacles are foreseen:

- Low interest/apathy of the target groups to participate in the InfoPoint activities
- Low engagement of internal and external stakeholders due to ineffective communication

Possible mitigating measures include:

- Capitalising on existing networks
- Intensifying communication efforts and resources (if available)
- Replacing ineffective, traditional communication channels with innovative approaches

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working team	Project team Communications department	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024
2. Development of communication strategy	Project team Communications Department Department of Research	Communication strategy document	Human resources	April – May 2024
3. Design of the communication tools	Project team Communications Department	Communication tools/material	Multimedia tools Human resources	May 2024
4. Seeking approval	Project team Senior management	Approved strategy	Human resources	June 2024
5. Creating the InfoPoint	Project team IT support Communications Department Department of Research	Operational website/space within the faculty's website	Human resources Software	May – June 2024

GA2 - No changes were made

GA3 – Raising awareness on gender+ equality in sports environment

This GA designs a series of awareness-raising activities on gender biases and stereotypes in the sports environments and the role of GEP in addressing these inequalities.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising; Public document

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture

b. Objectives

The aim is to cultivate a culture of awareness, collaboration, and support for gender equality, through:

- Inserting the topic of gender equality on the organisational agenda
- Promoting a uniform understanding on the concept of gender+ equality in sports higher education

- Initiating discussions on unconscious bias, stereotypes, and the implications of gender inequality on individuals and the broader sports community
- Explaining the role of the GEP in advancing gender+ equality and institutional change

c. Implementation plan

The following activities will be followed to carry out this GA:

1. Setting up a working team
2. Development of the awareness-raising plan by defining the objectives, target audience, timeframe and budget, as well as a detailed plan of the activities and the desired outcome.
3. Design of the awareness-raising material, including the creation of relevant content and the visuals for all the dissemination material, based on the communication strategy which has been established under this GA.
4. Implementation of the activities, such as a) one info-day for students and staff to discuss basic concepts regarding gender equality, highlight the role of the GEP and stimulate interest for participation in the survey. In the **Info-day**, the academic community of PESF-UVT will be informed on the project running, results and organised actions. It will be organised as one-time event and it will be followed by a Press conference; b) one local stakeholder event for external stakeholders, and c) a social media campaign.
5. Evaluation of the awareness-raising plan's impact and possibility for future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, Department of Communication, Image, and Institutional Marketing, External experts

Only consulting: Ethics Committee, PESF-UVT Student Union, External experts

Only informing: Senior management

e. Potential obstacles

- Internal resistances and stereotypes regarding traditional gender roles
- Reluctance of students or staff to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics. This can be mitigated through a clear description of the content and objectives of the awareness-raising activities.
- Limited human resources and work overload
- Lack of internal expertise on gender bias and stereotypes in sports

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Setting up the working team	Project team Communications Department	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024

2. Development of awareness-raising plan	Project team Student Union Staff representatives Communications Department	Detailed plan	Human resources	May 2024
3. Design of the awareness-raising plan	Project team Communications Department	Communication material and material for the awareness-raising activities	Multimedia tools Human resources	June 2024
4. Launching the awareness-raising activities	Project team Communications Department External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	June – October 2024
5. Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)	Human resources	October – November 2024

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
The GA 3	Title of the change (e.g., timeline adjustment, new resources allocated, shift in focus)	Briefly state the reason behind the change (e.g. inspired by training, logistical challenges, low participation in one event etc.)

1. Setting up the working team	No changes were made	-
2. Development of awareness-raising plan	No changes were made	-
3. Design of the awareness-raising plan	No changes were made	-
4. Launching the awareness-raising activities	Timeline adjustment	<p>This activity consisted of 3 items:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> a) Infoday b) Stakeholder event c) Social media campaign <p>The first 2 were organised according to the proposed time schedule in October.</p> <p>Meanwhile, more knowledgeable experts showed their interest to participate as external advisers within the project. In order to benefit of their expertise and to accommodate them the social media campaign was delayed until February 2025.</p>
5. Evaluating impact	Time line adjustment	The adjustment was necessary due to the time line adjustment of the activity 4

GA4 – Development of a Guideline for the prevention, assessment and intervention in situations of harassment in the workplace and among students

This Grounding Action consists in the development of a guideline for preventing and addressing GBV incidents at the faculty.

a. GEP Element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- Development of a comprehensive guideline for preventing and addressing GBV cases within the faculty
- Definition of gender-based violence content and fundamental principles regarding reporting of relevant incidents, such as confidentiality
- Creation of a culture of zero tolerance towards gender-based violence and sexual harassment

c. Implementation Plan

7. Thorough assessment of existing policies and practices related to GBV prevention and treatment and of their alignment with the national and European legislation. This step also draws on the results of GA1 regarding the perceptions and incidents of GBV at faculty and university level.
8. Identification and appointment of competent body for handling reports on GBV incidents
9. Development of the guideline document, which shall include: a) scope and guiding principles, b) prevention measures, c) reporting procedures, d) support services within and outside the University, e) investigation procedures, and f) violation consequences.
10. Seek approval of the new GBV guideline and related procedures.
11. Training of the new GBV body in charge of implementing the Guideline on what is gender-based violence and its specificities, for example, understanding trauma and implementing a victim-centred approach.
12. Preparation for the implementation of the Guideline - Establishment of the stipulated procedures.

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, IT Department,

Only consulting: Ethics Committee, Legal Department, External experts

Only informing: Senior management

e. Potential Obstacles

- Resistances: Lack of recognition that this GBV is an important issue, that the faculty is facing such behaviours, and of the need to adopt measures and policies on gender-based violence
- Limited resources (financial, human, time) for developing and maintaining internal structures and procedures.
- Potential legal or regulatory constraints in establishing certain procedures.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
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1. Assessment of existing policies/priorities	Project team Legal Department	Summary of existing policies/gaps	Human resources	October 2024
2. Appointment of competent body	Project team Legal Department	New position Description of responsibilities	Human resources Financial resources for the new position	November 2024
3. Development of the Guideline	Project team Legal department External experts (if necessary)	Guideline document	Human resources	November – December 2024
4. Seek approval for the new Guideline	Project team Senior management	Approved Protocol New reporting mechanism	Human resources	January 2025
5. Training of the competent body for GBV incidents	Project team External expertise	Participation in training session	Human resources Financial resources for capacity-building in external trainings	January – March 2025
6. Establishment of new procedures	Project team IT team Communications Department	New structures in place and operational	Human resources Software/technological equipment	February – April 2025

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
The GA 4	Title of the change (e.g., timeline adjustment, new resources allocated, shift in focus)	Briefly state the reason behind the change (e.g. inspired by training, logistical challenges, low participation in one event etc.)
1. Assessment of existing policies/priorities	No changes were made	-
2. Appointment of competent body	No changes were made	-

3. Development of the guideline document	Time line adjustment	We identified experts who will contribute to the document in order to add value to the document. To accommodate them we delayed the action for February 2025
4. Seek approval for the new Guideline document	Time line adjustment	March 2025- The adjustment was necessary due to the time line adjustment of the activity 3
5. Training of the competent body for GBV incidents	No changes were made	-
6. Establishment of new procedures	No changes were made	-

GA5 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

This GA develops and implements awareness-raising activities on GBV and sexual harassment in sport environments both at university and at local/national level.

a. GEP Element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- To increase understanding both of internal and of external stakeholders on forms of gender-based violence (physical, sexual, psychological, economic and financial, sexual harassment, online) in the sports context
- To create a safe environment and a culture of respect, equality and zero tolerance towards gender-based violence
- To introduce staff and students to the relevant regulatory framework and internal procedures in place (reporting and case management, support mechanisms) in a simple and comprehensive manner

c. Implementation plan

The following activities will be carried out to implement this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up the working team (incl. students and/or staff, and a communication team to engage external stakeholders effectively)

2. Development of a comprehensive scheme (Define objectives and message, target audience, timeframe and budget, outline the campaign’s activities and desired outcome)
3. Design the material for the planned activities (define appropriate channels, create the visuals, prepare the presentations)
4. Launch the awareness-raising activities, such as one workshop organised for staff, one workshop organised for students, one workshop organised specifically for first-year students and a local stakeholder event (e.g. in the form of an awareness day) to raise awareness of targeted external stakeholders such as sports clubs, trainers, associations, umbrella organisations, public authorities.
5. Evaluate the scheme’s impact and explore possibility for future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, GBV institutional body, Department of Communication, Image, and Institutional Marketing, External Experts, Staff representatives

Only consulting: PESF-UVT Student Union, Ethics Committee

Only informing: Senior management

e. Potential obstacles

- Internal resistances and stereotypes regarding traditional gender roles
- Low engagement of internal and external stakeholders due to ineffective communication. Possible solutions include: capitalising on existing networks, intensifying communication efforts and replacing ineffective, traditional communication channels with innovative approaches.
- Reluctance of students or staff to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics. This can be mitigated through a clear description of the content and objectives of the awareness-raising activities.
- Limited human resources and work overload
- Lack of internal expertise on gender bias and stereotypes in sports

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Setting up the working team	Project team GBV body Communications Department	List of team members	Human resources	January 2025
2. Development of awareness-raising scheme	Project team GBV body Student Union	Detailed plan	Human resources	January – February 2025

	Staff representatives Communications Department			
3. Design of the awareness-raising scheme	Project team Communications Department	Communication material Material for the awareness-raising activities	Multimedia tools Human resources	February 2025
4. Launching the awareness-raising activities	Project team GBV body Communications Department External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	March – May 2025
5. Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)	Human resources	June 2025

GA5- No changes were made

GA6 – Proposing inclusive actions within the teaching curriculum for practical/ sports activities towards gender+ equality

This GA consists of a number of actions that encourage a productive dialogue among academic and research staff members in order to agree on the GE principles and concepts that have to be incorporated into the teaching scheme. This will lead to proposed amendments in the existing curriculum.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising; Dedicated resources

Thematic: Integrating the gender dimension into the teaching content

b. Objectives

The main purpose of this GA is to incorporate the gender discussion into the didactic process by introducing a portfolio of awareness assessment tools and teaching strategies, hosting academic dialogues and suggesting amendments on the curriculum.

c. Implementation plan

GA6 activities are as follows:

4. Creating the auto evaluation assessment form
5. Preparing focus group discussion with the academic staff in order to explore: a) identification of GE differences, b) coping strategies applied during the teaching activity, c) topics and methods that need to be incorporated in the curriculum, d) the possibility of making amendments to existing modules
6. Discussion with previous students to gather their views on whether and how the curriculum would benefit from a gendered perspective
7. Carrying out focus groups discussion with academic staff
8. Colecting and Analysing the data from the focus groups
9. Report with results and recommendations for curriculum updates

d. Stakeholders involved

Co-producing: Project team, Department of Communication, Image, and Institutional Marketing, Department of Research and University Creation

Only consulting: Ethics Committee, PESF-UVT Student Union

Only informing: Senior management, Legal Department

e. Potential obstacles

- Heavy workload of academic staff leading to low participation
- Detection of possible biases due to the presence of different stereotypes that can lead to the drop off from the focus groups.

f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Creating the auto evaluation assessment quiz/form	Project team Ethics Committee Legal Department Department of Scientific Research Academic staff	Survey quiz	Human resources Office supplies	We started the auto-evaluation assessment quiz form but we do not have the final version until January 2025 when all the training materials will be done.

2. Preparing focus group discussions with staff/students	Project team Ethics Committee Department of Scientific Research	Interview guide Recruitment criteria	Human resources	Due to Holydays and legal free days in December was not the best month to round up a focus group. Therefore this activity was postponed for February 2025
3. Discussion towards previous students to gather their views on whether and how the curriculum would benefit from a gendered perspective	Project team Academic staff	Number of previous students participating	Human resources Venue	Due to the time delays in order to create the student focus group we have to postpone the disscussions with the students for March 2025
4. Carry out focus group discussion with staff	Project team Academic staff	Summary of gaps, choice of topics and strategies to address gender inequalities Proposed modules for amendment	Human resources	January – February 2025
5. Analysing the collected data from the focus groups	Project team Ethics Committee Department of Scientific Research	Analysing report	Human resources	March – April 2025
6. Report on findings and recommendations for curriculum update	Module teachers	Updated module (syllabus and material)	Time E-system	May – June 2025

Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: to secure formal institutional commitment to the 4I-GEP through a structured approval process, and ensure the lasting effect of the roadmap's achievements.

Implementation plan

Step 1 Develop a draft of the 4I-GEP. The development of the 4I GEP is a step in which the SUPPORTER team will create a document that will include all concepts related to gender equality, with a special focus on the field of sports, and specifically references related to gender-based violence in higher education institutions. This stage involves a review of the general GEP content of UVT, to which the specific aspects of the 4I, which have been integrated throughout the project, will be added.

Step 2 Feedback from students, academia and staff representatives. This step involves collecting feedback from both the academic community of the Faculty of Physical Education and Sport, including professors, students, and representatives of the student union within the faculty, as well as feedback from colleagues in the UVT union, faculty members, and last but not least, feedback from colleagues involved in the development of the university's GEP. This feedback will be collected through a form that will be distributed online, allowing respondents to evaluate the content of the faculty's I-GEP based on an appropriate scaling system for each item, as well as through open-ended questions where they can express their own opinions regarding the content of the document under consultation. After collecting and analyzing the responses, improvements will be made, if necessary, to the highlighted articles.

Step 3. Review by legal department. The review of the document by the Legal Department is a necessary step to ensure the legality and accuracy of the information included in the new 4I GEP. For this reason, the Legal Department will be provided with the final version of the document, which includes all relevant suggestions added following the public consultation conducted in the previous step, both regarding gender equality in general and the issues related to gender-based violence. After receiving the response from the Legal Department, the next step can be taken.

Step 4. Finalise the draft. The finalization of the draft is a stage that involves integrating into the document all suggestions regarding the legal aspects raised by the relevant department, in order to create a logical, comprehensive document that addresses all the elements required by the 4I and that will become a reference document for our faculty.

Step 5. Submit for reviewing and approval to Faculty Teaching Council. This involves disseminating the final document to the members of the Faculty Council for consultation and obtaining the final version through a vote. The document that has received legal approval will be subjected to consultation, and in a council meeting, it will be presented for a vote to be approved as an official document of the faculty. Once approved, the document can be disseminated and presented to the entire academic community through the faculty's media channels.

Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Busy time of the university year in January and February due to Exam sessions which leads to difficulties in matching on site working meetings and some delays 	Discussing and matching schedules, maybe using the online tools for the working meetings

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Reduced implication of the students and academic staff in the process of giving feedback based on their limited experience in the evaluation of such documents 	<p>Creating online tools like a form where they can evaluate the proposed GEP using different criteria and scales and where they can express their opinion regarding the most important aspects of the GEP.</p>
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Timeline

Activity (Step)	Involved stakeholders	Required resources	Timeline
Develop a draft of the 4I-GEP	SUPPORTER core team	Human resources	January-February
Feedback from students and staff reps	Student Union Staff reps	Human resources Feedback mechanism	March (1st half)
Review by legal department	Legal department	Human resources	March (2 nd half)
Finalise draft	SUPPORTER core team	Human resources	April
Submit reviewing and approval	Faculty Teaching Council	Human resources	May

7. Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education and Sport (GSTUPES)

Summary of changes

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender equality in sports environment.

Nature of the Change:

- 1. Change of GA's initial title**
- 2. Merger of GA1 and GA4**
- 3. Involved Stakeholders change**
- 4. Timeline was modified**
- 5. Resources were reallocated**

Justification for the Change

The merger of GA1 and GA4 was made due to the fact that GA4 was not contributing anything to our roadmap and these two GAs overlapped each other.

GA4 was removed from the Roadmap.

After we merged these two GAs, we changed the title to - Raising Awareness of Gender Equality in Sports Environment.

The list of involved stakeholders was also modified. There was no need for an external expert, both internal meetings were conducted by the SUPPORTER project team members. So we removed external expert from the list.

A timeline change occurred because July is a summertime and participants availability is very low. So, to involve more students, academic and administrative staff in raising awareness activities we decided to postpone the event.

Instead of external expert, we invited internal expert on gender equality issues.

GA2 – Development of a communication strategy for external stakeholder engagement

Nature of the Change: Changes in this GA affected only the timeline.

- 1. We delayed Info Point activity**
- 2. We deleted senior management approval activity from the timeline.**

Justification for the Change

Initially, we planned to create InfoPoint activity to take place in May- June 2024, however, due to the re-branding of our university, and because the university official web-site is under construction, this activity has been delayed to May-June 2025. As far as we do not need the approval of university

senior management to develop a communication strategy for engaging external stakeholders, we have deleted this activity.

GA3 Setting up a GE Committee at institutional level

Nature of the Change:

1. The timeline of this GA was entirely modified:

- ***The timeline of activities 1,2,3,7 was delayed***
- ***Activity N4 - Appointment of Committee's members activity was deleted***

2. We decided to remove from Implementation plan task N4

Justification for the Change

The implementation of activities 1,2,3 and 7 was postponed because we had implemented quite a lot of activities in this period. So we simply did not have time for these specific activities.

We removed this activity N4 from the timeline, because the members of the newly created Gender Equality Committee are already employees of our university and their appointment to additional positions is irrelevant.

The changes also affected the activities 5,6. We decided to include the activities 5,6 in the 4I GEP, which will be developed at the end of the project. The reason why we do so is the large amount of work.

Task N4 of the implementation plan was removed because it is linked with activity N4 and as we mentioned above it is not relevant to make internal replacement procedures.

GA4 - Raising Awareness on gender inequalities in the sports environments

Nature of the Change:

GA4 was deleted from the Roadmap

Justification for the Change

GA4 was not contributing anything to our roadmap and GA1 and GA4 overlapped each other.

GA5 - Establishing a gender audit and monitoring mechanism

Nature of the Change:

- 1. The timeline of activities 1,2,3,4 was modified***
- 2. Timeline activities 5,6,7 replaced in 4i- GEP***

Justification for the Change

The reason why we did so is the large amount of work during September-December period.

We decided to include the activities 5,6,7 in the Gender Equality Plan, which will be developed at the end of the project. The reason why we do so is the large amount of work.

GA 6

1. Implementation plan:

a) We replaced training for competent body/person under the step N3, after the Appointment of competent body/person.

b) We integrate steps 3 and 4 (in new roadmap this step is N4)

c) Appointment of competent body

2. As a result of the changes in implementation plan we modified the timeline:

a) The timeline of activities 1,2,3,4,5 was delayed

The timeline of this GA have been modified because we were unable to complete the activities within the specified period. As stated in the potential obstacles field the reason is - limited resources (human, time) for developing internal structures and procedures.

We decided to delete from the timeline activity N4, The reason for this is the decision of top management to refrain from unnecessary expenses.

GA7 - Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

No changes were made.

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
A) GA1 B) GA2 C) GA3 D) GA5 E) GA6	A) Timeline adjustment; change of the title; merger GA1 and GA4; Rescheduling an event B) Timeline adjustment C) Timeline and Implementation plan adjustment D) Transferring actions within the framework of the 4I-GEP	A) low availability of the participants. B) Rebranding of the university C) Target audience specification D) large amount of work

Grounding Actions

A set of seven Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis

on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

Dimension	GA1	GA2	GA3	GA4	GA5	GA6
<i>Intersectional</i>	x	x		x	x	x
<i>Innovative</i>	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>Inclusive</i>	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>Impactful</i>	x	x			x	x
<i>Tailored to sports</i>	x		x		x	x

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender equality and on the role of GEP in the promotion of a gender-inclusive culture with the University

GA1 is focused on an awareness-raising campaign, consisting in various activities to increase understanding of the basic concepts of gender equality, stereotypes and biases in academic sport environment and of the importance of GEP as an integral tool in promoting institutional change.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising;

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture

b. Objectives

- To get the topic of gender equality on the institution's agenda
- To promote a uniform understanding on the concept of gender+ equality
- To explain the role of the GEP in promoting gender+ equality and institutional change

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be carried out under this GA:

1. Setting up a working group for this GA. Besides the SUPPORTER project team, the working group includes a) the HR Department who is currently responsible for implementing the GEP, b) student and staff representatives (in order to better understand the target groups' level of awareness and needs), c) members of the Communications Department which will be responsible for designing the material of the awareness-raising campaign and d) [external consultants, if needed, to support the development of the campaign](#). The different tasks under this GA will be clearly allocated among the working group members. Once formed, this group will be responsible for the design and implementation of the campaign.
2. Development of the awareness-raising campaign, which includes the following:

- Establishing the campaign’s objectives, namely to challenge the current institutional culture by increasing knowledge on the basic concepts of gender equality and by introducing and explaining the role of the GEP.
 - Defining the target audience (students, academic and administrative staff, external stakeholders)
 - Setting the budget, indicatively taking into account the human resources that may be needed (either internally or for the involvement of external experts if there is no gender expertise in the university), the costs of communication material and of the venues where the different activities will take place).
 - Outlining the campaign’s activities and timeframe. Indicatively, the following activities shall be implemented:
 - One info-day for students of all levels to discuss basic concepts regarding gender equality and to highlight the role of the GEP
 - One info-session for academic and administrative staff to clarify the basic concepts on gender equality, to explain the role of the GEP and to highlight all efforts undertaken within the SUPPORTER project, including the results and planned actions, in order to promote institutional change
 - Determining the campaign’s outcomes, including the definition of clear and achievable results and indicators and tools to achieve them (e.g. feedback form for participants, pre/post-session questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge of the participants)
3. Design of the campaign’s material, including the preparation of the campaign’s material (posters, social media/website posts, presentations) and the use of appropriate communication channels for engaging the target groups
 4. Finalising the campaign and seeking approval from the senior management
 5. Implementation of the planned activities
 6. Evaluation of the campaign’s impact through feedback from participants and assessment of increased knowledge via a pre- and post-workshop questionnaire.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Senior management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Student Union	Consulting
Department of Communication	Co-producing
External experts	Consulting/Co-producing

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited human resources leading to difficulties in forming a working group Lack of internal expertise for developing the campaign Reluctance of students or staff to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics. Lack of interest in participating in workshops. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear allocation of tasks to avoid overload or confusion of working group Engagement of external experts for the development and implementation Developing (and communicating) clear description of the content and objectives of the workshops and panel discussion. Consider integrating it into existing sets of activities (e.g. induction week)

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Communications Department External experts Student Union Staff representatives	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024
2. Development of awareness-raising campaign	Working group (as formed in the previous step)	Detailed plan	Human resources	April – May 2024
3. Design of the awareness-raising campaign	Working group	Communication material Material for the awareness-raising activities (e.g. presentations for info-sessions)	Multimedia tools Human resources Communication department	May – June 2024
4. Seeking approval	Working group Senior management	Approved awareness-raising plan	Human resources	June 2024

5. Launching the awareness-raising activities: - one info-day for students - one info-day for staff	Working group External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Communication platforms Human resources Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	September-October 2024
6. Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)	Human resources	November 2024

GA2 – Development of a communication strategy for external stakeholder engagement

This GA builds an effective communication strategy and channels that covers the various dimensions of gender+ equality and focuses on external stakeholder engagement at local, national and international level.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources; Training and awareness-raising

b. Objectives

This action aims to help develop a robust communication strategy to shift institutional attention on the gender dimension and increase outreach efforts in order to advance the values of inclusiveness and gender equality in the local ecosystem. This translates into the following objectives:

- To increase visibility of university efforts to induce institutional change through the promotion of gender-sensitive initiatives
- To establish effective communication channels for internal and external stakeholder engagement
- To disseminate the results of the SUPPORTER and other projects and attract new collaborations
- To attract new collaborations with frontline actors in the sports environment

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up the working group. Besides the SUPPORTER project team, the Communications Department will be largely involved in this action. (incl. comms, students and/or staff) and clearly allocating tasks for building the communication strategy and the design of the awareness-raising plan
2. Defining the communication strategy short-term and long-term goals, tools and target audiences (internal and external stakeholders). This stage also identifies the existing communication channels and explores their effectiveness in pursuing the defined goals.
3. Development of the communication strategy, indicatively including the capitalisation of existing and the establishment of new channels (such as email exchanges, university events, seminars, and departmental meetings) and the creation of a toolkit with communication and dissemination material.
4. Seeking approval for the finalised communication strategy (if necessary)
5. As part of the communication strategy, create an InfoPoint within the University's website to serve as a repository for all resources and activities related to gender equality (e.g. GEP and related policies, legal and institutional framework, SUPPORTER activities and outcomes).

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Communications Department	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Students/Staff	Informing
HR	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Challenges in choosing appropriate communication channels and ensuring their effectiveness Limited human resources Lack of permission for the creation of the info-point within the website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Replacing traditional communication methods with innovative channels (e.g. expanding use of social media). Testing the channels before finalising the strategy could also help identify such issues in advance.
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f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Communications department	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024
2. Development of communication strategy	Working group	Communication strategy document	Human resources	April – May 2024
3. Design of the communication tools	Working group	Communication tools/material	Multimedia tools Human resources	May 2024
4. Seeking approval	Project team Senior management	Approved strategy	Human resources	June 2024
5. Creating the InfoPoint	Working group IT support	Operational website/space within the faculty's website	Human resources Software	May – June 2025

GA3 – Setting up a GE Committee at institutional level

This Grounding Action sees to the creation of a GE body at the faculty mandated with the management of gender issues through the implementation of the 4I- GEP.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

b. Objectives

- To establish an independent body for the management of gender related matters within the institution through the implementation of the 4I-GEP
- To increase gender expertise within the university, with a focus on gender issues in sports environments
- To establish accountability for the implementation and update of the 4I-GEP within the institution
- To ensure clear task allocation and smooth cooperation among institutional bodies with a similar mandate

c. Implementation plan

1. Review of the existing relevant bodies at institutional level and of all their respective tasks
2. Formulating the mandate of the GE Committee, mainly by a) developing the regulatory framework for the Committee's operation and b) by delimitation its responsibilities in relation to the ones undertaken by the other internal bodies (e.g. Ethics Committee, HR) and with regard to the institution's relations with external policies.
3. Defining the Committee's operation, including setting the criteria for the selection of the Committee's members, as well as the frequency, duration and whereabouts of the Committee's meetings.
4. Appointment of the Committee's members following internal placement procedures (to reduce the need of further resources in case of external recruitment)
5. Identifying the training needs of the Committee members on gender+ equality through discussion with external GE experts
6. Training for the Committee members according to identified needs
7. Internal communication of the new Committee and forging links with relevant institutional bodies to communicate their role and discuss effective ways for collaboration

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Co-producing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Student/Staff	Informing
Legal department	Consulting
HR	Consulting
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of available university staff to assume the Committee's responsibilities 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Call for applications-Job opening (in case financial resources are available)

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Overlapping mandates of different bodies • Resistance at management level due to lack of awareness/reluctance to allocate resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Clear allocation of tasks discussed and decided at management level • One-on-one meetings between the SUPPORTER project team and the management in order to explain in detail the importance of a dedicated body on gender equality
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f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Review of existing bodies and responsibilities	Project team	List of existing bodies with gender-related tasks	Human resources	March-April 2025
2. Formulating the GE Committee's mandate	Project team Ethics Committee Legal department	Document with mandate Established internal structures and capacity pool	Human resources	April 2025
3. Defining Committee's operational details	Project team Legal department HR	Set of criteria for commission's selection	Human resources	April 2025
4. Appointment of Committee's members	HR Legal department	List of Committee's members and roles	Human resources	November 2024
5. Identifying training needs	Project team GE Committee External experts	Report on knowledge gaps after meeting with GE experts	Human resources External expertise	4I GEP
6. Training of GE Committee members	Project team Ethics Committee External experts	Training material; Increased knowledge	Human resources	4I GEP
7. Internal communication of the Committee's creation and mandate	GE Committee Deans and Heads of Departments Ethics Committee	Satisfactory degree of internal communication	Institutional departments (heads and active department members) Communicators with external stakeholders	April 2025

GA4 – Establishing a gender audit and monitoring mechanism

This Grounding Action aims to create a gender audit and monitoring system and pilot the new data collection processes in a selected area of priority.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring

Thematic: Gender balance in leadership and decision-making; Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

b. Objectives

- To construe a comprehensive image regarding the organisation's and faculty's current datasets related to gender equality
- To conduct a needs assessment and analysis of the state-of-play in the institution
- To adopt a holistic approach in gender audit which includes the collection of qualitative and quantitative data, addresses aspects of intersectionality and considers the sports context

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this GA:

1. Creation of a working group and assignment of roles in a clear manner to capitalise on relevant expertise and avoid confusion in task implementation.
2. Review and analysis of existing datasets at the University to map what is already being collected. Focus is placed on methods, competent body and frequency of the gender audit. Identification of gender data gaps.
3. Defining suitable data collection and analysis methods and responsible institutional body. Selection of a suitable repository tool and defining the frequency of progress monitoring. Identification of criteria for the recruitment of participants
4. Development of tools for data collection on the two selected thematic areas, making sure to incorporate intersectional and sports-sensitive aspects. Both quantitative (e.g. statistical information and questionnaire) and qualitative (e.g. focus groups, interview) methods will be used and different target groups will be identified. External consultation may be needed at this stage.
5. Carrying out a pilot round of the defined data collection processes (e.g. survey and focus group) on this specific thematic area.
6. Analysis of the collected data and report on findings.
7. Reflection upon the efficiency of the selected tools and refinement for future use.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
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Project team	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Consulting
Ethics Committee	Co-producing
Student/Staff	Informing
HR	Consulting
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of understanding Low engagement (due to limited time, inadequate efforts for the recruitment of participants, little interest on GE, reluctance to share views) Internal resistances (to identify the need or value of a gender audit or to give prominence to latent inequalities) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Developing (and communicating) clear description of the objectives of the data collection Clear compliance with GDPR explained in information sheet and consent form accompanying the questionnaire/interview guide The preceding GA1 will raise awareness on the topic and importance of GE and create the basis for the successful implementation of this action

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Ethics Committee GE Committee HR	List of group members	Human resources	March-May 2025
2. Review and analysis of existing datasets	Working group	List of identified gaps	Human resources Software	March-May 2025
3. Defining data collection, analysis and recruitment methods/tools	Working group	Methodological plan for the collection and analysis of data List of recruitment criteria and recruitment methods	Human resources	March-May 2025

4. Development of data collection tools	Working group External experts	Interview guide and/or Questionnaire	Human resources Consultation time with experts	March- September 2025
5. Pilot round of data collection	Working group	Number of respondents/participants Number of interviews Feedback from personal meetings and focus groups	Human resources Communication tools for recruiting participants Venue Software	4I GEP
6. Data analysis	Working group	Report findings on	Human resources	4I GEP
7. Assessment and refinement of employed tools	Working group	Number of respondents Quality/sufficiency of collected data	Human resources	4I GEP

GA5 – Establishing Internal Structures and Procedures for GBV Prevention and Treatment within the Institution

This Grounding Action consists in the development of a Protocol for preventing and addressing GBV incidents at the University, and the establishment of the necessary structures for the implementation of the Protocol.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- Development of a comprehensive protocol for preventing and addressing GBV cases within the faculty.
- Definition of gender-based violence content and fundamental principles regarding reporting of relevant incidents
- Creation of a culture of zero tolerance towards gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

c. Implementation Plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this GA:

1. Thorough assessment of existing policies and practices related to GBV prevention and treatment and of their alignment with the national and European legislation.
2. Identification and appointment of competent body for handling reports on GBV incidents. This could involve the creation of a new body (e.g. person of trust) or the delegation of these tasks to existing bodies (e.g. Ethics Committee or the newly established GE Committee)
3. **Training for competent body for GBV incidents** in charge of implementing the protocol on what is gender-based violence and its specificities, for example, understanding trauma and implementing a victim-centred approach.
4. Development of the Protocol, which shall include: a) scope and guiding principles, b) prevention measures, c) reporting procedures, d) support services within and outside the University, e) investigation procedures, and f) violation consequences and seeking approval of the new GBV Protocol and related procedures.
5. **Establishment of new procedures for reporting GBV and SH** -elaboration of proposal,

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Senior management	Informing
Ethics and GE Committees	Co-producing
Legal Department	Consulting
IT Department	Co-producing
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Resistance in admitting that GBV is an important issue and of the urgency to adopt measures for preventing and combatting such cases ● Limited resources (financial, human, time) for developing and maintaining internal structures and procedures. ● Potential legal or regulatory constraints in establishing certain procedures. ● Reluctance of management to allocate resources for a new procedure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● One-on-one meetings between the SUPPORTER project team and the management in order to explain in detail the extent of GBV and the alarming numbers of unreported cases worldwide, combined with compounding vulnerabilities in the sports context ● Appointment of the GE Committee or the Ethics Committee as the competent body for handling GBV cases (instead of external recruitment)

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Assessment of existing policies/priorities	Project team Legal Department Ethics Committee	Summary of existing policies/gaps	Human resources	October 2024
2. Appointment of competent body	Project team Legal Department Ethics Committee	New position Description of responsibilities	Human resources Financial resources for the new position (if necessary)	December 2024
3. Training of the competent body for GBV incidents	Project team External expertise	Participation in training session	Human resources Financial resources for capacity-building in external trainings	March - April 2025
4. Development of the Protocol	Project team Ethics Committee External experts (if necessary) Appointed body	Approved Protocol document	Human resources	November – February 2024-2025
5. Establishment of new procedures for reporting GBV and SH at the university - elaboration of proposal	Project team Management <i>Appointed person of trust,</i> <i>GE Committee</i>	New structures in place and operational	Human resources - stuff	February – April 2025

GA6 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

This grounding action develops and implements awareness-raising activities on GBV and sexual harassment in sport environments both at university and at local/national level.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- To increase understanding both of internal and of external stakeholders on forms of gender-based violence (physical, sexual, psychological, economic and financial, sexual harassment, online) in the sports context
- To create a safe environment and a culture of respect, equality and zero tolerance towards gender-based violence
- To introduce staff and students to the relevant regulatory framework and internal procedures in place (reporting and case management, support mechanisms) in a simple and comprehensive manner

c. Implementation plan

The following activities will be carried out to implement this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up the working team (incl. students and/or staff, and a communication team to engage external stakeholders effectively)
2. Development of a comprehensive scheme (Define objectives and message, target audience, timeframe and budget, outline the campaign's activities and desired outcome)
3. Design the material for the planned activities (define appropriate channels, create the visuals, prepare the presentations)
4. Launching the awareness-raising activities. This includes: a) 1 workshop organised for staff, b) 1 workshop organised for students and c) 1 local external stakeholder event to raise awareness of targeted external stakeholders such as sports clubs, trainers, associations, umbrella organisations, public authorities.
5. Evaluate the scheme's impact and explore possibility for future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Communications Department	Co-producing
GE Committee	Co-producing
Student Union	Consulting
Mid-level management	Informing
External experts	Consulting/Co-producing

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
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<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reluctance of staff and students to attend the training and workshops • Lack of interest from younger students • Difficulty in engaging external stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing (and communicating) clear description of the content and objectives of the training and workshops • For freshly enrolled students -making the workshop obligatory as the first introductory class at the beginning of academic year. • Co-organisation of the external event with a key external collaborator (e.g. sports association, the National Olympic Committee)
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f. Timeline

<i>Activity</i>	<i>Responsible actor</i>	<i>Success criteria</i>	<i>Required resources</i>	<i>Timeline</i>
1. Setting up the working group	Project team GBV body Communications department Student Union Staff representatives	List of group members	Human resources	January 2025
2. Development of awareness-raising scheme	Working group	Detailed plan	Human resources	January – February 2025
3. Design of the awareness-raising scheme	Working group	Communication material and material for the awareness-raising activities	Multimedia tools, Human resources.	February 2025
4. Launching the awareness-raising activities Info-session for external stakeholders	Working group External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	March – May 2025

<p>5. Evaluating impact</p>	<p>Project team</p>	<p>Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire</p> <p>Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms</p> <p>Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)</p>	<p>Human resources</p>	<p>June 2025</p>
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Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: to secure formal institutional commitment to the 4I-GEP through a structured approval process, and ensure the lasting effect of the roadmap's achievements.

Implementation plan

Standard procedures for policy development and approval: SUPPORTER core team is responsible for drafting – February – March 2025

In this process should be involved:

- *Faculty Councils (academic staff and student reps) will provide feedback on first draft- March (2nd half) 2025.*
- *The University HR and the legal department reviews and checks GEP's alignment with institutional standards and compliance with applicable laws and regulations – April 2025*
- *Finalise the draft of GEP SUPPORTER core team and SUPPORTER partners - April-May 2025*
- *Representative Council will check before final approval – May 2025*
- *Vice-Rector (University's High-level leadership) will provide final approval of the GEP – June 2025*

Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The GEP might not fully comply with institutional standards or applicable laws. • Limited engagement or awareness about the importance of GEP • Bureaucratic Delays: The review process might take longer than anticipated. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Involve HR and the legal department <i>early</i> in the drafting process, not just at the review stage. • Provide training and continuous information on the importance of the GEP using awareness raising seminars. • Establish clear deadlines

Timeline

Activity (Step)	Involved stakeholders	Required resources	Timeline
Review of current GEP and feedback	Faculty Council, HR, SUPPORTER team	GEP document, workshops	March - 2025
Meetings and consultations on GEP	HR, Legal department; supporter team	Meeting rooms, in line platforms	April 2025
Finalizing document adjustment	Supporter team	Draft GEP document	April-May 2025
Final approval of GEP	Vice-Rector	Approved GEP document	By June 2025

8. State University of Physical Education and Sport (USEFS)

Summary of changes

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender equality and the role of GEP in the promotion of a gender-exclusive culture with the University

Initially, we planned to organise one info day for students of all levels to discuss basic concepts regarding gender equality and to highlight the role of the GEP and one info-session for academic and administrative staff to clarify the basic concepts of Gender equality, the role of the GEP and highlight all efforts undertaken within the SUPPORTER project, including the results and planned actions/ in order to promote the institutional change. As a result, we were forced to organize two information sessions, due to the great interest from students and academic staff. It was also necessary to expand the information policy about the SUPPORTER project.

GA2 – Development of a communication strategy for external stakeholder engagement.

In this GA we was planning to build the effective communication strategy and channels that cover the various dimensions of gender+ equality and focuses on external stakeholders engagement at local, national and international levels. We added age and ethnic origin as intersectional aspects in the data collected on staff and students for more information for communication strategy. This adjustment was inspired by the intersectionality exercise conducted during the Thessaloniki Mutual Learning Workshop in June 2024 of the SUPPORTER project. These new variables will enhance the inclusiveness of our data analysis and allow a more comprehensive understanding of the gender dynamics in our institution and what we to present for better understanding with external stakeholders.

GA3 – Setting up a GE Committee at the institutional/faculty level

In this GA sees to the creation of a GE body at the faculty mandated with the management of gender issues through the implementation of the GEP. After experience in workshops, trainings in the SUPPORTER project our work group decided to establish an independent body for the management of gender-related matters within the institution through the implementation of the 4I-GEP. Also, we add in the training needs of the Committee members on gender+ equality through discussions with external stakeholders the intersectionality exercise for promoting the GEP SUPES after.

GA4 – Raising Awareness of gender inequalities in the sports environments

No changes were made.

GA5 – Establishing a gender audit and monitoring mechanism

No changes were made.

GA6 – Establishing internal structures and procedures for GBV prevention and treatment within the institution

This GA consists of the development of a protocol for preventing and addressing GBV incidents at the University and the establishment of the necessary structures for the implementation of the protocol. In the implementation plan on the development of the protocol we also included extra

trainings for scope and guiding principles, reporting procedures, support services within and outside the University. We also discuss and use the information from external stakeholders about GBV during the Local event “**GENDER EQUALITY IN SPORTS - RIGHTS AND OPPORTUNITIES**” on 14 November 2024.

GA7 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

This GA develops and implements awareness-raising activities on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environments both at the university and at the local/national level. We add one awareness-raising activity with LLL Department with 2 groups – Specialty of Sport training and Specialty of Physical education on February 2025 because we see interest during the Local event on 14 November 2024.

Associated GA	Description of change	Justification
<p>The GA 1</p> <p><i>Raising awareness on gender equality and the role of GEP in the promotion of a gender-exclusive culture with the University</i></p>	<p>Organize two information sessions, due to the great interest from students and academic staff. It was also necessary to expand the information policy about the SUPPORTER project.</p>	<p>It was not enough one info session for each group.</p>
<p>The GA 2</p> <p><i>Development of a communication strategy for external stakeholder engagement.</i></p>	<p>We was planning to build the effective communication strategy and channels that cover the various dimensions of gender+ equality and focuses on external stakeholders</p>	<p>We added age and ethnic origin as intersectional aspects in the data collected on staff and students for more information for communication strategy.</p>
<p>The GA 3</p> <p><i>Setting up a GE Committee at the institutional/faculty level</i></p>	<p>Sees to the creation of a GE body at the faculty mandated with the management of gender issues through the implementation of the GEP.</p>	<p>We add in the training needs of the Committee members on gender+ equality through discussions with external stakeholders the intersectionality exercise for promoting the GEP SUPES after.</p>
<p>The GA 4</p> <p><i>Raising Awareness of gender inequalities in the sports environments</i></p> <p><i>No changes were made.</i></p>		

<p>The GA 5</p> <p><i>Establishing a gender audit and monitoring mechanism</i></p> <p>No changes were made.</p>		
<p>The GA 6</p> <p><i>Establishing internal structures and procedures for GBV prevention and treatment within the institution</i></p>	<p>The development of a protocol for preventing and addressing GBV incidents at the University and the establishment of the necessary structures for the implementation of the protocol.</p>	<p>In the implementation plan on the development of the protocol we also included extra trainings for scope and guiding principles, reporting procedures, support services within and outside the University. We also discuss and use the information from external stakeholders about GBV during the Local event “GENDER EQUALITY IN SPORTS - RIGHTS AND OPPORTUNITIES” on 14 November 2024.</p>
<p>The GA 7</p> <p><i>Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders</i></p>	<p><i>Develops and implements awareness-raising activities on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environments both at the university and at the local/national level</i></p>	<p><i>We add one awareness-raising activity with LLL Department with 2 groups – Specialty of Sport training and Specialty of Physical education on February 2025 because we see interest during the Local event on 14 November 2024.</i></p>

Grounding Actions

A set of seven Grounding Actions are envisaged to achieve the purposes of this roadmap and pave the way towards the development of a new, 4I-GEP, which will be sports-specific and place emphasis on addressing gender-based violence and sexual harassment. Each of these dimensions is comprehensively addressed by the different actions comprising the roadmap, as depicted in the following table.

<i>Dimension</i>	<i>GA1</i>	<i>GA2</i>	<i>GA3</i>	<i>GA4</i>	<i>GA5</i>	<i>GA6</i>	<i>GA7</i>
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<i>Intersectional</i>	x				x	x	x
<i>Innovative</i>	x	x	x	x	x	x	
<i>Inclusive</i>	x	x	x		x	x	
<i>Impactful</i>		x		x		x	x
<i>Tailored to sports</i>			x	x		x	x

GA1 – Raising awareness on gender equality and on the role of GEP in the promotion of a gender-inclusive culture with the University

GA1 is focused on an awareness-raising campaign, consisting in various activities to increase understanding of the basic concepts of gender equality and of the importance of GEP as an integral tool in promoting institutional change.

Organized two information sessions, due to the great interest from students and academic staff. It was also necessary to expand the information policy about the SUPPORTER project. It was not enough one info session for each group.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising; Public document

Thematic: Work-life balance and organisational culture

b. Objectives

As the first Grounding Action of this roadmap, GA1 aims to set the baseline for the following actions by pursuing the following objectives:

- To get the topic of gender equality on the institution's agenda
- To promote a uniform understanding on the concept of gender+ equality
- To explain the role of the GEP in promoting gender+ equality and institutional change

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up a working group for this GA. Besides the SUPPORTER project team, the working group includes a) the HR Department who is currently responsible for implementing the GEP, b) student and staff representatives (in order to better understand the target groups' level of awareness and needs), c) members of the Communications Department which will be responsible for designing the material of the awareness-raising campaign and d) external consultants, if needed, to support the development of the campaign. The different tasks under

this GA will be clearly allocated among the working group members. Once formed, this group will be responsible for the design and implementation of the campaign.

2. Development of the awareness-raising campaign, which includes the following:

- Establishing the campaign’s objectives, namely to challenge the current institutional culture by increasing knowledge on the basic concepts of gender equality and by introducing and explaining the role of the GEP.
 - Defining the target audience (students, academic and administrative staff, external stakeholders)
 - Setting the budget, indicatively taking into account the human resources that may be needed (either internally or for the involvement of external experts if there is no gender expertise in the university), the costs of communication material and of the venues where the different activities will take place).
 - Outlining the campaign’s activities and timeframe. Indicatively, the following activities shall be implemented:
 - One info-day for students of all levels to discuss basic concepts regarding gender equality and to highlight the role of the GEP
 - One info-session for academic and administrative staff to clarify the basic concepts on gender equality, to explain the role of the GEP and to highlight all efforts undertaken within the SUPPORTER project, including the results and planned actions, in order to promote institutional change
 - Determining the campaign’s outcomes, including the definition of clear and achievable results and indicators and tools to achieve them (e.g. feedback form for participants, pre/post-session questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge of the participants)
3. Design of the campaign’s material, including the preparation of the campaign’s material (posters, social media/website posts, presentations) and the use of appropriate communication channels for engaging the target groups
4. Finalising the campaign and seeking approval from the senior management
5. Implementation of the planned activities
6. Evaluation of the campaign’s impact through feedback from participants and assessment of increased knowledge via a pre- and post-workshop questionnaire.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Senior management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Student Union	Consulting
Department of Communication	Co-producing
External experts	Consulting/Co-producing

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited human resources leading to difficulties in forming a working group Lack of internal expertise for developing the campaign Reluctance of students or staff to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics. Lack of interest in participating in workshops. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear allocation of tasks to avoid overload or confusion of working group Engagement of external experts for the development and implementation Developing (and communicating) clear description of the content and objectives of the workshops and panel discussion. Consider integrating it into existing sets of activities (e.g. induction week)

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Communications Department External experts Student Union Staff representatives	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024
2. Development of awareness-raising campaign	Working group (as formed in the previous step)	Detailed plan	Human resources	April – May 2024
3. Design of the awareness-raising campaign	Working group	Communication material Material for the awareness-raising activities (e.g. presentations for info-sessions)	Multimedia tools Human resources	May – June 2024
4. Seeking approval	Working group Senior management	Approved awareness-raising plan	Human resources	June 2024
5. Launching the awareness-raising activities: - one info-day for students	Working group External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources	July – September 2024

- one info-day for staff		Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	
6. Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)	Human resources	September 2024

GA2 – Development of a communication strategy for external stakeholder engagement

This GA builds an effective communication strategy and channels that covers the various dimensions of gender+ equality and focuses on external stakeholder engagement at local, national and international level.

We added age and ethnic origin as intersectional aspects in the data collected on staff and students for more information for communication strategy.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources; Training and awareness-raising

b. Objectives

This action aims to help develop a robust communication strategy to shift institutional attention on the gender dimension and increase outreach efforts in order to advance the values of inclusiveness and gender equality in the local ecosystem. This translates into the following objectives:

- To increase visibility of university efforts to induce institutional change through the promotion of gender-sensitive initiatives
- To establish effective communication channels for internal and external stakeholder engagement
- To disseminate the results of the SUPPORTER and other projects and attract new collaborations
- To attract new collaborations with frontline actors in the sports environment

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up the working group. Besides the SUPPORTER project team, the Communications Department will be largely involved in this action. (incl. comms, students and/or staff) and clearly allocating tasks for building the communication strategy and the design of the awareness-raising plan
2. Defining the communication strategy short-term and long-term goals, tools and target audiences (internal and external stakeholders). This stage also identifies the existing communication channels and explores their effectiveness in pursuing the defined goals.
3. Development of the communication strategy, indicatively including the capitalisation of existing and the establishment of new channels (such as email exchanges, university events, seminars, and departmental meetings) and the creation of a toolkit with communication and dissemination material.
4. Seeking approval for the finalised communication strategy (if necessary)
5. As part of the communication strategy, create an InfoPoint within the University's website to serve as a repository for all resources and activities related to gender equality (e.g. GEP and related policies, legal and institutional framework, SUPPORTER activities and outcomes).

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Communications Department	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Students/Staff	Informing
HR	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Challenges in choosing appropriate communication channels and ensuring their effectiveness • Limited human resources • Lack of permission for the creation of the info-point within the website 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Replacing traditional communication methods with innovative channels (e.g. expanding use of social media). Testing the channels before finalising the strategy could also help identify such issues in advance.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
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1. Setting up the working group	Project team Communications department	List of team members	Human resources	March – April 2024
2. Development of communication strategy	Working group	Communication strategy document	Human resources	April – May 2024
3. Design of the communication tools	Working group	Communication tools/material	Multimedia tools Human resources	May 2024
4. Seeking approval	Project team Senior management	Approved strategy	Human resources	June 2024
5. Creating the InfoPoint	Working group IT support	Operational website/space within the faculty's website	Human resources Software	May – June 2024

GA3 – Setting up a GE Committee at institutional/faculty level

This Grounding Action sees to the creation of a GE body at the faculty mandated with the management of gender issues through the implementation of the GEP.

We add in the training needs of the Committee members on gender+ equality through discussions with external stakeholders the intersectionality exercise for promoting the GEP SUPES after.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

b. Objectives

- To establish an independent body for the management of gender related matters within the institution through the implementation of the 4I-GEP
- To increase gender expertise within the faculty, with a focus on gender issues in sports environments
- To establish accountability for the implementation and update of the 4I-GEP within the institution/faculty
- To ensure clear task allocation and smooth cooperation among institutional bodies with a similar mandate

c. Implementation plan

1. Geo members, as well as the frequency, duration and whereabouts of the Committee's meetings.
2. Appointment of the Committee's members following internal placement procedures (to reduce the need of further resources in case of external recruitment)
3. Identifying the training needs of the Committee members on gender+ equality through discussion with external GE experts
4. Training for the Committee members according to identified needs
5. Internal communication of the new Committee and forging links with relevant institutional bodies to communicate their role and discuss effective ways for collaboration

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Co-producing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Student/Staff	Informing
Legal department	Consulting
HR	Consulting
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of available university staff to assume the Committee's responsibilities • Overlapping mandates of different bodies • Resistance at management level due to lack of awareness/reluctance to allocate resources 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Call for applications-Job opening (in case financial resources are available) • Clear allocation of tasks discussed and decided at management level • One-on-one meetings between the SUPPORTER project team and the management in order to explain in detail the importance of a dedicated body on gender equality

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Review of existing bodies and responsibilities	Project team	List of existing bodies with gender-related tasks	Human resources	September 2024

2. Formulating the GE Committee's mandate	Project team Ethics Committee Legal department	Document with mandate Established internal structures and capacity pool	Human resources	October 2024
3. Defining Committee's operational details	Project team Legal department HR	Set of criteria for commission's selection	Human resources	October – November 2024
4. Appointment of Committee's members	HR Legal department	List of Committee's members and roles	Human resources	November 2024
5. Identifying training needs	Project team GE Committee External experts	Report on knowledge gaps after meeting with GE experts	Human resources External expertise	November – December 2024
6. Training of Committee members	Project team Ethics Committee External experts	Training material; Increased knowledge	Human resources	January – February 2025
7. Internal communication of the Committee's creation and mandate	GE Committee Deans and Heads of Departments Ethics Committee	Satisfactory degree of internal communication	Institutional departments (heads and active department members) Communicators with external stakeholders	March 2025

GA4 – Raising Awareness on gender inequalities in the sports environments

This GA focuses on fostering a better understanding of gender issues, stereotypes and biases in the academic sport environment through a set of awareness-raising activities.

No changes were made.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

b. Objectives

- To integrate discussions on unconscious bias, stereotypes, and the implications of gender inequality on individuals and the broader sports community.
- To empower female athletes by challenging the perception that certain sports are destined for men and encouraging gender-balanced involvement in sports, promoting the idea that talent and skills are not limited to gender.

- To tackle gender stereotypes beyond the selection of sports, including the gender of coaches and the myth of meritocracy behind leadership positions and career progression

c. Implementation plan

1. Setting up a working group for this GA. Besides the SUPPORTER project team, the working group should include a) the HR Department who is currently responsible for implementing the GEP, b) student and staff representatives (in order to better understand the target groups' level of awareness and needs), c) members of the Communications Department which will be responsible for designing the material of the awareness-raising campaign and d) external consultants, if needed, to support the development of the campaign. The different tasks under this GA will be clearly allocated among the working group members. Once formed, this group will be responsible for the design and implementation of the campaign.
2. Development of the awareness-raising campaign, which includes the following:
 - Establishing the campaign's objectives, namely to challenge the current institutional culture by increasing knowledge on the basic concepts of gender equality and by introducing and explaining the role of the GEP.
 - Defining the target audience (students, academic and administrative staff, external stakeholders)
 - Setting the budget, indicatively taking into account the human resources that may be needed (either internally or for the involvement of external experts if there is no gender expertise in the university), the costs of communication material and of the venues where the different activities will take place).
 - Outlining the campaign's activities and timeframe. Indicatively, the following activities shall be implemented: a) Two thematic workshops/Panel discussions with staff/students, b) One local stakeholder event to engage external stakeholders in a discussion about gender stereotypes in sports and how to tackle them.
 - Determining the campaign's outcomes, including the definition of clear and achievable results and indicators and tools to achieve them (e.g. feedback form for participants, pre/post-session questionnaire to assess the level of knowledge of the participants)
3. Design of the campaign's material, including the preparation of the campaign's material (posters, social media/website posts, presentations) and the use of appropriate communication channels for engaging the target groups
4. Finalising the campaign and seeking approval from the senior management
5. Implementation of the planned activities
6. Evaluation of the campaign's impact through feedback from participants and assessment of increased knowledge via a pre- and post-workshop questionnaire.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Senior management	Informing

Ethics Committee	Consulting
Student Union	Consulting
Department of Communication	Co-producing
External experts	Consulting/Co-producing

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Limited human resources leading to difficulties in forming a working group Lack of internal expertise for developing the campaign Reluctance of students or staff to attend the workshops due to misunderstanding of the topics. Lack of interest of external stakeholders to participate. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Clear allocation of tasks to avoid overload or confusion of working group Engagement of external experts for the development and implementation Developing (and communicating) clear description of the content and objectives of the workshops and panel discussion. Using the new communication strategy, invest efforts on networking and capitalise on existing collaborations to prepare impactful local events. Co-organisation of the event with an influential actor will be considered.

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Communications Department External experts Student Union Staff representatives	List of team members	Human resources	September 2024
2. Development of awareness-raising campaign	Working group (as formed in the previous step)	Detailed plan	Human resources	October 2024
3. Design of the awareness-raising campaign	Working group	Communication material and material for the awareness-raising activities (e.g. presentations for info-sessions)	Multimedia tools Human resources	October – November 2024
4. Seeking approval	Working group Senior management	Approved awareness-raising plan	Human resources	November 2024

5. Launching the awareness-raising activities	Working group External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	December 2024 – February 2025
6. Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)	Human resources	February 2025

GA5 – Establishing a gender audit and monitoring mechanism

This Grounding Action aims to create a gender audit and monitoring system and pilot the new data collection processes in a selected area of priority.

No changes were made.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Data collection and monitoring

Thematic: Gender balance in leadership and decision-making; Gender equality in recruitment and career progression

b. Objectives

- To construe a comprehensive image regarding the organisation's and faculty's current datasets related to gender equality
- To conduct a needs assessment and analysis of the state-of-play in the institution
- To adopt a holistic approach in gender audit which includes the collection of qualitative and quantitative data, addresses aspects of intersectionality and considers the sports context

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this GA:

1. Creation of a working group and assignment of roles in a clear manner to capitalise on relevant expertise and avoid confusion in task implementation.
2. Review and analysis of existing datasets at the University to map what is already being collected. Focus is placed on methods, competent body and frequency of the gender audit. Identification of gender data gaps.
3. Defining suitable data collection and analysis methods and responsible institutional body. Selection of a suitable repository tool and defining the frequency of progress monitoring. Identification of criteria for the recruitment of participants
4. Development of tools for data collection on the two selected thematic areas, making sure to incorporate intersectional and sports-sensitive aspects. Both quantitative (e.g. statistical information and questionnaire) and qualitative (e.g. focus groups, interview) methods will be used and different target groups will be identified. External consultation may be needed at this stage.
5. Carrying out a pilot round of the defined data collection processes (e.g. survey and focus group) on this specific thematic area.
6. Analysis of the collected data and report on findings.
7. Reflection upon the efficiency of the selected tools and refinement for future use.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Mid-level management	Consulting
Ethics Committee	Co-producing
Student/Staff	Informing
HR	Consulting
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of understanding • Low engagement (due to limited time, inadequate efforts for the recruitment of participants, little interest on GE, reluctance to share views) • Internal resistances (to identify the need or value of a gender audit or to give prominence to latent inequalities) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing (and communicating) clear description of the objectives of the data collection • Clear compliance with GDPR explained in information sheet and consent form accompanying the questionnaire/interview guide • The preceding GA1 will raise awareness on the topic and importance of GE and create the basis for the successful implementation of this action

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team Ethics Committee HR	List of group members	Human resources	September 2024
2. Review and analysis of existing datasets	Working group	List of identified gaps	Human resources Software	October 2024
3. Defining data collection, analysis and recruitment methods/tools	Working group	Methodological plan for the collection and analysis of data List of recruitment criteria and recruitment methods	Human resources	October – November 2024
4. Development of data collection tools	Working group External experts	Interview guide and/or Questionnaire	Human resources Consultation time with experts	November 2024
5. Pilot round of data collection	Working group	Number of respondents/participants Number of interviews Feedback from personal meetings and focus groups	Human resources Communication tools for recruiting participants Venue Software	December 2024 – February 2025
6. Data analysis	Working group	Report on findings	Human resources	February 2025
7. Assessment and refinement of employed tools	Working group	Number of respondents Quality/sufficiency of collected data	Human resources	March 2025

GA6 – Establishing internal structures and procedures for GBV prevention and treatment within the institution

This Grounding Action consists in the development of a Protocol for preventing and addressing GBV incidents at the University, and the establishment of the necessary structures for the implementation of the Protocol.

In the implementation plan on the development of the protocol we also included extra trainings for scope and guiding principles, reporting procedures, support services within and outside the University. We also discuss and use the information from external stakeholders about GBV during the Local event “GENDER EQUALITY IN SPORTS - RIGHTS AND OPPORTUNITIES” on 14 November 2024.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Dedicated resources

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- Development of a comprehensive protocol for preventing and addressing GBV cases within the faculty.
- Definition of gender-based violence content and fundamental principles regarding reporting of relevant incidents
- Creation of a culture of zero tolerance towards gender-based violence and sexual harassment.

c. Implementation plan

The following steps will be followed for the implementation of this GA:

1. Thorough assessment of existing policies and practices related to GBV prevention and treatment and of their alignment with the national and European legislation.
2. Identification and appointment of competent body for handling reports on GBV incidents. This could involve the creation of a new body (e.g. person of trust) or the delegation of these tasks to existing bodies (e.g. Ethics Committee or the newly established GE Committee)
3. Development of the Protocol, which shall include: a) scope and guiding principles, b) prevention measures, c) reporting procedures, d) support services within and outside the University, e) investigation procedures, and f) violation consequences.
4. Seeking approval of the new GBV Protocol and related procedures.
5. Training of persons/Committee members in charge of implementing the protocol on what is gender-based violence and its specificities, for example, understanding trauma and implementing a victim-centred approach.
6. Preparation for the implementation of the Protocol - Establishment of the stipulated procedures.

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing

Senior management	Informing
Ethics Committee	Consulting
Legal Department	Consulting
IT Department	Co-producing
External experts	Consulting

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Resistance in admitting that GBV is an important issue and of the urgency to adopt measures for preventing and combatting such cases Limited resources (financial, human, time) for developing and maintaining internal structures and procedures. Potential legal or regulatory constraints in establishing certain procedures. Reluctance of management to allocate resources for a new procedure 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> One-on-one meetings between the SUPPORTER project team and the management in order to explain in detail the extent of GBV and the alarming numbers of unreported cases worldwide, combined with compounding vulnerabilities in the sports context Appointment of the GE Committee or the Ethics Committee as the competent body for handling GBV cases (instead of external recruitment)

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Assessment of existing policies/priorities	Project team Legal Department Ethics Committee	Summary of existing policies/gaps	Human resources	October 2024
2. Appointment of competent body	Project team Legal Department Ethics Committee	New position Description of responsibilities	Human resources Financial resources for the new position (if necessary)	November 2024
3. Development of the Protocol	Project team Ethics Committee External experts (if necessary)	Protocol document	Human resources	December 2024 March 2025
4. Seek approval for the new Protocol	Project team Senior management	Approved Protocol-reporting mechanism	Human resources	January 2025

5. Training of the competent body for GBV incidents	Project team External expertise	Participation in training session	Human resources Financial resources for capacity-building in external trainings	March-February 2025
6. Establishment of new procedures	Project team IT team Communications Department	New structures in place and operational	Human resources Software/technological equipment	February – April 2025

GA7 – Raising awareness on GBV and sexual harassment in sports environment with internal and external stakeholders

This grounding action develops and implements awareness-raising activities on GBV and sexual harassment in sport environments both at university and at local/national level.

We add one awareness-raising activity with LLL Department with 2 groups – Specialty of Sport training and Specialty of Physical education on February 2025 because we see interest during the Local event on 14 November 2024.

a. GEP element

Mandatory: Training and awareness-raising

Thematic: Measures against gender-based violence, including sexual harassment

b. Objectives

- To increase understanding both of internal and of external stakeholders on forms of gender-based violence (physical, sexual, psychological, economic and financial, sexual harassment, online) in the sports context
- To create a safe environment and a culture of respect, equality and zero tolerance towards gender-based violence
- To introduce staff and students to the relevant regulatory framework and internal procedures in place (reporting and case management, support mechanisms) in a simple and comprehensive manner

c. Implementation plan

The following activities will be carried out to implement this Grounding Action:

1. Setting up the working team (incl. students and/or staff, and a communication team to engage external stakeholders effectively)
2. Development of a comprehensive scheme (Define objectives and message, target audience, timeframe and budget, outline the campaign's activities and desired outcome)
3. Design the material for the planned activities (define appropriate channels, create the visuals, prepare the presentations)

4. Launching the awareness-raising activities. This includes: a) 1 workshop organised for staff, b) 1 workshop organised for students and c) 1 local stakeholder event to raise awareness of targeted external stakeholders such as sports clubs, trainers, associations, umbrella organisations, public authorities.
5. Evaluate the scheme's impact and explore possibility for future relaunch

d. Stakeholders involved

Stakeholder	Level of participation
Project team	Co-producing
Communications Department	Co-producing
GE Committee	Co-producing
Student Union	Consulting
Mid-level management	Informing
External experts	Consulting/Co-producing

e. Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Reluctance of staff and students to attend the training and workshops • Lack of interest from younger students • Difficulty in engaging external stakeholders 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developing (and communicating) clear description of the content and objectives of the training and workshops • For freshly enrolled students -making the workshop obligatory as the first introductory class at the beginning of academic year. • Co-organisation of the external event with a key external collaborator (e.g. sports association, the National Olympic Committee)

f. Timeline

Activity	Responsible actor	Success criteria	Required resources	Timeline
1. Setting up the working group	Project team GBV body Communications department Student Union Staff representatives	List of group members	Human resources	February 2025

2. Development of awareness-raising scheme	Working group	Detailed plan	Human resources	January – February 2025
3. Design of the awareness-raising scheme	Working group	Communication material Material for the awareness-raising activities	Multimedia tools, Human resources.	February 2025
4. Launching the awareness-raising activities	Working group External experts (if needed)	Number of planned events Number of participants in each event Number of individuals reached through communication tools	Communication platforms Multimedia tools Human resources Venue Financial resources for guest speakers	March – May 2025
5. Evaluating impact	Project team	Increased knowledge through pre/post workshop questionnaire Satisfaction of participants in feedback forms Level of engagement with campaign content (e.g. likes, shares, comments)	Human resources	June 2025

Transitional action: 4I-GEP institutional approval

Objective: to secure formal institutional commitment to the 4I-GEP through a structured approval process, and ensure the lasting effect of the roadmap's achievements.

Implementation plan

The new GEP I have to approve in the Senate of University. I have to present it before around two weeks before for the consulting with faculties and other members of Senate.

Potential obstacles

Obstacles	Mitigation measures
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Busy timetable • Time to put the GEP on the Senate 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Working • Hard working with work group and members of SUPPORTER project

Timeline

Activity (Step)	Involved stakeholders	Required resources	Timeline
Developing the new GEP SUPES	Members of SUPPORTER project, Quality Department of University, Work groups during the SUPPORTER Project	<i>Timetable of members, timetable of students and academic staff.</i>	<i>February – March 2025</i>
Last analysis of the new GEP SUPES Consultation of the new GEP in the departments	Members of SUPPORTER project, Quality Department of University, members of Etic Committee of University, members of work groups during the SUPPORTER project.	<i>Timetable of members, timetable of students and academic staff</i>	<i>April 2025</i>
Approving the new GEP SUPES	Members of SUPPORTER project, Dean of Faculty of Physical Education and Sport	<i>Timetable of members, timetable of academic staff</i>	<i>May 2025</i>
<i>Approving the new GEP SUPES in the Senate SUPES</i>	Members of SUPPORTER project, Dean of Faculty of Physical Education and Sport, Quality Department of University, members of Etic Committee of University,	<i>To present the new GEP before 2 weeks of the Senate</i>	<i>June 2025</i>

Annex III – GEP checklist

Addressing the key steps for developing/updating your GEP

Topic	Questions to reflect upon
Step 1: Getting started	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Have you conducted a situation analysis to assess the current gender equality status at our institution? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you identified key internal and external stakeholders? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you taken into account any other institutional policies related to gender equality?
Step 2: Analysing and assessing the status quo	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Have you collected sex-disaggregated data across key areas (e.g. leadership positions, students' enrolment in different levels of study, administration)? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you reviewed policies, procedures, and practices to detect inequalities? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you analysed the findings from your roadmap implementation to identify what actions need to be continued, nuanced or improved within your new GEP?
Step 3: Setting up the GEP	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Have you identified clear objectives? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you linked objectives to specific actions, measures, and indicators? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you identified target groups for each action? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you set a timeline for implementation? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you identified to which thematic GEP element are your actions related (work-life balance and organisational culture, recruitment and career progression, leadership and decision-making, GE in research and education) <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Is the new GEP available both in the national language and in English? <input type="checkbox"/> Has the new GEP been formally approved? <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Are there funds specifically allocated to gender equality in your new GEP? <input type="checkbox"/> Does your new GEP allocate human resources for the implementation of its actions? <hr/> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> <input type="checkbox"/> Are leadership and key decision-makers going to be actively involved in the GEP implementation? <input type="checkbox"/> Is your GEP dynamic and flexible, like your roadmap?

Step 4: Implementing the GEP	<input type="checkbox"/> Are there plans for training and awareness-raising?
Step 5: Monitoring and evaluation	<input type="checkbox"/> Have you set up mechanisms for monitoring progress? <input type="checkbox"/> Have you defined process, output, outcome and impact indicators? <input type="checkbox"/> Are findings from monitoring efforts going to be used to refine and improve interventions?

Incorporating the 4Is

Intersectionality

- Is your GEP intersectional?
- Have you considered multiple and overlapping inequalities in your data collection process?
- Did you include measures to support underrepresented groups in your institution in the intersection with gender?
- Does your new GEP promote diverse representation in decision-making in your institution (e.g. consultation/members from various ethnic, disability, socioeconomic backgrounds etc.)?
- Does your new GEP ensure that the modules which address gender equality aspects integrate an intersectional perspective?

Impact

An impactful GEP entails a growing institutional capacity of the organisation for gender mainstreaming along a number of pre-identified intermediate stages and themes for change. Twelve key themes have been identified: core team of change agents; capacity/skills of the change agents for driving institutional change for gender equality; leadership actively committed to gender equality/gender mainstreaming; availability of resources; data collection and statistical analysis; involvement of internal stakeholders; involvement of external stakeholders and experts; coverage of the different dimensions/areas of gender equality; Institutional change; transparency and accountability; institutional policy-making based on robust understanding of gender equality; organisational culture; and organisational governance.

- Is your GEP likely to have impact on your institution and beyond?
- Have you developed clear objectives?
- Is each objective linked to specific measures and actions?
- Have you linked the measures to specific targets and indicators (outputs, outcomes, impacts)?
- Is the GEP Committee implementation adequately trained?

- Have you involved external stakeholders and experts in the development process?
- Have you included a dissemination and communication strategy for your actions?

Inclusiveness

GEPs should address inclusiveness in its design, implementation, and evaluation in the following forms: 1) inequalities and inclusivity by considering other sociocultural factors in relation to gender+ such as race, ethnicity, age, sexuality, disability etc.; 2) geographical inclusiveness by recognising the local and regional differences between organisations and enabling knowledge transfer from more advanced to less experienced organisations; 3) internal inclusiveness by engaging internal stakeholders ranging from students, administrative and academic staff to top management; and 4) intersectoral inclusiveness by engaging external stakeholders.

- Is your GEP inclusive with regard to its design and implementation?
- Have you engaged a diverse range of stakeholders in its development and in the implementation plan?
- Are your policies and actions accessible to all (disability-friendly, language-inclusive)?
- Do your measures foster an open and safe culture for all genders?

Innovation

An innovative GEP entails the implementation of measures that demonstrate originality and creativity in fostering gender equality. This may involve introducing new ideas, concepts, and intersections; employing advanced participatory methods; forming unconventional partnerships; or implementing targeted actions to address emerging challenges. In other words, an innovative GEP offers out-of-the-box solutions to address common GE issues, while being inclusive, intersectional and impactful.

- Is your GEP innovative in terms of concepts, methods, and partnerships?
- Have you introduced new methods, tools, or participatory approaches regarding GE?
- Does your plan challenge traditional gender equality frameworks?
- Are you integrating best practices from other institutions or sectors?

Embedding measures against gender-based violence

- Does your new GEP examine the prevalence of all forms of gender-based violence in your institution?
- Does your new GEP have organisational policies in place to combat gender-based violence?
- Does your new GEP have a protocol for reporting and investigating GBV cases?
- Does your new GEP include measures for the support of gender-based violence victims?

- Does your new GEP foresee regular trainings and awareness-raising activities to help create a culture of zero tolerance for gender-based violence?
- Are the reporting mechanisms ensuring protection of victims from retaliation (e.g. failing marks in a module etc.)?

Tailored to sports environment

- Does the curriculum include discussion on gender stereotypes in sports, leadership and media representation?
- Are students, coaches and staff educated on gender bias in sports through trainings, coursework and awareness-raising activities?
- Are gender stereotypes in the portrayal of athletes/coaches addressed?
- Are gender stereotypes in sports participation explained and addressed?
- Does your new GEP include measures to increase women's representation in coaching and sports management roles?
- Does your GEP consider work-life balance challenges specific to coaching, training and sports academia (e.g. career break due to parental leave)?
- Does your GEP address gender-based violence specifically in the sports environment (e.g. coach-athlete relationship, harassment in training facilities etc.)?

Annex IV – New 4I-GEPs

The 4I-GEPs are attached in pdf form in this report, in the following order:

1. University of Banja Luka (UNIBL)
2. University of Ljubljana (UL)
3. Charles University (CU)
4. National Sports Academy “Vassil Levski” (NSA)
5. Lithuanian Sports University (LSU)
6. Universitatea de Vest din Timisoara (UVT)
7. Georgian State Teaching University of Physical Education (GSTUPES)
8. State University of Physical Education and Sport (USEFS)

